

شناسنامه اثر

Identity impression

«This article has been translated into French, German, English, and Russian languages»

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"A Comparative Analysis of Sartre's Atheistic Revolt and Marx's Dialectical Materialism versus Kierkegaard's Leap of Meaning and Tillich's Ontological Depth in Overcoming Existential Crises"

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Abstract:

Existentialism, as a response to the emptiness and mortality of human existence, has taken different paths in the thought of theistic and atheistic philosophers. While Sartre's existentialism is based on the negation of God, ontological rebellion, and the autonomy of the individual, and Marx sees human alienation in material and historical structures, Kierkegaard introduces the leap of meaning as a faith-based and metaphysical belief, and Tillich offers an ontological theology in response to existential anxiety. With a comparative analysis of existentialist responses to the human condition, focusing on the atheistic existentialism of Jean-Paul Sartre and the dialectical materialism of Karl Marx, in contrast to the theistic existentialist views of Søren Kierkegaard and Paul Tillich. Sartre's revolt of subjectivity and the negation of divine meaning are examined alongside Marx's view of human alienation as having socio-economic roots. On the other hand, Kierkegaard's "leap of meaning" is analyzed as a metaphysical act of faith, and Tillich's ontological depth as a theological response to existential anxiety. This study shows how each of these thinkers confronts crises of freedom, emptiness, and authenticity, and what distinct philosophical frameworks they offer for understanding existential suffering and the possibility of transcendence. This comparative study not only illuminates the ideological ruptures between atheistic and theistic existentialism, but also reveals the possibility of their co-speech within a broader philosophical dialogue. This article attempts to explore existentialist themes such as freedom, meaning, alienation, and authenticity in the thoughts of Jean-Paul Sartre and Karl Marx on the one hand, and Søren Kierkegaard and Paul Tillich on the other, and examines these approaches not only as conflicting systems but also as possibilities for dialogue within the existentialist tradition. Finally, this article attempts to show whether existential crises should be sought in faith, material transformation, or existential courage, and through these questions, to achieve a deeper understanding of the meaning of existence in the contemporary philosophical landscape.

Keywords: Existentialist- Dialectic- Materialism- Sartre-Kierkegaard-Tillich-Leap of Meaning-Subjective

Introduction:

From the mid-nineteenth century to the mid-twentieth century, existential philosophy or existentialism emerged as a profound response to the spiritual, moral, and metaphysical crises of modern man. Instead of relying on comprehensive rational systems, this stream of thought addressed the existential situation of the individual, the experience of anxiety, freedom, and responsibility, and attempted to search for the meaning of life in the loneliness and unanswerability of existence. In the meantime, existentialism found a two-

pronged path: one in the form of atheistic thought with representatives such as Jean-Paul Sartre and Marxist thinkers, who denied any a priori essence and divine meaning; And the other in the form of religious existentialism, with thinkers such as Søren Kierkegaard and Paul Tillich, who spoke of the possibility of faith, meaning, and ontological depth in the midst of darkness and existential anxiety. Sartre, by emphasizing radical freedom and the rebellion of consciousness against any transcendent system, frees man from the void of meaning so that he alone can be the creator of meaning. Marx, with a materialist and dialectical interpretation of history, also considered alienation to be rooted in economic structures and sought human fulfillment in the transformation of the material world. On the other hand, Kierkegaard, by proposing the concept of the "leap of faith," saw the way out of existential despair not in denying it, but in embracing it and leaping towards God. Tillich, using ontological language and existential theology, also considered existential anxiety not as a negation of meaning, but as a sign of its depth. In the post-Enlightenment world, with a gradual break with traditional models of meaning and truth, modern man found himself confronted with spiritual emptiness, existential anxiety, and ontological crises. In the midst of these conditions, existentialist philosophy emerged as a profound and thoughtful response to the tragic situation of modern man; a movement that sought identity, freedom, responsibility, anxiety, faith, and meaning not in a priori and general systems, but in the lived experience of the individual. However, this movement itself divided into two important branches: one based on faith and theology, and the other based on atheism, materialism, and rebellion against any transcendental foundation. Jean-Paul Sartre, a prominent representative of atheistic existentialism, considered man to be an undefined being abandoned in a meaningless world. From his perspective, "existence precedes essence"; that is, man first exists, then creates his essence through choice and action. Sartre not only denies any divine essence or metaphysical end, but also considers human freedom to be absolute and burdensome; to the point where he bears the responsibility for his entire existence. He considers anxiety to be the inevitable result of this freedom and the meaning of life to be something that can be created by the individual himself, not discovered by an external system. Karl Marx, although he was raised in the dictionary of classical German philosophy, also analyzed the world not from the perspective of existence or meaning, but from the perspective of production relations, economics, and material structures with a fundamental turn. Marx's dialectical materialism considered man to be the product of history and class relations; of self-alienation not as a metaphysical matter, but as a result of capitalist exploitation. In Marx's thought, human liberation lies not in faith or inner leap, but in social revolution and the realization of a classless society. Thus, the meaning of life in the material world and its changing structures are redefined. On the other hand, Søren Kierkegaard, the Danish philosopher and founder of religious existentialism, criticizes modern absolute rationality and abstract

systematizations, emphasizing personal experience, anxiety, despair, and the “leap of faith.” He believes that only by fully accepting and overcoming existential despair can man reach the “stage of faith”; A faith that is not based on reasoning, but on the basis of paradox, risk, and a living relationship with God. For Kierkegaard, the meaning of life is possible only in an inner and personal relationship with the transcendent. Paul Tillich, a German philosopher and theologian, also, following the tradition of religious existentialism, reinterpreted traditional theological concepts from an ontological perspective. He considered existential anxiety to be an inherent thing and a sign of man's inescapable situation in the face of nothingness. In his view, faith is interpreted not as belief in a set of propositions, but as "ultimate surrender" to the foundation of existence. By combining Heidegger's philosophy, existential analysis, and theological concepts, Tillich attempted to show that man can only understand the depth of existence by truly confronting emptiness; Where God manifests as the “foundation of being.” By looking at these four schools of thought in a comparative way, one can discern the lines of tension between faith and atheism, meaning and emptiness, matter and spirit, and the individual and history. The present article aims to examine the contrasts, overlaps, and philosophical openings in response to the crisis of contemporary human meaning through a comparative analysis of Sartre’s atheistic rebellion, Marx’s dialectical materialism, Kierkegaard’s leap of faith, and Tillich’s ontological depth. This article aims to examine these two opposing poles in the thought of four prominent thinkers from a comparative perspective: Sartre’s atheistic and deconstructive rebellion, Marx’s materialist critique, versus Kierkegaard’s and Tillich’s faith-centered and metaphysical responses. The goal of this analysis is not simply to show the contrast, but rather to search for the possibility of dialogue and mutual understanding between the two main strands of existentialism; so that perhaps, amidst the conflict or coexistence of these views, new light can be shed on the crisis of the meaning of modern man.

Jean-Paul Charles Aimard Sartre

A handwritten signature in black ink that reads "JP Sartre". The signature is written in a cursive, flowing style with a large, prominent 'S'.

Jean-Paul Sartre was one of the most influential thinkers of the 20th century; a philosopher, writer, playwright, social critic, and intellectual whose name is associated with the philosophy of existentialism and phenomenology. He was born in Paris in 1905 and grew up in a cultured family. He lost his father as a child and spent his childhood in isolation, in his grandfather's house and among books. From the very beginning, signs of literary and philosophical genius appeared in him. Sartre continued his studies in

philosophy at the École supremaire de Paris and in 1929, when he ranked first in the philosophy exams, his name was mentioned among the intellectual elite of France. In the same year, he met Simone de Beauvoir; a French writer, philosopher, and feminist who became his lifelong intellectual and emotional partner. Despite a deep and lasting relationship, the two never married and experienced a certain kind of free and unconventional life, which was sometimes accompanied by side effects and criticism. After a period of teaching in French high schools, Sartre went to Germany and became acquainted with the thoughts of Edmund Husserl and especially Martin Heidegger. This acquaintance initiated his serious entry into the world of phenomenology and the philosophy of the originality of existence. His return to France was accompanied by the writing of important works, the most famous of which are the novel *Nausea* (1938) and the philosophical book *Being and Nothingness* (1943). In these works, concepts such as freedom, anxiety, emptiness, and human responsibility are raised. He believed that "man is condemned to freedom," meaning that man must always choose one of the choices and be responsible for its consequences. In the field of literature, Sartre also wrote numerous works, including plays such as *Flies*, *Dirty Hands*, and *Closed Doors*, in which he also depicted his existentialist concerns. He also published a collection of short stories entitled *The Wall*. Sartre always tried to take philosophical thought out of the academic world and make it current in artistic and political forms. For this reason, in the middle and final decades of his life he was known more as a political intellectual. He supported communism, although he never joined the French Communist Party, and he took clear positions against dictatorships and inequalities, especially in Latin America, Algeria, Vietnam, and even Iran. He defended the rights of refugees, political prisoners, and revolutionary movements, and in the final decades of his life he even met with groups such as the Red Army Faction.

In 1964, he was awarded the Nobel Prize in Literature, but he refused to accept it. In a letter to the Nobel Academy, he wrote that a writer should not be attached to official institutions and should not sacrifice his intellectual independence for pride. Although he was almost unable to write at the end of his life due to blindness, Sartre remained active through interviews and contacts with the intellectual community. His death in April 1980 marked the end of the life of one of the most important and challenging thinkers of the 20th century. Some 50,000 people attended his funeral in Paris, the largest funeral for a philosopher in modern times. He was buried next to Simone de Beauvoir in the Montparnasse Cemetery. By using the language of literature to convey philosophical concepts, Sartre crossed the border between philosophy, literature and politics and left a new model for the contemporary philosopher; a model of a free, bold, social thinker and critic of institutions of power. The principles of philosophy (existentialism) are based on the originality of existence and its precedence over human nature.

When we want to talk about existentialism, we must specify what we mean. Jean-Paul Sartre, Martin Heidegger, Gabriel Marcel, Søren Kierkegaard were among the existentialist thinkers. The basis of Sartre's philosophical view of man is that he considers man to be free, and on this basis he denies any god-like force that deprives man of his free will (of course, Sartre himself believes that the existence or non-existence of God has no effect on the originality of man); Because he believes that man cannot be free and is condemned to freedom, which brings with it the responsibility of choice. Of course, this issue is completely true based on the Mu'tazilite and Ash'arite theological God, as well as the Christian theological God and the Jewish theological God. Sartre does not clearly deny God, but rather believes that God has left man to his own devices. When man is free, he must accept responsibility for every choice he makes, and it is from this insight that Sartre considers himself responsible for the world war, and here anxiety and anxiety arise when a person says to himself, since I am responsible for this, was this right and what consequences will it have that I do not know or will not see!?. Moreover, the statement that man is the creator of values has no meaning other than that life does not have the concept of "already been". Before you live, life in itself is nothing; but it is up to you to give meaning to life. "Value" is nothing but the meaning you choose for it.

Sartre's existentialist ideas, about individual freedom and responsibility, the possibility of our existence and the distance we have from ourselves, can still be important for modern philosophy. But Sartre was also a moralist, and his attempt to develop a moral theory can still be important for "post-modern" philosophy. Few philosophers have had the good fortune to witness the fame and influence of his thought in their own lifetime. But Sartre is unlike any philosopher who has ever lived.

The Philosophical Views of Jean-Paul Sartre: An Academic Analysis of Existentialism

Jean-Paul Sartre (1905–1980) is one of the key thinkers of the twentieth century, best known for his school of "existentialism," a movement that It deals with individual freedom, human responsibility, existential anxiety, and the inherent meaninglessness of the world. Sartre's philosophy is known as a branch of atheistic existentialism and is largely based on the foundation of "existence before nature," a proposition that sets Sartre's philosophy apart from many traditional schools of metaphysics.

1. Existence before nature

The starting point of Sartre's existentialism is the rejection of the traditional view of Western philosophy that man has a fixed, defined nature before birth. In contrast, Sartre argues in his seminal book *Being and Nothingness* (*L'Être et le Néant*, 1943) that: "Man's existence precedes his nature."

This means that man first "is," thrown into a world, and then constructs an identity for himself through his actions, choices, and responsibility. Unlike manufactured objects (e.g., a knife made for a specific purpose), humans have no predetermined essence or purpose.

2. Absolute Freedom and Existential Responsibility

In Sartre's system of thought, freedom is a fundamental concept; but this freedom is not a privilege but a "conviction." He writes in his famous sentence: "Man is condemned to freedom." That is, humans cannot abandon their freedom, because in every situation, even in accepting obedience to an order, the responsibility for choice rests with them. This attitude has grave consequences: the responsibility for actions, thoughts, choices, and even values rests with the individual; and no external authority, whether God, custom, or society, can justify the individual's responsibility.

3. Human Anxiety and Helplessness

In Sartre's worldview, the lack of a divine observer or transcendental meanings leads to an experience called "existential angst." Man finds himself abandoned in a world without a center and without a purpose. This anxiety is not only due to fear of the future, but also has its roots in man's perception of absolute freedom and infinite responsibility.

4. The Other and the Instrumental Gaze

In his analysis of the "relationship with the other", especially in the famous chapter "The Gaze" in *Being and Nothingness*, Sartre shows how the presence of the other affects man's self-consciousness. When man realizes that he is being looked at by the "other", he experiences himself as an object in his gaze. This experience, in Sartre's words, creates a kind of "alienation"; because man is transformed from "being for oneself" (*être-pour-soi*) to "being for another" (*être-pour-autrui*).

5. The Badaini in Ethics and the Choice of Values

Sartre believes that there are no absolute moral values and that man must create his own values through free choice. But these choices are not merely individual. He writes: "When I choose something for myself, I have in fact chosen it for all men." In this sense, an individual choice carries a general message and highlights the moral responsibility of the individual towards humanity.

6. Nothingness (néant) and the freedom of consciousness

One of Sartre's philosophical innovations is the analysis of the concept of "nothingness". Unlike traditional philosophers who focus on "being", he shows that consciousness is inherently defined by negation and distancing. Human consciousness always goes beyond what is and distinguishes itself from reality. This negativity of consciousness is the condition of human freedom, because it allows him to deny what is and aim for what should be.

7. Literature and Philosophy

Unlike philosophers who considered language an ineffective means of conveying meaning, Sartre considered literature a means of conveying philosophical messages. His plays and novels (including *Nausea* and *The Flies*) carry existentialist themes and represent his attempt to unite artistic form and philosophical content. Sartre's philosophy is not a closed and rigid system, but an open and evolving project that seeks to answer the most fundamental existential questions of man. His existentialism is a bold attempt to restore human dignity in a world devoid of meaning and metaphysical foundations. Ultimately, Sartre is a philosopher who invites not only to think, but also to act, write, and live in an original way.

Critique of Atheism in Sartre's Philosophy

As a being with rational power, man has always been trying to discover the truth of existence. One of the main questions that he has sought to answer is finding the origin of existence and how it came into being. In the meantime, divine religions and prophets have explained the principles of monotheism in order to answer this issue. Following the necessary existence is a common principle of all divine religions and divine philosophers, but some thinkers always consider the necessary existence to be contradictory, so that in their opinion, the existence of God cannot be proven. One of these atheist thinkers is Jean-Paul Sartre, who in his most important philosophical work, *Being and Nothingness*, has mentioned two main reasons for rejecting the necessary existence. These two reasons, which are in fact criticisms of Descartes and Leibniz's views on the necessary, one seeks to prove the contradiction of the necessary existence, and the other rejects the logical necessity of the necessary existence. He also sees the existence of God as an alien being, an obstacle to the realization of human freedom. Sartre returns freedom to human existence and considers man free from any constraints and for this reason, in his view, anything that prevents the realization of this inherent freedom cannot exist, and man has created the concept of God to escape this freedom and his responsibility. This research aims to criticize these reasons by explaining them with the foundations of the transcendent divine wisdom in which the Necessary plays a fundamental role. The need of man to

express his need for a transcendent truth, whether as a creator or as a superior power, has always had a special manifestation throughout the history of this mysterious being, so that the history of human life cannot be considered without his belief in a deity. In the meantime, there has always been a difference between the monotheists who believed in a single God and the masters of polytheistic beliefs. The divine prophets, as guides to mankind, have been trying to eradicate polytheism and disbelief from the face of human society. But when the issue of belief in God or disbelief in God takes on a rational and philosophical aspect, the defenders of each of these two beliefs try to prove their legitimacy by stating their reasons. Meanwhile, Christian philosophers even resort to rational justifications to prove and rationally justify the irrational propositions of Christianity and provide arguments to defend their beliefs. On the other hand, atheistic thinkers try to prove their views and bring them closer to the truth. Jean-Paul Sartre can be named as a thinker who not only does not hesitate to express his atheism, but also sees the existence of the necessary being as an obstacle that endangers the achievements of his philosophy. He bases his thinking on atheism. Atheism can be considered the cornerstone of Sartre's view, so that most of his philosophical principles are based on atheism, and if this foundation is removed, these principles will also be weak and baseless. In an interview, when the interviewer asks him about the two parts of the book **Words** that he wrote about God, he replies that these writings were mostly satirical or that they were expressions of the God that he was made to believe in during his education. God no longer exists for him since childhood and the question of God's existence has no longer been raised for him. In the division he makes for existentialists, he presents himself and Heidegger as atheist existentialists. This famous French thinker was able to register his name alongside the greats of thought in the 20th century by publishing literary and philosophical books. He was most influenced by Heidegger and chose phenomenology as his philosophical method. Although he attributed the basic criticisms to Husserl, the founder of this method. His most famous philosophical work, which was called the best-selling book of the 20th century in France, is called **Being and Nothingness**.

In contrast, in transcendental wisdom, the necessary existence as an indisputable and accepted principle is not only provable, but also uses the most basic arguments to prove the divine essence and attributes. In transcendental wisdom, the necessary existence is the basic principle that is the support of Mulla Sadra's philosophical system. By relying on Sadra's philosophy, we can provide a logical response to Sartre's arguments. Before stating these arguments and criticizing them in this study, we will examine the grounds of Sartre's atheism and then we will criticize his reasons for rejecting the necessary existence. In this field, some studies have been conducted that have a critical approach, but examining these

arguments based on the principles of transcendental wisdom is considered a new step. Examining these arguments based on the principles of transcendental wisdom can be useful and helpful in answering the doubts of atheists, who generally have similar reasons.

Grounds of Atheism in Sartre

Every thinker must be measured in the time and conditions in which he was present, and his thoughts must be understood. The rejection of the necessary existence can also be traced back to Sartre's life. The basis of atheism in him goes back to his childhood and the age of twelve. This atheism does not form in him all at once, but its manifestation and emergence is in the form of rejection, and it has gradually taken place in the book **Words** and is rooted in the beliefs of his family. In the book **Words**, he depicts the religious disunity that existed in his family as follows: "I was both Catholic and Protestant. On the one hand, I criticized and on the other, I obeyed. The laxity and indifference of my ancestors in religious matters led me astray due to the difference in religious beliefs, and yet I still had a light of faith in the corners of my heart: every day, without exception, I knelt before the image of God in my bed, clasped my hands together, and prayed; but I did not always remember God." The Protestant grandfather and the Catholic grandmother, the arguments over religion that took place between these two people, and The words and hadiths that arouse his disgust. These differences of opinion lead Sartre to conclude that none of them have true faith and that religion is only a tool for the capitalist class to rely on to carry out its purposes.

The place of atheism in Sartre's thought

In the process of every thought, there are some results that are obtained as a result of reasoning and are the end of thinking, but there are some assumptions and presuppositions that a person carries with him before he enters into reasoning and production. Now it must be examined whether the principle of atheism is a result of Sartre's thought system or whether it is a subjective principle. According to what he himself states in the book **Words**, the root of his atheism goes back to his twelve years of age, and at that time he reached atheism with an intuitive approach and did not give it up.

In the year 1321, in the city of Rochelle, I was waiting one morning for my friends with whom I was to go to high school. This wait was long, and to escape my loneliness, I decided to think about the power of the superpowers; but as soon as this thought took root in my brain, it came down from the air and disappeared without telling me why. When I realized it, I asked myself with a doubt mixed with fear that [he] existed, and then I thought that the matter was over. On the one hand, the matter was really over; because from then

on, I never felt any sadness or temptation to get acquainted again. Of course, it is far from fair for us to stop about a thinker in the same approach of his childhood or adolescence and to judge his entire thinking, because every thought is in a process of evolution, and this is the nature of human science that it changes and develops. But regarding Sartre, and considering what was quoted from the book **Words** and considering that this book is considered one of Sartre's later works, it seems that he still retained this childhood intuition. Although during an interview he gave towards the end of his life, he stated that he could not accept the randomness and chance of the world and declared his readiness to accept a creator (National Review, 1982: 677), no mention of this can be found in any of his works, and atheism is present as the main principle and cornerstone of his thinking in all of his works. Regardless of whether Sartre returned from his atheistic views or not, we will examine his arguments to prove his main principle in order to achieve our goal and leave that issue to an independent study.

Sartre's Arguments for Rejecting Necessary Existence

The principle of atheism is considered a given principle for Sartre, but he also uses arguments to prove this claim. Of course, sometimes he sees the existence of God as contradictory to the results of his philosophy, and sometimes he argues on the principle of necessary rejection, which in this section we are in a position to express the arguments for the rejection of necessity from Sartre's point of view and criticize them based on transcendental wisdom. The arguments that Sartre presents in this case are based on three main parts. In the first argument, it is a criticism of Descartes, who considers God to be a being who is his own creator, and in the second argument, he criticizes Leibniz, who states the logical necessity of God's existence. In the third argument, he does not directly address the transformation of God's existence, but as a result of his words. He considers the acceptance of God to be associated with the lack of human freedom, and from this association he arrives at the non-existence of God.

A) The first argument, the transformation of God's being as His creation

To enter into the discussion, it is necessary to briefly explain Sartre's view of existence. He divides existence into two aspects: in-itself and for-itself. Based on his phenomenological basis, he mentions a pure and unbroken existence that is a phenomenon, but not a phenomenon of consciousness, but has independence, and he calls this aspect of existence "being for-itself." In contrast, there is another type of existence that is not the basis of its own existence. This is the existence of consciousness, or the existence of man. The name of this type of existence is "in-itself" (ibid.: 33). This duality in the division of existence forms the basis of Sartre's philosophy. In his discussion of existence for itself, Sartre evades the necessary argument that fundamentally no being can

be the basis of its own existence after stating that existence for itself is not the basis of its own existence: Any attempt to design the thought of existence that is the basis of its own existence will inevitably lead to the creation of a thought that, while being possible as being in itself, will be the basis of its own nothingness. The act of causality, by which the self is its own cause, like any repetition of itself by itself, is an annihilating act precisely because the primary relation of existence is a return to itself and a kind of reflection, and this original being also appears on the basis of possible existence, that is, precisely the being that is in order to be the cause of itself. The basis of this argument can be summarized in this, which, according to Sartre, also lies in consciousness. When a person becomes aware of an object, there is also a self-consciousness within this same self-consciousness. In fact, consciousness is also consciousness of itself, but this same consciousness sometimes reflects on itself, in which case consciousness as a reflecter is also the object of reflection, in which case consciousness rediscovers its existence, and in light of what we said earlier in explaining the act of consciousness as annihilation, in this case consciousness annihilates itself in order to rediscover itself. This is the meaning of Sartre's statement that man is the basis of his non-existence, but not the basis of his being, because in order to be the basis of his being, that reflective consciousness must return to itself in a reflective act, but this is impossible because it means that what is being rediscovered has somehow already existed and, as Islamic scholars say, is an acquired result. These are the main problems that are The Cartesian Hume of God is taken. Of course, in this statement, Sartre has placed God's consciousness as human consciousness, and since it is placed under the title of being-for-itself in that situation, it is presented as a possibility. Sartre has introduced his argument as follows: First, he considers that the principle of creation requires having a prior nature. Having a prior nature means that the creature has a specific, definite and formed mode of existence in the mind of the creator before creation, like a knifemaker who has the shape and size of the knife in his mind before making the knife. This point means that necessary existence means an existence that is itself its own cause. Second, necessary existence means that it has created itself. Sartre's argument is stated as a criticism of Descartes' argument to prove the existence of God. Descartes uses the existence of the concept of God in the human mind, which God himself is the creator of this concept in the human mind. Because the cause must include all the perfections of the effect, and the concept of infinity that exists in the human mind can only be the effect of an infinite being, which is God. The basis of this argument can be summarized in this: According to Sartre, there is also a self-awareness in consciousness. When a human becomes aware of an object, there is also a self-awareness within this self-awareness. In fact, consciousness is also awareness of itself. But this same consciousness sometimes contemplates itself, in which case consciousness, as a thinker, is also the object of contemplation, in which case consciousness rediscovers its existence.

According to Sartre's explanation of consciousness, this act is a leap and transcendence towards the object, in which process the knowing subject annihilates himself in order to rediscover himself. In other words, when the knowing subject identifies himself, he has no specific identity other than the transcendence towards the object, and his existence is perception. This is the meaning of Sartre's statement that man is the basis of his own nothingness, but not the basis of his own existence. Because in order to be the basis of its own existence, that reflective consciousness must return to itself in a reflective act, but this is impossible because it means that what is retrieved has already existed in some way. In other words, consciousness cannot place itself as an object identity. Because in this case it must be both fixed and transcendent and move, and the result of the move is what has already existed, and this is the attainment. These forms are the same major forms that are taken in the Cartesian concept of God. Of course, in this statement, Sartre has placed God's consciousness like human consciousness, and since it is placed under the title of being-for-itself in that situation, it is presented as a possibility. With this explanation, the principle of creation requires having a prior nature. Having a prior nature means that the creature has a specific, determined and formed mode of existence in the mind of the creator before creation, like a knifemaker who has the shape and size of the knife in his mind before making it. In the case of the knife, there is no contradiction because the essence of the knife precedes its existence and belongs to consciousness, which is in the realm of existence in itself. However, in the case of God as the creator of himself, because he has conceived his essence before his existence, he is in the realm of existence for himself, and because he himself is consciousness and the knowing subject, he is explained as an existence for himself.

With these explanations, his statement can be stated with these premises: First, any creation requires prior conception and awareness of the nature of the object. Second, God created Himself, so He thought about His nature before creating it. Third, anything whose nature becomes conscious before its existence is an existing in itself and does not have consciousness, so God is an existing in itself. Fourth, God, in the assumption of creation, has conceived His own nature before His creation, so He is conscious and exists for Himself. The result is that God, while being for Himself, must also be in Himself, if it is proven that these two modes of existence are different and cannot be combined. In other words, God has two characteristics: He is conscious and He recognizes Himself, which is a characteristic for Himself. Second, He has stability and determination and is recognized, which is a characteristic for Himself. And since in his view these two types of characteristics are each for a specific part of existence and cannot be combined with each other, he considers the existence of God to be a contradiction and, in a word, the necessary must design its own essence in order to be its own cause, and this is the contradiction.

b) Criticism

The basis of this argument is based on the criticism that Sartre expresses on Descartes. We express it based on transcendental wisdom, which we also accept. God is not the cause of himself. God does not create himself, and the necessity of existence does not mean that God created himself, but rather that his essence is necessary and the assumption of non-existence is not allowed in it. The expressions that Sartre says about existence in itself, that it is pure existence, non-existence has no meaning in it, it is solid and has no discontinuity. We say the same expressions about the necessary essence, that it is pure existence and has no discontinuity. Sartre's interpretations of existence in itself are very close to the interpretations of transcendental wisdom regarding the necessary existence. For example, Mulla Sadra states in his book, *Explanation of the Necessary Essence*, that the necessary is not that which is impossible to be necessary from its absence, but rather that the necessary means that its non-existence is impossible: "The concept of the necessary is not that which necessitates the impossible non-existence, but rather that the self is the impossible non-existence." So we agree with Sartre in criticizing Descartes's view, but the conclusion drawn from this criticism is different, and it stems from a misunderstanding of the meaning of the necessity of existence. With this misunderstanding of necessity, Sartre proves that the basis of being itself is impossible and no being can be the basis of its own existence, so God cannot be the basis of its own existence, so if there is a God, it would be possible, not necessary. However, the divine sage concludes from these premises that God cannot be the basis of his own existence, so God has no basis. God is pure existence and the assumption of non-existence has no place in it. Another criticism that can be made of Sartre in this regard is that for Sartre, there is no consciousness exclusive to human consciousness. Therefore, to prove the point that the existence of God cannot be the basis of his own existence, he takes help from consciousness, which has been stated, whereas consciousness, or in other words, necessary knowledge, is like the knowledge of presence, which is briefly and in detail in Mulla Sadra's statement. Of course, this type of view of necessary knowledge will not lead to the results that Sartre seeks, and it cannot be stated through divine knowledge that the necessary cannot be its own creator. However, as stated, it can be said that this statement is the cause of the distance and acquisition of the result.

The second argument, criticism of the argument on the existence of the necessary from his possibility

The second argument for rejecting the logical necessity of the existence of God is expressed in the form of rejecting Leibniz's argument. First, he proves the possibility of God's existence as follows: A concept exists if it is possible, and to be possible it must not have a contradiction, and contradiction is in the form of negation and affirmation, and

since the concept of God only includes positive predicates, this concept is free from any negation, so no contradiction will be realized in its essence, so God is possible. The next premise of his argument is that the possibility of God's existence entails the necessity of His existence, so that, considering the meaning of possibility in Leibniz's view, since the concept of God includes all positive predicates and existence is also a positive concept, then God exists. This argument contradicts the premise of Leibniz's argument, which states that the necessary possibility necessitates His existence. If we want to express it logically, Leibniz's argument is as follows: first, the concept of God's existence is possible; second, this concept is such that its possibility of existence requires its existence, therefore God exists. Sartre divides possibility into possibility outside of existence and possibility related to existence. In an example, Sartre refers to a ball that is rolling on a flat surface on which a folded cloth is spread. It is possible for this ball to deviate in its path due to collision with these folds. The possibility of the ball's deviation is not the possibility of the ball, but arises from an ignorance of the future and from consciousness that displays its ignorance of reality in the form of a possibility. In fact, whether it is possible for the ball to deviate along the path is another form of the statement that I do not know whether the ball will deviate along the path or not. This possibility is not related to existence and is external. In fact, this possibility is related to the direction of the proposition.

But another possibility is conceivable that is related to existence. The possibility that this ball itself could not have been, its existence has no necessity. This type of possibility is always accompanied by existence and will not be separated from it. This possibility cannot have a priori status with respect to a necessary existence. Sartre says: "Being encompasses the possibilities of existence. Existence is the basis of these possibilities. Therefore, the necessity of existence cannot be free from its possibility. In a word, if there is a God, then existence is possible." Now, by explaining the two types of possibility, the matter becomes clear. The claim is that the necessary possibility necessitates its existence. Sartre says either this possibility is external to the necessary, in which case it is not a necessary possibility at all. And it is an external matter. So this possibility cannot necessitate the existence of God, but if it is said that the meaning of possibility is the same possibility of existence, then we say that this possibility cannot necessitate existence because this possibility is the same possible existence that is not separated from existence. So if there is a God, then it is possible to exist.

The premises of this argument can be stated as follows:

First, Leibniz says that the necessary possibility necessitates its existence. Second, possibility is either the possibility of existence or outside of existence. Third, if possibility is outside of existence, it cannot necessitate existence. Fourth, if possibility is related to existence, it is inseparable from existence. So if Leibniz means the possibility outside of

existence, the necessary is not an existence, and if it is the possibility of existence, then the necessary is not an existence, and if a God is assumed, it will be possible.

d) Criticism

Like the first argument, this argument also carries a relatively correct criticism of Leibniz's argument, but the conclusion drawn from it is not correct. The criticism that the possibility of God necessitates His existence is a false premise, a correct criticism, but drawing the conclusion that even if there is a God, He is possible to exist is a misunderstanding. What we must state in this explanation based on transcendental wisdom is that the necessary essence does not receive its necessity from possibility in any way. The approach to the necessary existence is not through the assumption of the possibility of its existence, but in the way of the truthful, the necessary existence is a primary matter in the conclusion, without any mention of the necessary possibility in the premises. Even according to Allamah Tabataba'i (may Allah have mercy on him), the necessary essence of the Almighty does not need to be proven and is an obvious matter, and if an argument is presented, it is for the purpose of punishment, not proof. To prove this claim, they use an obvious proposition that "there is a reality." Now, in the next stage, for this principle of reality that exists and must have an instance, it is said that not every being can be an instance of this reality because the assumption of its non-existence does not lead to a contradiction. For example, if this table does not exist, the general principle of reality is not violated. Even if all humans or living beings in the world do not exist, this principle is still not violated. But there is a violation when we say that there is no being in this world that does not have the necessity of existence, that is, there is no being whose non-existence cannot be assumed. In that case, this obvious principle of "there is a reality" is violated. Then we use this obvious proposition that the principle of reality is necessary, eternal, and necessary by nature. In fact, in this way, the possibility of having the necessary is a given for Sartre, while it was previously stated that possibility is one of the necessities of essences and the necessary essence has no nature. Considering this basis, it can be stated that according to the principles of transcendental wisdom, this argument of Sartre is also very baseless and baseless because its basis is the possibility of necessity, while it was stated that the necessity cannot be given possibility in any way. Of course, possibility has different meanings, and what Sartre means is that it is related to existence and non-existence or essential possibility. But it seems that Leibniz can somehow answer Sartre: that possibility has a more general meaning than the equator of relation, which is the absence of transformation. Apparently, in Leibniz's words, possibility is taken in this general meaning, and in this case, Sartre's objections do not apply to him because it can also include the necessary existence. If we want to answer with Sartre's literature, we must say that this possibility is related to existence itself, and this existence is necessary and

possible in the sense that its existence is not impossible. In addition to all these criticisms, it can be said that Sartre's argument is much more specific than the claim. By stating these things, he seeks to prove the transformation of the necessary existence, whereas, assuming correctness, he has rejected a distorted argument from the arguments on the necessary existence, and this will not harm solid arguments such as the proofs of the righteous.

Third argument: God prevents the realization of freedom

Sartre proposes a field of existence as the existence of the other, which he borrowed the principle of this term from Hegel. The existence of the other is the existence of others. It was stated that Sartre explains human existence with consciousness and considers it to be constantly changing. This consciousness has an object that is always something in itself. In itself, it is the same as stability. Now suppose a conscious being makes another conscious being aware of it, in that case that object (the object of consciousness) is no longer for itself, so it cannot be free because being free is incompatible with being in itself. This existence for itself that makes us aware of itself is the other in Sartre's literature. He proposes the existence of the other as an obstacle to freedom, and for this purpose uses the term gaze. The other constantly makes man an object, and in that case man is no longer as an object for himself because he is his object and has no freedom. The only thing that man can do at this time is to make the other his object. In Sartre's view, the existence of another, in addition to causing suffering, as can be seen from his play *The Retreat*, is also the determinant of his existence. Man as a self cannot reflect on himself and become aware of himself, and he cannot determine himself and recognize his essence through the gaze of another and from his gaze. God, in Sartre's view, is the other who constantly sees man, but man is unable to see him, which is why man cannot make him his object. Accepting the existence of God means accepting a permanent limitation that deprives man of freedom through his gaze, but man cannot do this in return. In this denial, he has gone so far as to consider the denial of God as a logical requirement for achieving freedom and liberty, and since freedom is introduced as the essence of man, the denial of God is necessary. Talking about man's freedom in relation to God is meaningless; Because man is a pure object in front of God and, like other objects, he lacks any freedom. God's gaze gives meaning to man's existence and man sees himself as God saw him. A man who looks at himself through God's eyes becomes alienated from his true self, which is free from subjectivity; therefore, we can express the famous phrase from the play "Hell is other people" about God and say "Hell is God." Sartre's argument can be logically expressed as follows: First, freedom is inherent in man; second, the deprivation of the essence of the object is impossible; third, the acceptance of God leads to the deprivation of man's freedom, so the acceptance of God is impossible.

f) Criticism

In criticizing this view, it should be said that according to the anthropology of the transcendent wisdom of the human soul, in fact, there is a divine connection and belonging. God is closer to man than the jugular vein, but not as an alien, but as the original truth of man. Shahid Motahari has explained this view in this way: "A being's attachment to his ultimate end and perfection is not self-alienation, contrary to Mr. Sartre's opinion; it is more self-absorption; that is, it is more self-denial. If freedom reaches the stage where man is free even from his own end and perfection, that is, even from himself, this type of freedom brings self-alienation. This type of freedom is against human perfection. If freedom also includes the perfection of the being, that is, includes something whose evolutionary stage is existence, in the sense that I am free even from my own evolutionary stage, the imperfection of my more perfect self is free, and the concept is that I am free from my more perfect self. This freedom distances man from himself more than this dependence." According to this explanation, it becomes clear that, contrary to Sartre's thinking, the existence of God not only does not prevent man's freedom, but on the contrary, by cutting himself off from his true origin, man has actually alienated himself from himself. God's gaze on man and His companionship with man do not stop man, but this companionship is a guardian companionship that will cause man's growth and exaltation, and the more man is attentive to it, the more he will use this eternal support. What becomes evident to man by studying the works of Sartre and others like him is that the lack of a correct understanding of the Creator and the lack of communication with Him can lead a person's thinking to a place where he feels God's gaze as a heavy gaze on him, but the mystic melts into this gaze and makes love to Him. Another criticism is the introduction to the argument that he considers freedom to be inherent in man. The meaning that Sartre uses of freedom is freedom in the sense of existential independence. Of course, Sartre concludes social freedom from this freedom in the sense of existential independence and believes in a kind of association between the two. In expressing transcendental wisdom, freedom in the first sense is completely denied to man. Man is the same as the relation to the cause and the same as belonging, and is exactly opposite to freedom, but the connection between evolutionary freedom and social and individual freedom is not accepted. Man, while being the same as belonging and depending on his cause, is also free, but Shahid Motahari is trying to make the realization of individual and social freedom in the true sense conditional on the realization of spiritual freedom, namely obedience to the Creator. Intrinsic freedom, that is, existential independence for man, is by no means achievable, but this is not associated with absolute human determinism. Man, while belonging and depending on the Creator, also has free will.

Existentialism

Existentialism or existentialism is a philosophical school that refers to the works of a group of philosophers of the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. Despite profound differences in their school views, these philosophers share the belief that philosophical reflection begins with the human subject and not simply with abstract subjects. In the framework of existentialism, the starting point of the whole A philosophical L is a person defined by their "attitude to existence"; an attitude characterized by feelings of disempowerment, confusion, and the encounter with a world that is seemingly meaningless and absurd.

According to existentialists, life is meaningless unless the person himself gives it meaning. This means that we find ourselves in life. Then we decide what meaning or essence to give it. As Sartre said: We are condemned to freedom; that is, we have no choice but to choose and to bear the burden of responsibility for our choice. Existentialism is sometimes confused with nihilism, which is different from it. Nihilists believe that life has no purpose or meaning. While existentialists believe that man must create the meaning and purpose of his life himself. Existentialism is derived from the word *existence*, meaning existence. Søren Kierkegaard is considered the first existentialist in history. There is a difference between "atheistic existentialism" and "Christian existentialism". Among the best-known Christian existentialists are Søren Kierkegaard, Gabriel Marcel, and Karl Jaspers. After World War II, a new movement emerged that could be called literary existentialism. Representatives of this new movement include Simone de Beauvoir, Jean-Paul Sartre, Albert Camus, and Boris Vian.

History

Existentialism was clearly articulated by Friedrich Nietzsche and Søren Kierkegaard, philosophers from the nineteenth century. Although it also had pioneers in previous centuries. Throughout his philosophical career, Socrates repeated these two mottos: "The life that is not worth living" and "Know thyself." The first motto clarifies the nature of philosophy and the second motto clarifies the nature of existentialist philosophy. In the 20th century, the German philosopher Martin Heidegger influenced other existentialist philosophers such as Jean-Paul Sartre, Simone de Beauvoir, and Albert Camus (a nihilist whose works are similar to existentialist views, but are essentially absurdist). Fyodor Dostoevsky and Franz Kafka also incorporated existentialist concepts into their literary works. Just as there are common tendencies among existentialist thinkers, there are also differences and disagreements among them. The main difference is between existentialists who, like Sartre, deny the existence of God, and existentialists like Tillich who believe that God exists. Not all of them necessarily agreed that it was correct to apply existentialism to their works.

The term existentialism seems to have been coined by the French philosopher Gabriel Marcel in the mid-1940s and adopted by Jean-Paul Sartre, who introduced existentialism in an article he gave to the Club Metnout in Paris on October 29, 1945. His article, published as *Existentialism and the Originality of Man*, played an important role in the spread of existentialist thought. The term has been applied to other philosophers in the past whose philosophy has focused on existence, and in particular on human existence. Martin Heidegger focused his work on human existence from the 1920s, and Karl Jaspers called his philosophy the philosophy of being in the 1930s. Both were influenced by the Danish philosopher Søren Kierkegaard. For Kierkegaard, the crisis of human existence was the main concern. He is known as the first existentialist. In fact, he was the first to explicitly make existentialist questions the focus of his philosophy. Other writers have also explicitly raised existentialist themes throughout the history of philosophy and literature. In 1835, Søren Kierkegaard wrote his first existentialist text in a letter to his friend Peter Wilhelm Lund. In this text, he described the truth that is practical for him:

What seems unclear to me in my mind is what I should do, not what I should know. Except for the knowledge that precedes all action. I must understand what God really wants me to do. That is to find the truth that is true for me. To find the meaning for which I can live and die... Of course, I do not deny that I still understand the necessity of knowledge and that by it one can act beyond the rest of humanity. But knowledge must be used in my life. And now this is the most important thing in my view. Kierkegaard's early thoughts are formalized in his prolific philosophical and theological writings. And many of them form the foundations of twentieth-century existentialism.

Kierkegaard and Nietzsche

Søren Kierkegaard and Friedrich Nietzsche are two of the philosophers who are recognized as the founders of the existentialist movement. However, neither of them used the term "existentialism," and it is not clear whether they accepted or rejected twentieth-century existentialism. Their focus was on subjective human experiences rather than on the objective truths of mathematics and science. For them, the truths of mathematics and science were far removed from understanding human experience. Like Blaise Pascal, they were interested in people's silent struggle with the apparent emptiness of life and in entertaining themselves to escape the everyday. Unlike Pascal, Nietzsche and Kierkegaard considered the role of free decision-making, especially decisions that concern fundamental values and beliefs, and how such decisions change the nature and identity of the decision-maker. Kierkegaard and Nietzsche are examples of those who define the nature of their being. They were also pioneers of other intellectual movements such as postmodernism, nihilism, and various branches of psychology.

Dostoevsky and Kafka

Two of the first important literary writers in the field of existentialism, Franz Kafka and Fyodor Dostoevsky. Dostoevsky's *Notes on the Underground* tells the story of a man who cannot fit into his own society and is dissatisfied with the identity he has created for himself. Many of Dostoevsky's novels, such as *Crime and Punishment*, present concepts in the form of existentialist philosophy, and the plot lines are inspired by secular existentialism. For example, in *Crime and Punishment*, one finds the main character, Raskolnikov, going through an existential crisis and leaning towards an Orthodox Christian worldview, which is close to the one Dostoevsky wants to defend. Kafka, in his best-known short story, *The Metamorphosis*, and in his major novel *The Trial*, often created surreal and unfamiliar characters who struggle with despair and emptiness. In his philosophical essay *The Myth of Sisyphus*, Albert Camus, a French existentialist and absurdist, describes Kafka's works as fundamentally absurd. He also does not see the present as a relentless cry of hope, as religious existentialists like Kierkegaard and Cestov called it.

Early 20th Century

In the early decades of the 20th century, a number of writers and philosophers began to express existentialist ideas. The only difference between them was the name they chose for their ideas. In his 1913 book *The Tragic Sense of Life*, the philosopher Miguel de Unamuno saw life as "flesh and bones" separate from pure rationalism. Unamuno rejected systematic philosophy and believed in the individual's quest for faith. His works always have a tragic, even absurd, sense of the nature of the quest, which is a symbol of his interest in Don Quixote, Cervantes' fictional character. Unamuno was a writer, poet, playwright, and professor of philosophy at the University of Salamanca. His short story "Holy Manuel, the Martyr Benefactor," about a priest's confusion over his belief in immortality, is among the best existentialist stories. Another Spanish thinker, Ortega Ygast, wrote in 1914 that human existence must always be defined for each person and under the continuous events of his life: "I am myself and what has happened to me." Like Sartre, human existence is not an absolute subject and is always subject to circumstances. Chestoev and Nikolai Berdyaev are two Russian-Polish thinkers who became famous as existentialists after the Russian Revolution and during their exile in Paris. Chestoev was born in Kiev to a Ukrainian-Jewish family and in his book *Everything is Possible* (1905) he made sharp criticisms of rationalism and stylization in philosophy. Berdyaev was also born in Kiev but with an Eastern Orthodox background. He made a fundamental distinction between the world of the spirit and the everyday world of science. For Berdyaev, human freedom is rooted in the realm of the spirit. A realm that is not dependent on the causes and effects of scientific theories. Man living in a scientific world is alienated from the truth of the

freedom of the soul. Man should not be interpreted in relation to his physical nature. Rather, he should be seen as an image of God as the founder of free and creative action. The Fate of Man (1931) is his major work that deals with such themes. Long before Gabriel Marcel coined the term existentialism, he had introduced the important concepts of existentialism to his French audience in his essay Being and Objectivity (1925) and in the journal *Metaphysics* (1927). Marcel, a playwright and philosopher, found his philosophy to be a state of metaphysical self-alienation: "man's search for harmony in the transient life." For Marcel, harmony must emerge from the exploration of the secondary response that he has to the "dialectical" description of the world. He looks at it with "astonishment and bewilderment", and its scope is not limited to knowing about humans and God. It is achieved by considering their "presence". This presence expresses something more than simply being somewhere, as something may be in the presence of something else. For him, presence refers to the "innumerable" possibilities, and the will to be exposed to the other.

After World War II, Sartre traveled to Germany in 1930 to study phenomenology with Edmund Husserl and Martin Heidegger. He wrote critiques of their work in his seminal essay *Being and Nothingness*. Heidegger's ideas had become familiar to French philosophical circles through Alexandre Codge's use of them in his series of lectures in Paris in the 1930s on the elaboration of Hegel's ideas. His lectures were very influential. The crowd included not only Sartre and Merleau-Ponty, but also Raymond Quesno, André Breton, Georges Bataille, Louis Althusser, and Jacques Lacan. An excerpt from Heidegger's *Being and Time* was published in French in 1938, and over time his articles found their way into French philosophical journals. In the wake of World War II, existentialism became a well-known and significant philosophical and cultural movement. Especially among the general public of the two French writers, Sartre and Camus, whose theoretical articles, as well as their best-selling novels, plays, and popular magazines, had gained an important place among their audiences. It was during these years that Heidegger's *Being and Time* became famous outside of Germany. Sartre used existentialist concepts as a theme in his novel *Nausea*. In *Being and Nothingness*, he expressed the principles of his philosophy. But two years after the liberation of Paris from the Nazi occupation, he and his close associates (Camus, Simone de Beauvoir, Maurice Merleau-Ponty, and others) became world-famous as the standard-bearers of the existentialist movement. In a very short time, Camus and Sartre in particular became the leaders of the postwar French intellectuals, and by the end of 1945 they had achieved widespread popularity among the public. Camus was the editor of the very popular left-wing newspaper (the former French Resistance) *Combat*. Sartre launched his own left-wing magazine, *L'Etape Moderne*, and two weeks later gave a rousing lecture on existentialism and humanism at the intensive meetings of the "Club Metno." "There was

not a week that the newspapers did not discuss us," de Beauvoir wrote. Existentialism had become the first herald of postwar enthusiasm. By the end of 1947, Camus's old plays and novels were being revived. His new play *Caligula the Performer* and Camus' novel *The Plague* had been published. The first two novels of Sartre's *Road to Freedom* trilogy and Beauvoir's *Blood and Others* had appeared. Sartre's and Camus's works had also been translated into other languages. The Parisian existentialists had achieved international fame.

Concept

Existentialist philosophers examine human existence as a distinct species from the existence of other beings and, careful to distinguish this distinction, call human existence existence. They try to show how human existence or being in this world differs from other forms of existence. "Every new nature is valuable in itself" is a proposition that the school of the originality of existence offers about the definition of the concept of value. Accordingly, in continuation of Descartes' philosophical phrase "I think, therefore I am", Albert Camus says: "I rebel, therefore I am." This phrase, in addition to accepting the sentence that was raised about value, also has a meaning in itself. That living like the past is equal to living inauthentically. Every human being who steps into the world has specific genetic characteristics and an environment unique to that person, who as a result of these factors has a unique personality (consciousness), therefore it is valuable in itself. Here, reference is made to the precedence of human existence over his nature, and in the field of ethics, human value is separated from his performance. Here is where Jean-Paul Sartre writes: "A whole human being is made up of all human beings and has equal value to all of them, and the value of each of them is equal to him." [9] And now the question must be answered that while a cat is also unique when it is born. So why don't we give importance to the originality of the cat's existence? In answering this question, we must refer once to the Cartesian project and again to Franz Brentano's existential psychoanalysis. Descartes believed that the human ability to choose for various reasons means human creativity. This creation means creating or realizing something new that has a high value. On the other hand, Brentano in existential psychoanalysis concludes that the cat's consciousness is always of external objects. But in addition to external objects, man is also aware of himself, and this awareness distinguishes him from other beings.

Principles

Four fundamental concepts can be highlighted in existentialism: 1) the possibility of being unnecessary or accidental, 2) freedom, 3) responsibility, and 4) originality. Man does not have a priori nature that God or nature supposedly created. Man, like any being, is possible and not necessary. He creates himself and freely chooses between possible options. He is

responsible for his choices and must be able to create what he knows to be right (and not to act according to the example of everyone). In this case, he has done something original. Sartre's presentation of these points began with an ontological perspective that he himself called phenomenological ontology and was originally based on the philosophical achievement of Heidegger.

The possibility of being unnecessary

Saying that something exists raises the question of whether it exists for a specific reason, for example, according to its own nature. The existentialist response from Sartre is expressed in a literary text, through the mind of Antoine Roquentin, the central character of the novel *Nausea*:

That moment was extraordinary. I was there. Motionless and frozen. Immersed in a terrifying fascination; but right at the heart of this fascination something new appeared. I understood nausea. I was its possessor. To be honest, I had not yet defined my discovery to myself. But I think it is easier for me to express it in words now. The essential possible is the unnecessary. I mean that by definition existence is not a necessity. Being is very simply being there. Beings are revealed, they let us encounter them, but we can never infer them. I think there are people who have understood this. Only they have tried to overcome this unnecessary possible by inventing a necessary existence whose cause is assumed to be in itself. So no necessary being can explain existence. The unnecessary possible is not a false aspect that can be brushed aside. It is absolute and therefore completely uncaused. Everything is uncaused. This garden, this city, and myself.

Freedom

Man plans. At every moment, he is forced to move forward towards the future by choosing from among the set of alternatives before him. Man has no choice but to make these choices and is condemned to freedom. The only state in which we are not free is to be free not to be free. Human reality does not exist except in freedom. In the school of existentialism, freedom means the possibility of choosing. From Sartre's point of view, "we are the choice" is to exist by choosing. There is no difficult external situation that makes human freedom of choice completely impossible. Undoubtedly, situations reduce the number and variety of options, but they do not eliminate the possibility of choice altogether. Even in prison and in a camp, I am not completely deprived of the possibility of choice. I can choose whether to resist or not, to go along with the jailers and torturers or not. After the liberation of France, Sartre wrote that the French had never been as free as they were during the occupation by the Vichy dictatorship and the Resistance. Because they were free by choosing alternatives such as joining the Resistance, tolerating silence, or collaborating with the occupiers. This freedom imposed itself on them in the strict sense

of the word. No one could not decide on this matter, and every day this choice, which had to be freely formed, was before the French. As a result, they were constantly aware of their freedom and tested it. In the unshrouded dead and the burial of tortured prisoners on the verge of death, they speak of their freedom. They realize that they are free even on the night of their execution. Although it is known that man cannot choose some powerful alternatives. It is clear that there are many obstacles to individual freedom, and when freedom is mentioned as the basis of human actions, it cannot be said that I am free to do something that, in decimal terms, adds two plus two to make five. Human freedom arises from his situation in the necessity of choice. Indeed, freedom arises from limitation; because man, due to his limitations, projects and is forced to choose an option in freedom. What is meant by freedom here is that when freedom is considered the basis of my actions, the invalidity of any goal that has been determined in advance for my actions becomes apparent. I can organize myself according to the goal that I choose, or so to speak, I can create the meaning of my life myself. Along with that, I create a world and give it meaning on the basis of which I myself live. The issue of freedom is not well understood unless the concept of the originality of existence is understood from the concept of the situation. Man is constantly in various situations. Being thrown into the world is a fundamental situation. But seemingly less important situations also arise constantly in everyday life.

Fundamental situations

Man is inseparable from his human condition. The human condition is accompanied by several condemnations. I am condemned to be born. My being means that I have been thrown into this world. I am condemned to be born in a certain situation (as a man or a woman in a racial class, a nation, educational conditions and health facilities, etc.). I am condemned to live and work alongside others. Finally, I am condemned to die. In these fundamental situations, I do not act very freely. To say the least, my circle of freedom in this case is small and limited. If I commit suicide, I have only brought forward the time of death, but death will still be inevitable, meaning the end of my life. If I move from my country of birth to another place, I have changed the status assigned to me at birth, but I still have to live and cooperate with others in a new status assigned to me. It cannot be assumed that a person completely separates himself from his status. A pauper may become rich, a man may become a woman after surgery, or a prisoner may be released. But they will always remain a rich man who was once poor, a woman who was once a man, and a free man who was once a prisoner. The set of my statuses is my world, and I am in this sense my being in the world. The person I make of myself is inextricably linked to my plans, my work environment, and in a word, to the statuses and choices I make in these statuses. All statuses are part of the “status of statuses,” that is, “being in the world.”

Responsibility

Freedom does not provide a calm and comfortable status for man. The anxiety of making the right choice is constantly alive in us. We always feel the responsibility of whether what we have chosen is the best possible choice for ourselves, our loved ones, and the advancement of our plans and ideas, and we will face it as long as we are alive and will not be comfortable and relaxed. Choice is never easy. If it is true that human existence precedes his essence, then human beings are responsible for who they are. This does not mean that human beings are responsible for their own individuality, but for all human beings. Responsibility in existentialist philosophy goes hand in hand with freedom. To say that each person is responsible for their own choices in which and with which they have exercised or tested their freedom means that the person is responsible for their actions. Being committed to their own choices means recognizing them as correct actions. According to Sartre, recognizing the choice as correct should have a meaning outside the scope of relativism. He says that each person should be able to explain their choices to others and be accountable for them. The word *responsabilite*, meaning responsibility, is derived from the French word for response, and both go back to the Latin response. The Arabic and Persian word *respodere*, also means someone who is asked a question and must answer, and the infinitive and noun infinitive of responsibility also come from the infinitive of question. Heidegger was responsible for his own choice when he became a member of the Nazi Party and opposed the killing of Jews in death camps and The crematorium remained silent. Sartre was responsible for his many years of silence about the existence of concentration camps in countries that called themselves socialist. Each of us is responsible for the formation of who we have become.

Dread

When we say that man chooses, we mean that each of us chooses, we also say that each of us, by his choice, chooses all men. Each of our actions in creating who we want to be, at the same time creates an image of man as we think he should be. Choosing to become this or that is an affirmation of the value that we choose. In this way, our responsibility is much greater than we think; because my responsibility commits all humanity. In this way, I am responsible for myself and for everyone. I create a particular image of man that I have chosen myself. By my choice, I have chosen everyone.

Misconception

Freedom is so closely associated with responsibility, obligation, and fear that most people refuse to recognize or use their freedom. This Sartrean view is one of the arguments that has become known to us as the “escape from freedom.” Most people, knowing that they must accept responsibility for their free choices, prefer to take refuge in the arms of someone who chooses and decides for them, a powerful and unmonitored force, a

patriarchal tyranny that, no matter how much it forces them, at least has the advantage of reducing the evil of free choice. Sartre wrote in his Notebooks on Ethics that people like slavery and allow themselves to be treated like objects. A good example of this is the belief in conspiracy theories by most people. Most people prefer to think that those who have all the power in their hands decide the fate of others. Thus, there is no possibility of free decision-making or choice for such people.

Authenticity

Sartre explained that a complete break with false belief is impossible, but one can be true to oneself “in a way that we call authentic.” Heidegger did not consider any kind of morality to be authentic morality. For this reason, he had set aside the discussion of ethics. In his view, authenticity could not be considered a moral presupposition. Authenticity meant the act of Dasein. Not behaving like “everyone else,” and as such discovering and following one’s own path. For Heidegger, authenticity was the effort to find the right path. Can the word “right” be used here? Doesn’t this word suggest an ethical concept? According to the common meaning of ethics, the answer is no; because the discussion goes beyond the limits of an individual, an Dasein. But in another sense of ethics (i.e., considering ethics as the invention of a personal approach to life), it can be said that it was "moral." Perhaps one can mention the ethical choices of Dasein. Sartre and Emmanuel Levinas were two followers of Heidegger who considered this second meaning to be important and moved along its path. In the specific sense that Sartre had in mind for ethics, authenticity made sense to him. In the novel *Being and Nothingness*, Sartre showed that authenticity cannot be achieved. There is no authentic person in the strict sense of the word. But one can move towards authenticity. This progress is possible by choosing what I am sure of, which is my freedom, not the legacy of the past or the promise of contemporaries. One can have authentic actions, that is, choose options contrary to false beliefs. Man is not perfect, he is not like Spinoza's God who has reached the point of perfection. Man is not perfect even when he is only of his own will, against others, against false beliefs. He is a projected reality governed by forced circumstances, but he has self-reliant actions and a “moral drive towards originality.” Sartre says that man is not what he appears to be and what others think he is. Similarly, what others think he is not is. Others aside, man is not what he is now, in reality. Because he is in the process of transformation and becoming, facing the future, and must change himself, and constantly become someone else in order to finally perhaps give an image of himself. I am a person and I cannot have the ontological perfection of things.

Sartre’s Existentialist Philosophy

The principles of existentialist philosophy are based on the originality of existence and its precedence over human nature. When we want to talk about existentialism, we must clarify what we mean. Jean-Paul Sartre, Martin Heidegger, Gabriel Marcel, and Søren Kierkegaard were existentialist thinkers. Of course, Marcel and Kierkegaard had a faith-like vision and their thoughts were not atheistic. Sartre and Heidegger are the exact opposite of these two, who had atheistic thoughts. The basis of Sartre's philosophical view of man is that he considers man to be free and on this basis he rejects God; because he believes that man cannot be free, while he has an absolute and unique creator who knew from eternity what he wanted to create. According to him: "Freedom is at the heart of all human experiences and it is freedom that distinguishes man from all other types of beings. Of course, this is completely true based on the Mu'tazilite and Ash'arite theological God, as well as the Christian theological God and the Jewish theological God. When a person is free, he must accept responsibility for every choice he makes, and it is from this insight that Sartre considers himself responsible for the world war, and here anxiety and anxiety arise when the person says to himself, since I am responsible for this, is this right and what consequences will it have that I do not know or will not see!?" Sartre's existentialist thoughts, regarding individual freedom and responsibility, the possibility of our existence, and the distance we have from ourselves, can still be important for modern philosophy. But Sartre was also a moralist, and the attempt he made to propose Kurdish ethics can still be important for "post-modern" philosophy. Few philosophers have had the good fortune to witness the fame and influence of their thought in their lifetime. But Sartre is different from all philosophers who have ever lived.

Karl Marx (born 1818 in Trier, Prussia, Germany) was a German philosopher, economist, historian, sociologist, political theorist, and revolutionary socialist. He studied law and philosophy in Germany. Due to his political writings, he was stripped of his citizenship and lived in exile in London for decades with his wife and children. His most famous works are *The Communist Manifesto* and the three-volume work *Capital*. Since the mid-19th century, when Marx's numerous works were gradually published, the humanities, including philosophy, history, and sociology, have been divided into two distinct sections: before Marx and after him, with Marx or against him. He once (1848), together with his friend and colleague Friedrich Engels, said in an ideological treatise called "*The Communist Manifesto*", "A spectre is haunting Europe, the spectre of communism." That ghost may have died down, but today there is undoubtedly another ghost that still haunts the Golan: that of Marxism. As mentioned, his most famous works are *The Communist Manifesto*, one of the most influential political writings of all time, and *Capital*, an enduring masterpiece in economics. Marx was not well-known and prominent during his lifetime, but after his death he became an international icon. This article first discusses (a) the life of Karl Marx, then (b) lesser-known facts about Karl Marx, and finally (c) the

history of Marxism and the development of Marx's thought. Karl Marx was the third son of Heinrich Marx-Löw and was considered a member of the city's famous rabbis. Despite the fact that many of his predictions were refuted, his philosophical insights continue to inspire millions, and his economic approaches are a guide for those who wish to better understand the mechanisms of the modern world. Marx was born two hundred years ago and began his political and philosophical scientific struggles with his close friend, Friedrich Engels, and it was with him that he wrote the "Communist Manifesto" a year before the revolutions of 1848. During these years, Karl broke with the academic environment and German and Young Hegelian idealism and turned to the issues of the labor movement. He published the first volume of his famous book, Capital, in 1867. This book contains his views on the critique of political economy. Marx fell in love with a girl, quarreled with her father, and went with his mistress to Paris and then to London. He spent more than thirty years of his last life in London and in exile, where he died. It is worth mentioning that in 2005, in a public opinion poll of BBC radio listeners, Karl Marx was chosen as the greatest thinker of the second millennium. He won first place by a very large margin, ahead of Albert Einstein and Isaac Newton. Bertrand Russell, the famous English philosopher, believes that Marx, like Hodgkin, is on the one hand a product of philosophical radicals and continues their rational religion and their opposition to the romantics, and on the other hand a real reviver of materialist philosophy. Marx has given a new interpretation of this philosophy and has established a new relationship between it and human history. On the other hand, Marx is the last of the great system builders who succeeded Hegel and, like Hegel, believes in a rational formula that summarizes the evolution of mankind.

Marx's beliefs

As a non-religious person, Marx's father was a man of the Enlightenment who was interested in the thoughts of philosophers such as Immanuel Kant and Voltaire. Today's world knows Marx in two ways: many researchers still recognize him as a profound analyst of class systems; he ruthlessly criticized structures based on exploitation and injustice and showed the way to the liberation of the oppressed masses. At the same time, many thinkers of his political thought assess his "dangerous" because this thought was the theoretical foundation of the totalitarian and terrifying systems that caused misery and misery for countless masses along with the captivity and death of millions of people. Thus, Marx has inspired both humanist thinkers such as Antonio Gramsci and Romain Rolland and Erich Fromm, and has given the opportunity to brutal dictators such as Stalin and Mao to commit cruelty and bloodshed in his name and to establish imaginary paradises, real hells on earth. Critical criticism and analysis are the key tools of Marx's thinking and conceptualization. He does not have an independent philosophical system, does not

present a straightforward political theory of governance, does not outline how revolutions should be, and does not express a specific opinion about the characteristics of communist society. All we have of him is criticism and refutation of the philosophical or political discourse that dominated the world at that time. In economics, he first criticized the theories of the founders and defenders of capitalism and then presented his own "scientific" approaches. Although Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, Germany's most influential philosopher, had died in 1831, when Karl Marx went to Berlin to study philosophy a decade later, the academic environment was still under the influence of Hegel's philosophical system. Marx, like almost all students, joined the followers of his philosophy; but it was not long before he began to mercilessly criticize the great master's theories. To understand Marx's dialectical view of how history progresses and progresses, it is necessary to be familiar with Hegel's theories. Hegel's philosophy is very extensive and complex; But simply put, his philosophical system is a study of the process of evolution throughout the material and spiritual history of mankind, from the earliest stages of the emergence of civilization to the present day and even the future of which Hegel draws a general outline. The word Geist, whose forms and stages of development Hegel describes in his various works, can be translated as idea, thought, mind, reason, and spirit, although none of these But it encompasses all of them.

According to a long-standing philosophical tradition, Hegel considers existence, including man, as dual, that is, a totality consisting of body and soul. The human body belongs to nature and the realm of the material world; but what determines his existence is his soul, which belongs to the world of the spirit. From his perspective, human existence and history are the result of the growth and development of the spirit. This view inevitably leads to reactionary political consequences, because it considers the existing socio-political system to be the result of an upward or upward process.

According to Hegel's philosophy, nothing in the universe is fixed or stable, everything is eternally in change and transformation, and that too in an evolutionary direction. He sees nature, history, and society in an unstoppable transformation that constantly reveals the "spirit" at a higher level and in a more complete manifestation. But Hegel does not depict the process of growth or development in a simple and straightforward way or in a direct way, but on a contradictory basis and calls it "dialectic". From Hegel's point of view, every process consists of three bases or themes: thesis, antithesis and synthesis. Every situation or state, which we assume to be the initial situation, is a thesis; this thesis carries within its essence an opposing element called antithesis. The thesis and antithesis conflict with each other so much that they finally disappear but are not destroyed, but are elevated to a higher level in their combination; But this higher stage, called synthesis, does not last long, but rather becomes a new proposition or thesis to begin a new process of growth and

development, that is, it in turn encounters a new antithesis, which in their turn begins a new process in conflict with each other, and so on. After Hegel's death, his followers were divided into two wings: the right wing and the left wing. The right wing remained loyal to Hegel's mental model with all its political and social implications, the axis and purpose of which was to support the Prussian monarchy, but the followers of the left wing, who wanted the democratic transformation of the country, turned their backs on the political and social conclusions of Hegel's thought. Marx, like the left Hegelians, accepted Hegel's logic or dialectical method, but took a critical path against his idealism or philosophical theme. He said that existence correctly proceeds according to a dialectical process, but its driving force, contrary to Hegel's idea, is not idea or spirit, but matter. Matter itself is the generative of spirit and in an evolutionary process it manifests and transforms it. Thus he saw the development of the idea or spirit as a function of the development of matter and expressed this anti-Hegelian view in various ways. For example, he wrote: "Unlike German philosophy, which aims from heaven to earth, we must go from earth to heaven. It is not the thoughts and imaginations, the words and desires of men that affect their real lives; on the contrary, it is the objective deeds and activities and the conditions of man's real life that shape his thoughts and views." Marx and his close colleague Friedrich Engels formulated their achievement in *The German Ideology* as follows: Hegel's idealist philosophy was a body standing upside down, we set it on its feet, that is, we returned it to its right and natural position. Thus, from a certain period, around 1846, Marx completely turned his back on metaphysics, gave up exploring philosophical categories and ideas, and focused his attention on the material existence of man, and considered human society to be its origin or main context. It was from here that, instead of studying philosophical thoughts and ideas, he turned to the material relations of society, because he had concluded that: "Man's consciousness does not determine his existence, but it is his material life that creates his consciousness." In continuing to separate the spiritual life of society from its material foundation, he divided the elements of society into a base and a superstructure, and he believed that material affairs and structures constitute the foundation of a society, while mental patterns and structures, or what we call the culture or spiritual life of society, constitute its superstructure. To put it more clearly: the entire culture of any society, including all intellectual and mental patterns and beliefs such as philosophy, religion, ethics, and law, always follows the material conditions of that society's life. This relationship is not always obvious and straightforward, but as the material foundation of society changes, its cultural superstructure also changes sooner or later. Marx, who now turned his attention to society, attempted, following a Hegelian model, to examine the historical course of societies in the light of the functioning and development of social phenomena on the one hand, and to identify the main or determining factors in this evolutionary process on the other.

He started from the obvious principle that man is forced to work in order to meet his basic needs, to provide food, clothing, and housing, which he does in connection and cooperation with others and within a context of social relations. Through constructive work, man both transforms nature and improves his standard of living. But man does not work in a vacuum but in conditions that he has inherited from his predecessors, these conditions being: material possibilities, or the technical and productive means, and the relations that place him in contact with other producers.

Through continuous historical studies, Marx discovered that all human societies have undergone certain social formations or formations that have provided a suitable environment for human work and activity. These formations, which shape specific historical periods such as slavery and feudalism, always reflect the level of economic and technical development of the productive forces of each society.

Based on Hegel's dialectics, Marx sees each stage of social development as containing a contradiction that is constantly becoming more acute and is the real factor of its transformation and development. From the point when the relations of production come into complete conflict with the material possibilities of production and block its progress, the whole economic life falls into crisis and becomes a ground for the emergence of social inflammations. Marx, who himself lived in turbulent times, was determined to discover the mechanism of social uprisings. He realized that those who are placed in an inferior position in the relations of production as a whole, due to the unjust distribution of wealth and are naturally dissatisfied with the dominant system, form a "class" in connection with each other and inevitably struggle with unjust structures. In the very first paragraphs of the "Manifesto" it is declared: "The history of all human societies up to our time has been the history of class struggle." But according to Marx, as long as the material conditions or relations of production are not in place, the subordinate class has no chance of victory in the struggle against oppressive structures, which is why systems based on class oppression have lasted for centuries, despite the stubborn struggles of the oppressed layers. Victory is possible only when the productive forces, due to maximum growth, no longer correspond to the existing relations, or in other words, when the relations of production operate in complete contradiction to the productive forces, the whole of economic life faces a general crisis, and this is the right situation for the rising class to overthrow the system with its united struggle and establish a new system based on its own interests. In Marx's view, the series of uprisings and revolutions that finally brought feudalism to its knees was because the productive forces had reached such a level that they were no longer compatible with the dominant relations in the landownership system and the time had come for the bourgeoisie to dominate society with the capitalist system. This transformation is often accomplished by a violent revolution. This is why Marx saw

revolution as the "locomotive" or driving force of society, like a midwife who brings a new society into being from the womb of the old society. The capitalist system, which ended feudal oppression, failed to end the exploitation of man by man, but instead replaced it with a new type of class oppression that was even more severe. Capitalism, according to Marx, has an amazing dynamism. By mastering new values and structures, and especially with the industrial revolution, this system advanced the productive forces in an unprecedented way and brought society to a high level of wealth production and abundance of material products, but this progress did not bring universal prosperity and well-being because it was distributed very unequally. According to Marx, in capitalism, class contradictions develop in a new way and the two main classes of society, the exploiters and the exploited, are irreconcilably opposed to each other: the capitalist minority, the owners of capital and the means of production, are placed against the vast majority of workers who own nothing but their own arm strength or labor power.

The Poverty of Philosophy

In his book *The Philosophy of Poverty*, which Marx wrote in criticism of Proudhon's *The Poverty of Philosophy*, Proudhon speaks with a radical and metaphysical perspective about the separation of object and subject and the necessity of the subject's domination over nature and providing for the growth of the forces of production and technological tools. In many of Marx's writings, the metaphysical foundation for accepting man as a subject (a cognitive agent) and the main role of man as a powerful knowing subject in understanding the world, and the necessity that understanding must be shaped in line with the desire for domination of the world, can be found with the same force as in the writings of the most ardent defenders of modernity, and although this view is sometimes returned to at the beginning of Marx and Engels' praise of the development of forces in the bourgeois era in the *Manifesto*. It seems that Marx and Proudhon have a deep disagreement about technology and the development of its social position. However, if we look closely, we see that their discussion is about results and not the main proposed causes. In *The Poverty of Philosophy* (Chapter II, Book II), Marx wrote in a critique of Proudhon that Proudhon did not understand that the machine is nothing more than a more advanced and composite form of the instrument of labor, which itself was formed in line with and in the service of the social division of labor and is in no way a separate economic category. The machine is the expression of the economic form of life. Society and in the service of production relations and cannot be considered as the basis of the social division of labor, but Proudhon's problem is in seeing everything in reverse and calling the machine a tool for dominating nature and not realizing that we ourselves have created it in the process of dominating natural forces and have been able to control it. However, in the *Paris Manuscripts*, Marx's opposition to the opposition of man and nature and the necessity of

man's dominating the world of objects is clear. In this book, the duality of man and his environment is generally rejected and the human nature of nature or the natural nature of man is discussed. In the manuscripts, Marx refers to nature as a part of human existence and declares that the nature that grows and develops in human history, that is, the development of human society, is indeed the true nature of man. Therefore, the nature that grows and develops through industry, even if it is alienated from man, is the true anthropological nature.

Connected Thought

Like the Left Hegelians, logic or the dialectical method He accepted Hegel but took a critical approach to his idealism or philosophical theme. He said that existence proceeds correctly according to a dialectical process, but its driving force, contrary to Hegel's conception, is not the idea or spirit. Rather, it is matter. Matter is the generative force of the spirit and manifests and transforms it in the evolutionary process. Thus, he saw the development of the idea or spirit as a function of the development of matter, and he rejected this anti-Hegelian view. He stated variously. For example, he wrote: "Unlike German philosophy, which aims from heaven to earth, we must go from earth to heaven. It is not the thoughts, imaginations, words, and desires of human beings that affect their real lives; on the contrary, it is the objective deeds, activities, and conditions of human life that shape their thoughts and views." Marx and his close associate Friedrich Engels formulated their achievement in "The German Ideology" as follows: Hegel's philosophy (idealism) was a body that had stood upside down, so we set it on its feet. That is, we returned it to a correct and natural position.

Theory of History

Marx's theory of history means understanding the changes in human societies based on material conditions in all periods of human history. Believers in this theory believe that by using this theory, they can not only analyze the causes of all changes in human society over time, but also predict the future of humanity. The remarkable advances in applied sciences and industry that occurred in Europe in the 18th century and the first half of the 19th century led to a fundamental change in the attitude of Western thinkers towards the humanities and social sciences. As a result of this change in the view of Western thinkers towards social issues, a science-centered approach was created, so that the use of the word "sciences" in the humanities to mean applied sciences such as physics and chemistry, etc. became common. According to this approach, just as researchers in applied sciences achieve effective results by using accepted scientific methods to uncover our unknowns and add ambiguities to our awareness and knowledge, so that in the process we become more knowledgeable and responsible humans towards nature, animals, air, and the lives

of ourselves and others, if knowledge is transformed into our understanding of the objects and events around us and brings a better life for humans, nature, and our world, it is equally expected that teachings in the humanities will produce correct and useful results by using scientific methods. Another topic that led to a change in the attitude of Eastern thinkers towards the humanities and social sciences was "Darwin's theory of evolution." Charles Darwin was a natural scientist. In this theory, he showed that life is essentially a long process of evolution. An evolution in which all living things, including plants and other animals, progress towards betterment and perfection. This theory quickly spread to the humanities, especially history and social sciences. Thus, just as plants and animals are evolving and progressing, human and human societies are also moving towards evolution and progress. According to these two attitudes, namely the "science-centered" and "evolutionary" attitudes, the duty of a thinker in the humanities and social sciences is to be able to discover the laws that lead to the evolution of human societies and to accelerate the process of evolution. By discovering these laws, just as we achieve more advanced tools in the natural and applied sciences, we hope to be able to build more advanced, more moral, and more evolved societies in the humanities. Two groups of sociologists who have had this view of the humanities and sociology have been functionalist sociologists and Marxism. In response to the question of what external factor causes the evolution of human societies, functionalist sociologists consider the needs of society and the environment in which humans live to be the cause of this evolution, and Marxist sociologists consider the "economy" to be the cause of the evolution of human societies. Before addressing Marx's theory of historical materialism, it should be noted that the idea that human societies are evolving was prevalent among thinkers many years before Darwin's theory of evolution. For example, Hegel considered the "spirit of nations" to be the cause of the evolution of human societies. However, the impact that Darwin's theory had on this way of thinking was that it transformed this attitude from a purely philosophical attitude into a scientific one.

Communism

Communism (from the Latin word *Communis*, meaning common) is a classical political-scientific-economic movement that has been around since the 19th century, mostly based on the ideas of Karl Marx and the Communist Manifesto. To define his distance and difference from the non-worker socialism of the 19th century, Marx chose the title that the worker socialist movement had given itself, namely communism. The goal of this political movement is to eliminate private ownership of the means of labor, abolish wages, and dismantle social classes through a workers' revolution. Under the title of public ownership of the means of labor, it attempts to draw a social organization without social classes with common ownership and in the absence of private ownership or state ownership. In other

words, the proponents of communism and socialism believed in an absolute state economy and avoided a free economy, and the first state that was formed in this way in Russia was the former Soviet Union.

Communism and its various definitions

Communism encompasses a variety of schools of thought, including Marxism, anarchism (anarchist communism), and other political ideologies that coexist. All of these share the analysis and critical discourse that the current order of society results from its economic system, capitalism; that within this system there are two major social classes: the working class - who must struggle to survive and constitute the majority of society - and the capitalist class - a minority that owns the means of production and employs the working class - and that this conflict between these two classes is the root of all problems in society and will ultimately be resolved through a workers' revolution. The revolution puts the working class in power and, in turn, creates widespread social ownership of production, which, according to this analysis, is a key element in the transformation of society towards communism.

Karl Marx believes that in order to transform a society from a capitalist mode of production to a communist mode of production, it must go through a transitional period, and this is not possible all at once. Marx calls this transitional period the realization of the dictatorship of the proletariat with a workers' revolution. Mohammad Reza Nikfar, a leftist political philosopher, believes that the meaning of the dictatorship of the proletariat in Marx's literature basically implies the hegemony of the working class, and not the concept of dictatorship in today's political literature. Friedrich Engels explains the basic principles and foundations of communism, as well as concepts such as society, history, and economic systems from a Marxist perspective and using the theory of historical materialism in a book titled *The Principles of Communism*. This book was used as a basis for writing another manifesto for the Communist Party. Communism's main goal is to abolish private ownership of the means of labor under the title of social ownership of the means of labor and tries to draw a social organization without social classes with common ownership and in the absence of private ownership. Supporters of communism consider communism to be the highest stage of socialism. Socialism is actually a transitional period from capitalism to communism. Among the branches of communism, Islamic communism (Tudeh Party of Iran) and Christian communism (Fidel Castro in Cuba) can be mentioned. In some countries, such as the Soviet Union, China, and Cuba, communist parties succeeded in obtaining state power through revolution and guerrilla warfare. Although this action did not necessarily lead to the full implementation of socialism, it did lead to a form of state economy with socialist concepts for governing the state and society.

Social structure of communism

Communism is a social structure that promotes the establishment of a classless society, without a state (ruling body) based on common ownership of the means of production. Communism is usually presented as a branch of a larger movement called socialism, which is the policy of various political and intellectual movements that trace their origins to the works of Marx. Opponents say that communism is an ideology, while proponents say the exact opposite, that it is the only political system without ideology, since it is the logical result of historical materialism and the proletarian revolution. On the one hand, the communists practically constitute the most advanced and stable section of the working class parties of each country, and are in fact the driving force of that section; and on the other hand, from a theoretical point of view, they have the advantage over the great mass of the proletariat of clearly understanding the course of movement, the conditions and the final results of the proletarian movement. The immediate goal of the proletariat is the same as that of all other proletarian parties: to organize the proletariat into a class, to overthrow the rule of the bourgeoisie, and to seize political power by the proletariat. The theoretical conclusions of the communists are in no way based on ideas and principles that present themselves as world reformers.” Marx distinguishes his communism with a scientific term. Marx’s communism is a communism based on the freedom of the working class. The working class, due to its role in the relations of production, is forced to sell its labor power. This sale of labor power turns the worker into a machine and deprives him of his human nature. This exploitation creates the state for its own continuation, establishes an institution called the family (in its modern sense), which is patriarchal.

Marxism

Marxism is a political and social school that emerged under the influence of the ideas of Karl Marx, a German philosopher and revolutionary, in the late 19th century. Friedrich Engels was also an important figure in the thought of Marxism, and Marxists agree with the general principles of his thought. The basis of Marxism, as expressed in the "Communist Manifesto" (written by Marx and Engels), is based on the belief that the history of societies has so far been the history of class struggle and that in the present world there are two classes, the bourgeoisie and the proletariat, which The conflict between these two will shape history. There are very different understandings of Marxism and its analysis of world problems among different Marxists, but there is one thing that almost everyone agrees on: "The overthrow of the capitalist system through the workers' revolution and the abolition of private ownership of the means of production and the abolition of wage labor and the creation of a classless society with a free and equal people,

and as a result, the end of human alienation." Although Marxism is the foundation of various forms of communism such as Leninism, Trotskyism, and Luxemburgism, and Marx is often recognized as the father of communism, there are also non-Marxian communisms.

The most important components of Marx's thought

Materialism

Marx believed in materialism, meaning that there is only matter in the world. Marx took this concept of materialism from Feuerbach. Accordingly, the existence of God or spirit or any immaterial being will be ruled out and there is only matter in the world.

Dialectics

Marx learned dialectics from Hegel. According to dialectics, everything in the world is changing and transforming. In front of everything, there is an opposite or opposition, which Marx calls the thesis and antithesis. The combination of these two creates a synthesis.

Historical determinism

Determinism means being determined or determined. Historical determinism means that history has an inevitable process. According to Marx, history is divided into several stages. The first stage is called the "primitive commune" and in it everything was communal and there was no private property, then history reached the period of slavery, and after that feudalism, and in Marx's time it was in the stage of capitalism. Marx predicted that capitalism, with the help of revolution and the dictatorship of the proletariat (workers without tools), would reach "socialism", at which point private property would be abolished and all property and assets would be communalised, and then it would reach "communism", a classless, stateless and propertyless society. This prediction has not yet come true.

Dialectical materialism or dialectical materialism

It is primarily considered epistemology, that is, the theory of knowledge or knowledge. The main goal of this philosophy is empiricism, that is, a view of knowledge in which the knowing subject confronts the real object and reveals its essence with the help of abstraction, and from this assumption of the direct confrontation of thought with reality, and the assumption of the greater impartiality of the subject with respect to the object, it follows from external guarantees of the truth of knowledge. Dialectical materialism opposes the concept of knowledge as insight, production, and theoretical practice, and thus, one can say that the theory of practice itself is theoretical.

Karl Marx saw dialectics as compatible only with the events of history and society, but Friedrich Engels extended the scope of dialectics to the realm of nature. But Engels did not claim that historical materialism could be deduced from dialectical materialism. This was done by Georgy Plekhanov, who first used the term, and by Vladimir Lenin, who interpreted it in such a way that the nature of the world was compatible with revolutionary aspirations. Joseph Stalin manipulated it even further, extracting from it a political cosmology. Plekhanov's "The Evolution of the Monistic View of History" (1895), Lenin's "Materialism and Empiriocriticism" (1909), and Stalin's "Dialectical and Historical Materialism" (1939) explain step by step the stages of the development of dialectical materialism into a party philosophy. Some Marxist thinkers recognize Marx as the only reference.

Dialectical materialism in simple terms

Dialectical materialism in simple terms means that an object cannot be studied and judged without taking into account the influence of the surrounding environment on it and the influence of that object on the environment.

Criticism of Marx's Theory

1. One of the biggest criticisms of Marx's theory has been and is that his predictions did not come true. He predicted that a communist revolution would soon occur in England; but this revolution never occurred in this country. History, which he believed should follow an arbitrary course in accordance with its historical periods, did not.
2. The second major criticism of Marx's thought is usually directed at the reductionist aspect of this thought. Reductionism means that you summarize and reduce an important and great matter to one thing. Marx reduces historical developments that arise from many cultural, social, political, etc. factors solely (and in some interpretations mainly) to the economy. He also ultimately reduces the economy to the means of production. In this way, he ignores or considers many important and effective factors to be of little importance in his theory.
3. Many thinkers of ultimate communism criticize Marx, who envisions a society without classes, without a state, and without private property. In principle, such a society is not possible, and therefore Marx's prediction that he would achieve this society was never realized.

The strength and positive impact of Marx's thought

The strength that made Marx's thought one of the most influential political thoughts is that Marx protested against the rights of workers and the exploitation that was carried out on

them by the employer class. Marx's thoughts improved the situation of workers who worked more than 12 hours and sometimes even 16 hours a day and received very little pay; and gradually led employers to respect more workers' rights such as a working limit of 8 hours a day, insurance, etc. For this reason, the majority of supporters of the Marxist thought are workers, but it should be noted that the defense of workers' rights is not limited to Marxism alone and it is possible to defend workers' rights without relying on Marxist teachings.

The thought of Marxism-Leninism

One of these interpretations, which was the thought of Marxism-Leninism (Lenin's interpretations of Marx's thought), was by Vladimir Lenin was implemented in the former Soviet Union, and after 70 years, due to its inefficiency and inability to solve the problems of society, and despite numerous amendments and adjustments by Lenin's successors, instead of realizing a communist society, it ultimately led to the collapse of the Soviet Union.

Communism in Today's World

In today's world, the economy and politics of countries have become two-pronged, in such a way that they are either purely bourgeois (like the United States and most European countries and the so-called West) or they claim to be socialist and communist. Currently, socialist and communist countries behave in two ways: either they openly show that they are supporters of the socialist and communist system (like Cuba, North Korea, Vietnam and other current countries in the world that claim socialism and communism) or their economic and political systems are covertly and indirectly like this. In general, many countries have not abandoned their Marxist line of thought in any way and have continued with this economic and political system until now. The world in which we are striving to understand intellectual actions is not a world that was crystallized in a few years and formed by a few dogmatic individuals. It is a world that was formed over a period of several hundred years and by thousands of powerful thinkers who came together in a whirlwind called time and gathered different ideas and opinions. Existentialism is an important philosophical school in the contemporary West, which was invented by the Danish philosopher and theologian Kierkegaard. Existential philosophers deal with human concerns and extreme and borderline situations such as suffering from injustice, the desire for immortality, hope, love, faith and other existential issues of man and have established a kind of closeness and connection with their audience. Therefore, the importance of the subject of the work can be referred to the concerns of existential philosophers. It should be noted that the purpose of writing this article by me is neither criticism nor defense, but representation. The general explanation of the understanding of the general ideas of

existentialists has been sufficiently done. The thinkers who have begun to unravel the blind intellectual knots of society in this important intellectual field are not representatives of a school of thought, and despite all this, the dependence of their very individual ideas on each other, which time, nationality, and character have separated them from each other, is not without attraction. They lead to each other, form natural families. Each sheds light on the others and, in general, expands certain common themes. In the continuation of this topic, we will learn that in order to provide historical background and explain the development of existential philosophers, four chapters were opened in the historical background section. First, a brief report is given on the course of the discussion in the Descartes system until the nineteenth century. Then, the thoughts of three thinkers who have had a great influence on the existential system are briefly described. But before that, I will explain a few definitions of existentialism for readers who may not be familiar with it. It is hoped that by reading this article, your awareness in various intellectual fields will increase. Existentialism (Latin: Existentialism) is a term applied to the work of certain philosophers from the late 19th and early 20th centuries who, despite deep doctrinal differences, share the belief that philosophical thinking begins with the subject of man, not merely subjective thinking. In existentialism, the starting point of the individual is determined by what is called the "attitude to existence," or the feeling of being lost and disoriented in the face of a seemingly meaningless and absurd world. According to existentialists, life is meaningless unless the individual himself gives it meaning. This means that we find ourselves in life, then we decide what meaning or essence to give it. As Sartre said, we are condemned to freedom. That is, we have no choice but to choose and to bear the burden of our choice. Existentialism is sometimes confused with nihilism. While a separate category Nihilists believe that life has no purpose or meaning. While existentialists believe that man must create his own meaning and purpose in life. Existentialism is derived from the word Existence (in Latin: Existence) meaning existence. Søren Kierkegaard is called the first existentialist. Existentialism has types that can include atheism and Christianity. Among the most well-known Christian existentialists are Kierkegaard, Marcel and Jaspers. The verb *existere* and *existo* in Latin means to emerge from appearing and to emerge. This term is also common with being and existence, but in the terminology of existentialist philosophies it is interpreted as the originality of existence and has nothing to do with Mulla Sadra's theory of the originality of existence, which is about absolute existence. In these philosophies, it is necessary to pay attention to the root of the word Existence, which is derived from the Latin *Existere*, which is a compound of two parts: *Ex* (from outside) and *istere* (rising). (to stand) and its meaning in Latin is emergence, manifestation, and manifestation, and from here the relevance of the term "emergent rising or rising" for this term becomes clear. In existentialism, as stated, emergent rising or sometimes transcendent existence refers to an

existence that constantly wants to pass and become a new thing, which only applies to human existence. So in the philosophy of existence, existence means permanent transcendence, that is, passing from the existing state. Therefore, existence requires becoming. When in the philosophy of existentialism, existence is taken to mean permanent transcendence and passing from the existing state and is considered synonymous with becoming, it is also linked to its literal meaning. Since we said that its literal meaning is apparent It is becoming and coming into being. So existence is a unity that is constantly renewed and appears in another form. In another meaning of existentialism, existential philosophers examine human existence as a distinct type of existence from the existence of other beings and carefully call human existence existence due to this distinction. They try to show what is the difference between the existence or being of man in this world and other forms of existence. "Every new nature is valuable in itself." This is the proposition that the school of originality of existence presents about the definition of the concept of value. In a way that, following the philosophical phrase "I think, therefore I am" by Descartes, Albert Camus says "I rebel, therefore I am." In addition to accepting the sentence that was raised about value, this phrase also has a meaning in itself. That living like the past is equal to living inauthentically. Every human being who enters the world has unique genetic characteristics that, as a result of these factors, have a unique personality (consciousness). Therefore, it is valuable in itself. Here, we refer to the priority of human existence over its nature and in the field of ethics, we have separated the value of man from his performance. This is where Jean-Paul Sartre writes: "A whole human being is made up of all human beings and has equal value to all of them, and the value of each of them is equal to him." Existentialism was clearly put forward by Friedrich Nietzsche and Søren Kierkegaard, philosophers of the nineteenth century. Although it had pioneers in previous centuries. Socrates repeated these two slogans throughout his philosophical career: "A life without need is not worth living," and his second slogan was to "know thyself." The first question clarifies the nature of philosophy, and the second question the nature of existentialist philosophy. In the 20th century, the German philosopher Martin Heidegger influenced other existentialist philosophers such as Camus. Dostoevsky and Kafka also incorporated existentialist concepts into their literary works. While there are common tendencies among existentialist thinkers, there are also differences and disagreements among them. (The main difference is between existentialists who deny the existence of God, such as Sartre, and existentialists who believe that God exists, such as Tillich) and not all of them necessarily accepted the correct application of existentialism to their works. It seems that the term existentialism was used by the French philosopher (Marcel) in the mid-1940s and was adopted by Sartre in 1945. Existentialism and the Originality of Man was also an essay that Sartre published around the same time that played an important role in the spread of existentialist thought. The

term had previously been attributed to other philosophers whose philosophy focused on existence, and in particular human existence. Heidegger focused his work on human existence from the 1920s, and Jaspers called his philosophy the philosophy of being in the 1930s. Both were influenced by the Danish philosopher Kierkegaard. For Kierkegaard, the crisis of human existence was the main concern. He is known as the first existentialist. In fact, he was the first person to make existentialist questions the focus of his philosophy. Other writers have also explicitly raised existentialist themes throughout the history of philosophy and literature. Following the emergence of existentialism over the decades, when society became formally acquainted with it, the term existentialism suddenly became widespread. Some writings and thoughts that dealt with the concept of existentialism in some way include:

- The Teachings of Buddha
- The Confessions of Saint Augustine
- The Superior Mysticism of Mulla Sadra
- William Shakespeare's Hamlet

Historical Backgrounds

Existentialism is one of the important schools of thought of the 19th century onwards, which is referred to with various definitions such as existential schools, the school of being, and the school of the originality of existence. It is obvious that the existential school and the school of the originality of existence have a substantial difference from the theory of the originality of existence that exists in Islamic philosophy, and the similarity is only in their names. Since this school of thought is a kind of rejection of absolutism and emphasizes the moment of life and living, it cannot be referred to as philosophy. Because philosophy is a general thought, and this is what these schools seek to deny. Regarding the historical background of this school, it should be said that after World War II, among people who, despite the slogan of freedom, found that they had no control over their lives and had become hopeless, hopelessness, and nihilistic, this philosophy tried to provide an efficient and appropriate justification for the situation and offered a way out or to cope with this feeling of emptiness. According to them, humans who are immersed in their daily lives are impersonal beings who have no understanding of existence at all. If this same human feels fear within himself that comes from emptiness and death, etc., he will realize the perception of existence. Because of this fear and apprehension, it becomes the basis of human freedom and the reason for his separation from other beings. They say that there is no goal, value, or duty that gives direction to humans and imposes a path, and that humans themselves must create value and meaning and choose any action that they consider

valuable in their minds as a duty. Therefore, they are also responsible for their actions. Among the prominent figures of this school of thought, some of whom, of course, refrain from calling themselves by this name, we can repeatedly mention Kierkegaard (the father of existentialist philosophy), German Nietzsche, Jaspers and Sartre, Marcel and Camus. Considering the emphasis of existential philosophies on human existence, the historical roots of this philosophy are attributed to Socrates or Augustine. From the existentialist point of view, man can be discussed in two ways:

1- Abstract

2- Concrete

In the concrete view, we discuss man in a logical and argumentative way. Now, demonstrative or empirical. For example, we know the sex and age of man or study the parts of his body through experimental research. The study of man from the point of view of a biochemist, psychologist, sociologist and philosopher is an abstract discussion. These thinkers study man in isolation from other objects. But in the concrete view, man is studied with all his relations and relationships, and man's relationship with other humans, with God, nature, etc., and everything other than him is not taken into account. The knowledge of existentialist philosophers about man is systematic, not inductive, they want to create man with all his relations and not isolated from the outside world.

Existential Figures

- Before Modernity

(Epictetus- Marcus Aurelius- Saint Augustine- Socrates- Pascal)

- Nineteenth Century

(Friedrich Nietzsche- Gabriel Marcel- Kierkegaard- Fyodor Dostoevsky- Onomono-Franz Kafka- Heidegger- Jaspers- Freud)

- Twentieth Century

(Albert Camus- Simone Weiss- Simone de Beauvoir- Jean-Paul Sartre- Ortegaist- Chestoffe- Nikolai Berdyaev)

Principles of Existentialism

In existentialism, we can highlight and discuss four fundamental concepts that are called the principles of existentialism. These principles are:

1- The possibility of the non-necessity or contingency of existence

2- Freedom

3- Responsibility

4- Originality

Man does not have a priori nature that God or nature supposedly created. Man, like any being, is possible and not necessary. He creates himself and freely examines and chooses among possible options. He is responsible for his own choices and must be able to do what he knows to be right. (And not to act according to the example of everyone) and in this case he has done something original. Sartre's presentation of these points began from an ontological perspective that he himself called phenomenological ontology and was based on the philosophical achievements of Heidegger. We will explain each of these current principles briefly in the following.

Unnecessary Possibility

The statement that something is, raises the question of whether that thing is for a specific reason for others according to its own nature or not?

The answer in the existentialist school of thought is expressed in a literary text, namely through the mind of Antoine Roquentin, the central character of the novel Nausea: "That moment was extraordinary. I was there. Motionless and frozen. Immersed in a terrifying gravity. Right in this heart something new appeared. I understood nausea. I had it. To be honest, I hadn't yet defined my discovery to myself. But I think we'll move on now. Sartre continues: "It's easier to put it into words. The essential is the unnecessary possible. I mean, by definition, existence is not a necessity. Very simply, existence means being there. Beings are revealed. They let us encounter them. But we can never infer them. I think there are people who have understood this. Only they have tried to overcome this unnecessary possible by inventing a necessary being whose cause is also assumed in itself. So no necessary being can explain its existence. The unnecessary possible is not a false aspect that can be dismissed when heard. It is absolute and therefore a completely uncaused thing. Everything is uncaused. This garden, the city, and myself...)

Freedom

Man projects. At every moment, it is inevitable that one moves towards one's future by choosing among the set of alternatives before them. Man has no choice but to make these choices and is condemned to freedom. The only state in which we are not free is when we are free not to be free. In fact Humanity does not exist except in freedom. In the school of existentialism, freedom means the possibility of choosing. From Sartre's point of view,

"We are the choice" is to exist by choosing. There is no difficult external situation that makes human freedom of choice completely impossible. Undoubtedly, situations reduce the number and variety of options, but they do not completely eliminate the possibility of choice. Even in prison and in the camp, I am not completely deprived of the possibility of choice. I can choose whether to resist the jailer or not. After the liberation of France, Sartre wrote that the French have never been so free, even during the occupation of the authoritarian government and the resistance movement, this was also clear. Human freedom arises from his situation in the necessity of choosing. Indeed, freedom arises from limitation. Because man, due to his limitation, plans and is forced to choose an option in freedom. The meaning of freedom here is that when freedom is considered the basis of my actions, the invalidity of any purpose that has been predetermined for my actions becomes apparent. I can organize or create myself according to the purpose I choose. I can change the meaning of my life myself. Along with that, I create a world and give it meaning on the basis of which I myself live. Responsibility

Freedom does not provide a calm and comfortable state for man. The anxiety of making the right choice is constantly alive in us. The responsibility of whether what we have chosen will cause problems for ourselves, our loved ones and others. Choice is never easy. If it is true that the existence of man precedes his nature, man is responsible for who he is. This does not mean that man is responsible for his own individuality. Rather, he is responsible for all men. Responsibility in the philosophy of existentialism accompanies freedom. To say that each person is responsible for his or her own choices in which he or she exercises or tests his or her freedom means that the person is responsible for his or her own actions. To be committed to one's choices is to recognize them as right actions. For Sartre, recognizing a choice as right must have meaning outside the relative scope of belief.

Authenticity

Sartre explained that a complete break with false belief is impossible. But one can be true to oneself in the way we call authentic. Heidegger did not consider any kind of morality to be authentic morality, which is why he had set aside the discussion of morality. For him, authenticity could not be considered a moral presupposition. Authenticity had meaning in actions. Not behaving like "everyone else" and, as such, discovering and following one's own path. For Heidegger, authenticity was the effort to find the right path. Can the word "right" be used here? Doesn't this conceptual term suggest morality? According to the common meaning of ethics, the answer is negative. In another sense of ethics, we can say that it is a personal approach to life. Perhaps we can mention ethical choices in this. Sartre had a specific meaning of ethics in mind. For him, authenticity had meaning in ethics. In *Being and Nothingness*, Sartre showed that authenticity cannot be

achieved. There is no authentic person in the strict sense of the word. But one can move towards authenticity. This progress is through choosing what I am confident in, from my freedom. It is not the legacy of the past or the promise of contemporaries. It is possible. One can have authentic actions. That is, contrary to false beliefs, man is not perfect. He is not like Spinoza's God who has reached the point of perfection. Man is not perfect even when he is only of his own free will, against others, against false beliefs. He is a thrown reality that is governed by forced conditions, but he has actions based on himself and not a "moral drive towards authenticity." Sartre says that man is not what he appears to be and what others think he is. In the same way, what others think he is not, is. Others aside, man is not what he is now, in reality. Because he is in the process of transformation and becoming, he is facing the future and he must change himself and constantly listen to someone else in order to finally perhaps give an image of himself. I am a man and I cannot have the ontological perfection of things.

Philosophical Existentialism

But this trend is more philosophically complex. What we call philosophical existentialism took on two different colors in Germany and in France. In Germany, Husserl first founded the religion of phenomenology as a precursor to this school, and his students Heidegger and Jaspers tried more than him to bring the philosophical aspect of existentialism to fruition. In fact, Heidegger's famous saying is not far from the truth in a sense. In other words, if we consider the concept of existence as it was from the Middle Ages onwards: "philosophy begins with Plato and ends with me": that it became limited and gradually became more limited until it became a purely subjective concept, we see that we cannot go further than Heidegger and that philosophy in this sense ends with Heidegger. But overall, although the German existentialist philosophers did not understand the meaning of existence as they did in the wisdom and mysticism of the East, they tried to maintain a kind of transcendental dimension within the limitations that the history of European philosophy had placed before them, and consequently, to attribute values to man and to human society. In France, there were two types of existentialism: religious existentialism, represented by Gabriel Marcel, and anti-religious existentialism, represented by Sartre and his followers. One of the characteristics of these people is that they are mostly literary and critical of society. Their literary works have artistic and literary value, including the plays they have written, the poems they have composed, the stories and critical essays and novels they have written. They have tried to give philosophy a literary and artistic aspect, that is, aspects that are related to everyday life and to beauty and emotions and feelings. The human being is dealing with it. But the fundamental difference between them is that Marcel and people like him believe that man is "alone" and that his relations with the

world and others and God are severed and man is an individual, but they add that between this man and that transcendent being that is God, there is a chasm and a gap that man must jump over and what gives value to the existence that we call the non-existence of man as a heroic and living being is this jump from one side to the other, while Sartre and his followers believe that the value of man lies in enduring this. Man must endure the fact that he is a lonely being and will never have contact with another. So the only thing that is worth preserving is human values, values such as injustice and the like. That is why many existentialists who follow Sartre are left-wing and Marxist. That is, some of them are politically Marxists, and philosophically existentialists. However, it should be noted that existentialist philosophers have not been willing to accept the title of existentialism. Only Sartre has used this term explicitly, and Gabriel Marcel has accepted it only once. However, historians of contemporary philosophy have given the title of existentialist and existential philosopher to many people other than Sartre, such as Kierkegaard, Jaspers, Heidegger, Nietzsche, etc. Even writers such as Abagnano and... have also been existentialists.

Issues Accepted by Existentialists

Existentialist philosophers have some issues in common, but they differ in their number. Copleston addresses three issues in his book *Contemporary Philosophy*, and Paul Edwards, editor of the *Encyclopedia of Philosophy*, raises six issues. Some of the common issues are as follows:

Self-knowledge: Self-knowledge, not philosophical or empirical anthropology, is one of the commonalities of existential philosophers. Existentialists do not seek anthropology, either philosophical or empirical or anthropology; they seek self-knowledge, and the concern of all of them is self-knowledge, although the results they have reached are very different.

Freedom: The freedom discussed in existentialism is philosophical and ontological freedom, not political, social, and legal freedom. The French philosopher Sartre says: We are not free in being in time, in being in place, in living, and in acting, but man has the ability to choose and make choices in everything else.

Anti-obligation: The philosophy of existentialism, due to its belief in human freedom, eliminates anything that stands in the way of human freedom and choice. One of the principles that conflicts with human freedom is the principle of obligation, including jurisprudential, legal obligations, and moral values; because human freedom is limited by obedience.

Conceptual authenticity, introspection, essentiality: Existentialism is associated with the authenticity of the individual; because it says that each individual must be himself; therefore, its anthropology is also personal, not universal; this correlation of existentialism with the authenticity of the individual requires that it has no middle ground with realism; in philosophies of the authenticity of the specific human existence, everything acquires its meaning in relation to man, and man describes things from his own perspective; therefore, existentialism is opposed to realism and in favor of the authenticity of meaning. In general, the world without a knowing subject is an illusion and a fantasy; man is the main source of meaning and signification.

Transcendence and Passage: The issue of transcendence and passage is common to religious and non-religious existentialist philosophers. They believe that man is in the process of transcendence and passage, and as mentioned, the word Existence not only means existence, but also a kind of becoming and becoming.

Lack of a definite nature for man: Unlike animals, plants, and inanimate objects, man does not have a definite nature in advance. Every human being creates his own nature by using his own freedom. Man shows what he wants to be with his plans in the future and is never devoid of purpose and decision; therefore, the specific existence of a human being precedes his nature.

Value creation: The philosophy of existentialism considers man to be the creator of value and its implementer, that is, every person who finds a nature in his own journey of self-transcendence and passage, something becomes valuable to him; therefore, he creates value himself.

Criticisms of the school of existence:

The school of existentialism has positive points, for example, the emphasis on human existence; That man is the key to understanding the world; and that this existence of man is considered the center and end of all matters; and that man is in the process of becoming and can determine his destiny at will; although the essence of these matters is not new issues that they have said, some of the matters existed in the thoughts of Greek sages who lived for several thousand years. For example, Protagoras, one of the most authoritative sages of the Sophist who lived in the fifth century BC, is quoted as saying that Sadr al-Mutālīhin says about the human soul: The human soul is in relation to the matters it perceives like the relation of matter to form; that is, just as matter becomes form, the human soul also becomes in relation to its perceptions, becoming a type superior to nature. In other words, the fact that man is in the process of becoming is something that Sadra had stated before them in the discussion of the movement of substance in the human soul. In addition, the Holy Quran, a thousand years before the birth of existentialism, introduced

man as having the highest position in the universe: it considers him the vicegerent of God, and the only being capable of carrying the divine trust, etc.

But at the same time, this school has numerous problems and is plagued by a kind of contradiction and paradox:

This school believes that since every human being has his own unique existence, therefore he cannot be interpreted and explained with philosophical and metaphysical concepts; the question is, is this theory not itself a philosophical and metaphysical theory? The fact that man is in the process of transcendence, passing and becoming and is not stationary; does not contradict the fact that his essence has precedence over his existence; that is, before man, it can be said that man is a being capable of enjoying numerous perfections. Of course, based on the originality of Sadra's existence, existence has precedence over essence everywhere and is not specific to man. The fact that existentialists seek self-knowledge and do not seek anthropology; The question that arises here is that assuming the possibility of self-knowledge is accepted, without anthropology, does self-knowledge lead to anthropology or not? Does knowing the individual require general natural knowledge or not? If it does not lead to this or if existentialists are not looking for it, then what is the meaning of these sentences and their words that man is the key to understanding the universe; that man's existence is the center and end of all issues; that man's material existence precedes the nature or essence of his soul; that man is the main source of all meaning; and that man can determine his destiny at will? Do these statements express self-knowledge or anthropology? When they say: The nature of each person is different from others, they are so different that it is impossible to consider a single type for humans; can we believe that there is such a difference between human individuals that it is impossible to consider a single type for them? That is, is the difference between the existence of Zayd and Omar like the difference between a stone and a dog, which have nothing in common in their specific nature? That the philosophy of existentialism is a conflict of duties, including duties Jurisprudence, law and moral values; does it adhere to the requirements of this statement that it creates chaos and promotes violence? In addition, some of the duties and values of man are not inconsistent with the simplicity of his nature; because the nature and nature of man are with him; does the commitment to honesty and truthfulness contradict the simplicity of human nature? In any case, it seems that the main problem of Western philosophers is the weakness of their intellectual foundations and lack of familiarity with strong philosophical foundations, especially Sadra'i wisdom. In other words, the prevailing and prevailing philosophy in the West has two basic characteristics and signs: a) The relativity of truth, b) The exclusiveness of human perception in the senses; that is, only empirical sciences have value and validity, and sciences that are not based on senses and discuss mere rational things have no value and validity; therefore,

one of the problems of Western philosophy is that this philosophy leads to skepticism. In other words, it unintentionally cuts off its own roots.

Types of Existentialism

Some proponents of existentialism divide existentialism into three categories in terms of their tendency towards God and religion: a) Religious and theistic existentialism, headed by Kierkegaard, and in addition to him, Michael Onamono, Karl Jaspers, and Gabriel Marcel are also in this category.

b) Atheistic existentialism, headed by Jean-Paul Sartre, Albert Camus, and Kafka are also in this category.

c) Neutral or bewildered existentialism, led by Nietzsche and Martin Heidegger.

Atheistic existentialism

Atheistic existentialism or atheistic existentialism is a type of existentialism that strongly diverged from the works of Christian existentialism by Søren Kierkegaard, and built existentialism within the framework of an atheistic worldview. Søren Kierkegaard's philosophy provided the theoretical foundation for existentialism in the 19th century. Atheistic existentialism became formalized after the publication of Jean-Paul Sartre's *Being and Nothingness* in 1943, and Sartre later explicitly referred to it in *Existentialism and the Origin of Man* (1946). Sartre had previously written in the spirit of atheistic existentialism; Simone de Beauvoir also wrote from an atheist existentialist perspective, including *Nausea*, the short stories *The Wall* (1938). The term atheistic existentialism refers to the exclusion of any transcendental, metaphysical, or religious beliefs from existentialist philosophical thought. However, atheistic existentialism can share elements such as sadness or rebellion in light of human limitations with religious existentialism, or with metaphysical existentialism through phenomenology and the works of Heidegger. Atheist existentialism confronts the anxiety of death without resorting to the hope of salvation from God. For some thinkers, the weakness of existence has been largely theoretical, such as Jean-Paul Sartre, while others have been influenced by existentialist anxiety, such as Albert Camus and the debate on nothingness. Sartre said: "Being precedes essence." This means that before anything else, man exists (for example, on stage) and only then does he define himself.

The relationship between existentialism and religion

The philosophy of existentialism believes that we cannot understand something that cannot be decomposed and combined. On the other hand, the being cannot be decomposed

and transformed into a concept; because the being is unique; therefore, theoretical knowledge is not enough. Sadra also says:

The mind, which only understands essences and general concepts, can never take possession of existence, which is the only reality. There is a fundamental difference between essence and existence. Essence does not exist in itself, but is merely abstracted in the mind from partial forms or levels of existence; therefore, it is a mental phenomenon. However, the mind is unable to take possession of the objective reality of existence. It tries to create a mental concept by abstraction; A concept that does not necessarily indicate the true essence of existence. In other words, Sadra, like the modern existentialists, believes that what exists is exclusively particular; therefore, it can be known through concepts, analogy, and mental structure; because these are universal concepts and existence is unique and particular. The modern existentialists agree with Sadra that existence is not an attribute, but the reality of all attributes. According to the traditional view, what is real, not merely possible, exists. This view leads to the idea that existence is contingent on existence, but both Sadra and the modern existentialists disagree with the aforementioned theory and believe that existence is not contingent on existence, but rather an act of existence, which consists in the actual transition from possibility to reality. Seyyed Hussein Nasr says: Sadra raised true metaphysics to the level of the act of existence, the mysterious luminous command that caused things to leave the ocean of nothingness and enjoy the gift of existence. In other words, for Sadra, metaphysics does not deal with the things that exist, that is, beings, but with the very ray that is cast from pure existence itself towards nothingness, the act of existence. Sometimes existentialism is considered a reaction against rationalism; for example, it is said that Kierkegaard's experience is the affirmation of irrational and immediate things such as existence, faith, and personality, against the universal values of reason that abolish what is individual and particular; in other words, his experience is against Hegelian rationalism. Guido Ruggiero notes:

Existence, by its irrationalism and its movement towards the transcendent, is a passionate protest against the abstract concept of the idealist religion of the original meaning. In every period, there has been a reaction against that religion called anti-rationalism, individualism and existence. This theory is further strengthened by a brief examination of the existentialist view of reason; for example, Pascal contrasts reason with the heart. It is clear that Pascal does not consider the two to be completely opposed; for he emphasizes that with Both kinds of truth can be attained by serious inquiry. It is obvious that rational argument must be free from any emotional bias. But he also believes that the fruits of the heart are at the opposite pole to those things which we believe by chance. Before a person can grasp such truths, God must have transformed his whole nature. Faith and reason

belong to two different realms and need not be in conflict with each other. In fact, both are inevitable. Reason applies principles which are essentially the same in all men, but only by faith can a person attain that which is unique in him. Pascal says: Sense, reason and faith each have their own properties and their own degree of determination. Kierkegaard, who is considered the father of modern existentialism, presents an anti-rational philosophy. He does not deny the value of objective scientific and logical thought; In other words, he does not deny the practical utility of mathematics, natural science, history, and metaphysical thought, but he attacks those who claim that this is the whole story; that objective or rationalistic thought is all that is involved. In short, each existentialist philosopher has expressed, in his own way, a dissatisfaction with reason and rationalism. Here, the question arises: what is Sadra's view of reason? Sadra consistently says that the nature of existence and its unity can only be experienced. As we have already noted, Sadra is based on experience; experience that gave him intuitive certainty, Sadra believes that when you try to "change your mind" about existence in the form of a concept, it ceases to be existence and becomes essence. The rational content of that experience must be placed in the context of life in order to be fully understood. If they are accepted only as rational propositions, they lose their character as truth. Sadra emphasizes that once something is known by direct perception or intuition, it cannot be refuted by pure logical reasoning. Therefore, according to Sadra, the structure of the human mind is such that it only understands concepts. Concepts are nothing but general ideas or essences. The mental faculty that formulates concepts is reason. Sadra affirms that the mind can only understand essences and not existence, which is an objective reality outside the mind. This indicates that reason cannot understand existence; because reason can only grasp rational concepts and sensory ideas and essences. But existence is neither a sensory idea nor an intellectual concept. Existence is an objective reality. Therefore, Sadra, like the modern existentialists, in a way, expresses displeasure with rationalism and reminds us of the limitations of reason. Apparently, he, like them, acknowledges that reason cannot comprehend the ultimate truth, that is, the reality of existence, which is unique and particular. Reason can grasp what is universal and subjective. Sadra, like the existentialists, emphasizes that rational propositions and logical arguments are not as conclusive as the living experience of truth; in other words, the conclusions reached are based on experience.

Despite the aforementioned similarities between Sadra and the modern existentialists, there are many differences between their philosophies. In this regard, we should keep the following points in mind:

1. New existentialism is essentially humanistic. The fundamental question of new existentialism is which principle comes first when man is the subject of discussion: existence or essence. Their answer is that in the case of man, existence comes first. What

does it mean to exist? In their view, existence is not a phenomenon. Existence is the transition from possibility to actuality, but in order to exist, it is not enough to pass from one state to another. True existence requires free will. Consequently, for new existentialism, existence is a distinctive feature of man. Existence is a permanent transcendence; that is, it transcends the situation in which a person is. Our essence is what we choose to be. Therefore, essence is secondary to existence; because we must exist in order to be able to choose. All new existentialists, with slight differences, hold this view. Of course, only in the case of man does existence come before essence; because in the world of our experience, he alone is free. All Other beings are forced, it is only in the case of man that we can know what he has chosen only after his choice. This discussion shows that the new existentialism is fundamentally anthropocentric; that is, its starting point and axis is man; man alone has the will and, according to this view, only he is free and autonomous. We have already noted that Sadra is also an existentialist; in the sense that he also believes in the originality of existence. But the question is whether his philosophy is anthropocentric like the new existentialism? Sadra's philosophy is not anthropocentric. There is no doubt that Sadra deals with pure Being in his metaphysics, fundamentally. But he is aware of the supreme transcendental essence and its boundless dignity and rank. His discussion of the Absolute, since it is completely indeterminate and has transcendental aspects, shows that his doctrine, even when it uses ontology, Ontology is not limited. At the beginning of his metaphysics, Sadra focuses on the supreme principle, which is superior to all limits and boundaries; then, he deals with pure being, which is the creative principle and the first determination of the supreme principle. Finally, he considers existence, both in terms of its general and particular characteristics. In short, for Sadra, existence is a universal principle and its priority does not only concern man. All beings in the world are dominated by it. Therefore, it can be concluded that Sadra's existentialism is not humanist. In this respect, his existentialism is much broader than modern existentialism. On the one hand, insofar as it concerns the beings of this world, It is related, it is inclusive; that is, it is fundamental for explaining the essence of reality, in terms of its origin and the various stages of its emergence; and on the other hand, it is transcendental; but modern existentialism, especially as it finds systematic expression in the thought of Heidegger and Sartre, is essentially an ontology or an existential discussion of beings.

“Nothingness” is another fundamental concept of modern existentialism. Nothingness encompasses the whole of existence. Traditional metaphysics says: from nothingness comes nothingness. The existentialist philosopher will say: from nothingness comes being. For him, being and nothingness are one. Hegel was aware of this. He believed that pure being is pure nothingness. Man cannot enter into his own essential nature and ask the metaphysical question unless he has the courage to face nothingness. Heidegger analyzes

the common language of the content of this answer is that "Nothingness is the opposite of everything that is" to get a clue. A layman would say:

By first confronting what is and then negating it, we can hope to confront nothingness. This brings us to true metaphysics, where the question is posed: What is that which is (existence)? In fact, we cannot understand what this what is, in its entirety or in terms of its total annihilation or nothingness, but rather some experiences reveal it. For example, boredom is such an experience. By boredom is meant not boredom with this or that thing, but boredom with everything. Everything, that is, the totality of what is, seems colorless, tasteless, and meaningless. Similarly, for Heidegger, anxiety is the fundamental way of getting to know nothingness. Sadra explains in his *Travels* a simple and general concept of "nothingness." For him, the lack of meaning is attributed to different subjects as "nothingness," and there is no difference in its meaning. Difference only arises when it becomes. That difference is the effect of these subjects. Reason conceives different subjects with different attributes, such as cause, condition, and conditioned effect, and Then he adds to them the concept of non-existence. Then the concept of non-cause or non-condition arises. It is true that the non-existence of a thing makes possible the existence of its opposite, for example, the non-existence of black makes possible the existence of white, but this difference is only relative. Regardless of this, it is not possible to distinguish non-existence from other non-existences. In short, non-existence is only one and cannot be divided into different types. In reality, there is no such thing as non-existence, the cause, "non-existence." Similarly, if "this is non-existence," one cannot point to anything and say, "What is non-existence?" So if someone asks, "To be known," it simply means that existence is not a cause. Sadra concludes that non-existence, insofar as it is non-existence, does not exist. He then analyzes how human reason can make a concept out of something that does not exist and then use it as a subject. He believes that reason has the power to conceive and construct all kinds of (rational) concepts and ideas. (sensible); for example, reason can construct the concept of its own non-existence and can even construct the concept of absolute non-existence. In other words, for Sadra, non-existence is only a mental construct, not a reality. The discovery of existence is through existence, and on the other hand, the discovery of non-existence is also through existence. From the above discussion, the following conclusions can be deduced:

Existence is a fundamental matter. For Sadra, non-existence is secondary to necessary existence and possible existence. Sadra's statements show that he means by non-existence merely the logical act of negation, not nothingness. But Heidegger will say that the former (logical negation) is merely the logical and apparent state of the latter (non-being). The difference between individuals, the intensity of disgust, the pain of rejection, and the

bitterness of rejection are forms of non-existence that are more intense than the logical act of denial or negation.

The above discussion shows that Sadra tries to understand non-existence with the help of reason, while in the case of existence, He has already said that reason cannot be known by reason, but rather “non-existence” cannot understand objective reality.

Human originality

It should be said that in fact the term human originality has two completely different meanings:

In the human originality school, one can arrive at the theory that man is considered as the ultimate goal and transcendent values. This concept of human originality can be found in the thoughts of Cocteau. For example, in his story called *Around the World in Eighty Hours*, one of the heroes, when flying over the mountains in an airplane, says: “Man is a marvel.” This means that I, who did not have a share in building the airplane, use a few specific inventions that others have made, and I can personally consider myself responsible for the specific actions of a few people as a human being. This means that we can value man completely based on the best behavior of some people. This type of human originality is false. Because only horses and dogs may have a general judgment about man and say that “man is a marvel.” “And these animals - at least as far as I know - are not in the business of making such a judgment. But it cannot be accepted that a human being can make such a judgment about a human being. Existentialism exempts a human being from any such judgment. Existentialism never presents human beings as a goal and end. Because human beings must be rebuilt every moment. We should not think that there is a humanity that can be worshipped as a religion. As Auguste Comte thought. Worshipping humanity leads to Auguste Comte's theory of human originality, which contains philosophy, and it must be admitted that this thought leads to fascism. Such human originality is not useful to us.

Existentialist human originality

But another meaning can also be found in human originality, which in the depth of its concept is as follows:

Human beings are eternally outside themselves. Human beings, by establishing their "project" in the world outside themselves and with The disappearance into the embryo of the world creates man and his humanity. On the other hand, human existence is dependent on higher quests. Man, by this ascension and because he does not consider things except

in relation to this ascension, is in the midst and at the heart of this ascension. There is no world but the human world. The world of human introspection. What we call existentialist human originality is the combination of the search for higher goals and introspection: the higher goal as the creator of man (and not in the sense that the necessary being is the "higher goal", but in the sense that man eternally goes beyond his own limits) and introspection in the sense that man is not limited in himself. Rather, he is constantly present "in the human world". Hence, we use the term human originality to say that in the world, there is no law-making except man. To say that man decides about himself in abandonment (i.e., breaking away from the necessary being). And also because we say: man is an exploration and search in his nature. It is not Satan. Rather, it is precisely in the pursuit of a goal outside oneself – that is, in the abstraction, liberation, and realization of plans that man realizes himself as man.

Considering the concepts and writings described in the above text, it can be said:

Existentialism is an attempt to extract all the effects and results of a structured situation, relying on the Necessary. Existentialism never wants to immerse man in despair. But if, according to Christians, you do not believe in any Necessary thought, it is considered despair. In this case, the basis of the work of existentialism is despair. Existentialism is not an atheistic philosophy in the sense that it devotes its efforts entirely to proving the invalidity of the Necessary. Rather, in a more correct sense, it declares that even assuming the Necessary, the work does not change. This is our philosophy and our belief. And of course, this does not mean that we believe in the Necessary Being, but rather that in our opinion, the fundamental issue is not the existence of the Necessary Being. What is important is that man must personally rediscover himself and be certain that nothing can free him from himself, even if he finds evidence that the Necessary Being exists. In this sense, existentialism is a philosophy of optimism. It is a theory based on action, and it must be said that it is only with bad intentions that Christians can call us pessimists by attributing their despair to us.

Soren Kierkegaard

Søren Kierkegaard (1813–1855), also known as Kierkegaard, was a Danish Christian philosopher who dealt with the issues of existence, choice, and commitment, and who fundamentally influenced modern theology and philosophy, especially the existentialist philosophy of existentialism. He is often referred to as the father of existentialism.

Philosophical outlook

Kierkegaard's works are deliberately unsystematic, consisting of essays, short speeches, discourses, fictional letters, diaries, and other literary forms. Most of his works were originally published under pseudonyms. He chose the term existential for his philosophy because he saw philosophy as an expression of a rigorously tested individual life, not as the construction of a unified system in the manner of the 19th-century German philosopher Georg Wilhelm Friedrich Hegel, whom Kierkegaard attacked in his final epigraph to *The Unscientific* (1846: trans. 1941). Hegel claimed to have achieved a complete rational understanding of human life and history: Kierkegaard, on the other hand, pointed to the ambiguous and contradictory nature of the human situation. He challenged the extra-subjective and rational statement of the fundamental questions of life: for him the highest truth is an intra-subjective or individual truth.

The Choice of Life

Kierkegaard claimed that systematic philosophy not only presented a false view of human life but also, by often expressing life in terms of logical necessity, became a way of concealing choice and responsibility in individuals. He believes that individuals create their own nature through their choices; what must be done in the absence of generalities and extra-subjective criteria. The value of a choice can only be determined individually.[4] He could also find himself "on the brink" when he was a theology student at the University of Copenhagen, relentlessly reading serious literary and philosophical texts. Søren would nestle in the back row of his classroom, reading novels, just as the professor would tear up at the opportunity God had given him to guide these young people. He gambled until his father paid for his university, racking up debt upon debt, and forcing his father to pay him additional stipends, which of course he had to, otherwise Søren would not have been able to complete his theology studies and would have been dependent on his father. In his first major work, *Either/Or* (2 vols., 1843; translated 1944), Kierkegaard described two stages of existence from which a person may choose: the sensual stage and the moral stage. The sensual way of life is a refined hedonism. It involves the search for pleasure and a state of refinement.[4] The sensual person is constantly seeking variety and novelty, and is trying to ward off suffering. But he is ultimately met with despair and suffering. The moral way of life involves a kind of passionate, enthusiastic, and unconditional devotion to duty, social, and religious duties. He divided life into three stages, which he called the aesthetic stage, the moral stage, and finally the religious stage. In his other work, *Stages in the Path of Life* (1845: translated 1941), Kierkegaard identifies a number of individual responsibilities in this obedience, and also describes a third stage: the religious stage, in which the person submits to the will of God and in doing so finds genuine freedom. In *Fear and Trembling* (1846: translated 1941), Kierkegaard focuses on God's command to

Abraham to sacrifice his son Isaac, an act that violates Abraham's moral convictions. Abraham proves his faith steadfastly by setting out to obey God's command, even though he cannot understand it.[4] The introduction by Jean Valjean in the French translation and, of course, in the Persian translation by Abdolkarim Rashidian is instructive. This "suspension of the moral judgment," as Kierkegaard declares, allows Abraham to attain a proper devotion to God. To avoid ultimate despair, one must make something like a "leap of faith" into a religious life, which is inherently contradictory, ambiguous, and fraught with danger. One is called to it by a sense of dread (The Concept of Dread, 1844: transl. 1944), which is ultimately a kind of fear of nothingness.

Reason and Faith

For Kierkegaard, faith is not a kind of recognition, it is a passionate movement of the will towards the eternal bliss that man has always desired. This passion overcomes any hesitation and hesitation from without and is directed towards something contrary to custom and consensus or irrational and impossible; for revelation and inspiration are not only superior to reason, they are contrary to reason. For Kierkegaard, the loss of reason in order to find God is pure faith. Suffering and suffering are essential to the Christian life, faith itself is a kind of suffering, "the crucifixion of reason." Christianity is not a philosophical doctrine to be understood in the light of rational speculations; for Christ was not a philosopher, and his apostles did not form a small community of scholars. Kierkegaard believes that the first person to defend the Christian religion was in fact another Judas. In other words, the first theologian is the second Judas. "He also betrays with a kiss, but this kiss is foolishness. I consider the one who defends the Christian religion to be an unbeliever." In Kierkegaard's thought, God is not an object, so God shows his contamination by creating a sense of human alienation from God and sin.

Late works

Kierkegaard became involved in bitter controversies in the last days of his life, especially with the founding of the Danish Lutheran Church, which he considered to be a material and corrupt thing. His late works, As in The Sickness Unto Death (1849: translated 1941), it reflects an increasingly gloomy and dark vision of Christianity, emphasizing suffering as the essence of true faith. He often directed his attack on modern European society, which he denounced in The Present Age (1846: translated 1940) for its lack of passion and quantitative values. The insistence on his writings and his frequent polemics gradually undermined his health. He suffered a stroke in the street in October 1855, and died on 11 November 1855.

Influence

Kierkegaard's influence was initially limited to Scandinavia and German-speaking Europe, where his work had a strong connection with Protestant theology, and also on writers such as Franz Kafka. As existential philosophy emerged as a widespread European movement after World War I, Kierkegaard's works were widely translated, and he became recognized as one of the major figures of the new culture.

The "Leap" that Danish philosopher Søren Kierkegaard also called the Qualitative Leap is one of the main ideas of his philosophy, which later became known as the Leap of Faith. Søren Kierkegaard is a philosopher whose power, clarity, and intensity of emotions in his writings create the same feeling that reading Nietzsche's philosophical thoughts creates, and therefore it is not surprising that, given the deep humanism that was seen in the eyes of these two philosophers, both are considered the ancestors of modern existentialism in the 19th century. Despite the difference in importance of Kierkegaard's theism and Nietzsche's atheism, both philosophers were not afraid to stand up against public opinion and openly express their opinions and passionately defend human individuality against the crowd. Neither loneliness, nor poverty, nor the pressure of public opinion prevented them from expressing their beliefs, and they did not stop living their philosophy with strength until the last moment of their lives. Kierkegaard was a staunch defender of recognition "Individual inner experience" (Subjective Truth) as a truth to live alongside "external objective experience" (Objective Truth) as a truth to know.

During his lifetime, Kierkegaard launched three simultaneous attacks on his society:

- Attacking the Christian Church and condemning the Church for destroying human individuality and religious faith
- Attacking newspapers and magazines for trying to shape public opinions in a uniform manner and eliminating individual thought and the importance of thinking
- Attacking Hegel's philosophy, which was the undisputed and dominant power of the philosophical tradition of nineteenth-century Europe, for removing man from the text of philosophy and reducing humanity to human history

Kierkegaard paid a heavy price for fighting on these three fronts, and during his lifetime his critics and enemies were a collection of powerful figures in the Christian Church, owners of public publications and newspapers, and philosophers of his time, which naturally made him the number one enemy of his society, while he did not stop for a moment his passionate defense of the individual people whose individuality was being

crushed under the hammer of the church, the mass media, and the Hegelian philosophical system.

Søren Kierkegaard wrote in his manuscripts on May 14, 1847:

My will is that you write on my grave only "One" The Individual.

In his philosophy, Kierkegaard believed that there are three ways to live:

Aesthetic mode of life

Living with the aim of pleasure,

Enjoying life and the beauty of friendship

Ethical mode of life

Living with the aim of adhering to and realizing a belief and a moral goal

Religious mode of life - leap of faith

To passionately live what we believe in

Even if it goes against popular beliefs and the forces that govern life

In the audio file presented below, this idea is rewritten in the form of a simple literary text and simplified with examples.

This speech is presented in three acts:

Act One:

The first part of this text deals with the first level of life, or the Aesthetic mode of life, which encompasses the dominant approach of humans to life. A way of life in which the goal of everything we do is to find pleasure in it to find a good feeling. In this way of living, Pleasure is the main motivation and goal of life (a form of psychological hedonism). Someone who lives according to this way is constantly searching for variety and novelty and is trying to remove the suffering of life from himself. Will he be able to find meaning, lasting happiness, and pleasure without pain, and to continue it in his life? Can a life that is based solely on pleasure encompass and fulfill the full feeling and capacity of being human?

Act Two:

The second way of living is for ethical duty (Ethical Mode of life). At this stage we live to fulfill the duties we have undertaken. Someone who enters this stage can rise above the

pleasures of life and ignore them to fulfill a goal that he considers important, but this goal is still imposed on him as a duty by family, tribe, society, religion and popular beliefs.

This way of life is favored and supported by the forces that have defined these duties for us. In this way of living, we serve these beliefs and dedicate our lives to their fulfillment, but with all this sense of belonging, Kierkegaard does not consider such a belief to be equivalent to faith and sees a deep gap between this moral devotion and faith. Most believers of various ideologies who are ready to dedicate themselves to their belief fall into this group, and if someone dedicates their entire life to such a way of living, Kierkegaard calls him a knight of infinite resignation. Someone who passes through everything in his existence for his belief. This way of living is consistent with rationalizing and trying to justify actions based on what has been learned through belief. This way of living is a way of surrendering to a belief that has been dictated to us from the outside. So, if we match Kierkegaard's thoughts to the theory of interactional analysis and the descriptive circles of personality in it, namely child, parent and adult, the first two areas of Kierkegaard's living can be considered living in the child (felt concepts) and living in the parent (learned concepts). However, for Kierkegaard, entering the adult or the same thought concepts is not the end, but the beginning of a radical action that he calls the Leap.

Act Three: Kierkegaard believed that thought is always focused on something and when it is not focused on the "I", it inevitably leaves the first area, i.e. life for pleasure (child in psychological terms), and if it is not focused on the "other", it will also cross the border of the second method, i.e. duty (parent in psychological terms). A thinker who surrenders his foundation neither to the "I/child/felt life" nor to the "others/parent/learned life" and considers only a truth worthy of his mature thinking that is beyond the "Ego" and others/society/general opinions, places the person who thinks about such a truth on the verge of a leap of faith. For Kierkegaard, this leap is a transcendental act and irrational in its essence. The transcendent in Kierkegaard's thought is something beyond the historical thought of man, and between Transcendence and man there is an abyss whose depth can only be overcome by a leap of faith. For such a leap, one must first free oneself from the tyranny of scientism and rationalism and change direction from extroversion to introversion, from collective rationalism to personal empiricism. In Kierkegaard's philosophy, apart from the objective truth that exists in the outside world and is studied by science, there is also an internal subjective truth that is your inner truth, and although this truth cannot be measured by any scientific means, it is true for you. In Kierkegaard's thought, this truth is not a "belief" but a "action" and for this reason it must be lived in one's individuality, and living this truth requires a "leap of faith." A leap of faith is the only possible way to fundamentally change from a "way of being" to a "way of being." The one who makes such a leap is a Knight of Faith. Faith is a leap into the unknown and

darkness that can conflict with both morality and social traditions and even apparent religious beliefs. The leap of faith is not the recognition of truth, but the surrender to it, which is inherently irrational and non-negotiable. It is full of passion and determination that comes from within and is not committed to anything external. The leap of faith is the overcoming of any hesitation and doubt that we find rational! In *Fear and Trembling*, Kierkegaard examines the story of Abraham and Isaac/Ishmael and interprets it from the perspective of his philosophy. According to Kierkegaard, if Abraham had taken Isaac to the altar with the thought that I will sacrifice Isaac because it is God's will and I have no choice but to do so and that Isaac is doomed to destruction based on this, this would have made him the only devotee and believer who would be the only knight of infinite resignation and not what Kierkegaard calls the Knight of Faith. According to Kierkegaard, this story symbolizes how faith overcomes social morality, religion, logic and everything that seems right and how the knight of faith throws himself beyond good and evil. In this story, Isaac/Ishmael is the beloved and long-awaited son of Abraham. Isaac/Ishmael is a symbol of the most desired and cherished possessions in our lives and killing him in the image of infanticide is an act that goes against morality. The general religion and traditions are condemned and indefensible and unspeakable. This leap is not only the leap of Abraham but also the leap of Isaac. From Kierkegaard's perspective, this story can be seen as: killing the greatest desire of life and crossing the boundaries of morality, society, tradition and logic as a leap into the darkest darkness with the belief that everything you kill you will achieve with your inexplicable leap and no one... no one except those who choose the leap of faith will understand the meaning of what you are doing. In Kierkegaard's thought, faith is neither asceticism nor belief! Faith is an irrational leap beyond good and evil, and in this incomprehensible leap into the depths of darkness there is something infinitely personal and indisputable that only those who choose the leap of faith are aware of in their hearts. Kierkegaard believed that what our world suffers from is the lack of passion and faith. In his opinion, true faith gives us individuality, and traditional religion and ideology rob us of individuality. Kierkegaard and Nietzsche were two completely different sides of a belief that sees man as strong and unique, and wants to be strong in the face of life's suffering.

A leap of faith in philosophy is the act of believing or accepting something not based on reason. The term is associated with the Danish philosopher Søren Kierkegaard.

Terminological usage

As a term, a leap of faith can refer to the act of believing in something that is unprovable.[1] The term can also refer to a risky act that a person undertakes in the hope of a positive outcome.[2] Additionally, a leap of faith may refer to a mechanic in video

games in which the player is forced to jump to a platform or location that is not visible from the player's current position.

Background

The term is attributed to Søren Kierkegaard, although he never used the term "leap of faith", but referred to a "qualitative leap".

The concept of a leap of faith can have positive or negative connotations, depending on the context, as some feel it is a virtue to believe in something without evidence, while others consider it foolishness.

Development of the concept by Kierkegaard

A leap of faith, according to Kierkegaard, involves a turning, because the leap is made by faith. In his book *The Unscientific Thesis of Philosophical Postscripts*, Kierkegaard describes this leap: "Thought can turn on itself to think about itself and doubts and doubts arise. But this thinking about itself never does anything." Kierkegaard says that thinking must serve something by thinking. Kierkegaard wants to stop the "practice of self-reflection," and this is the movement that constitutes a leap. Kierkegaard was an orthodox Scandinavian Lutheran who was at odds with the liberal theological establishment of his time. His works included the orthodox Lutheran notion of a God who accepts man unconditionally, and that faith itself is a gift from God, and that the highest moral standing is achieved when a person realizes this and no longer depends on him or herself, and makes a leap of faith into the arms of a loving God. Kierkegaard describes the "leap" using the story of Adam and Eve, specifically the qualitative "leap" of Adam into sin. Adam's leap means a change from one quality to another; the quality of not being sinful to the quality of being sinful. Kierkegaard writes that the transition from one quality to another is possible only by a "leap".^[6] When a transition occurs, a person moves directly from one state to the other and never has both qualities.^[6] Note that Kierkegaard writes: "Man becomes aware at the moment that he has come into the world; Because his previous state, which he may not have adhered to, was a state of non-being. Kierkegaard felt that, because of the contradictions in Christianity, a leap of faith was essential in accepting Christianity. In his books *Philosophical Postscripts* and his non-scientific treatise *Philosophical Postscripts*, Kierkegaard addresses the paradoxes of Christianity. Kierkegaard agreed with Gottold Ephraim Lessing in describing this leap. Kierkegaard's use of the term "leap" was in response to Lessing's "ditch" that Lessing addressed in his theological writings. Both Lessing and Kierkegaard discuss the factor that may be used to invoke faith. Lessing attempted to directly combat rational Christianity, and when he failed, he fought it indirectly through what Kierkegaard called "imaginary structures".^[10] Both were influenced by Jean-Jacques Rousseau. In 1950, philosopher Vincent Edward Smith wrote

that "Lessing and Kierkegaard declare in a typical way that there is no bridge between historical and finite knowledge and the existence and nature of God." In 1946, Kierkegaard wrote: "A leap is made easier to the extent that there is a distance between the initial position and the place from which the leap is made. And so it is with a decisive move in the realm of the spirit. The most difficult action is not when one is far from the decision (as when a non-Christian is on the verge of deciding to become a Christian), but when it seems as if the matter has already been decided.

Paul Tillich

Paul Tillich (August 20, 1886 – October 22, 1965) was a famous German-born theologian and philosopher and the greatest American theologian of the 20th century. In general, his main goal in all his scientific and academic activities was to introduce Christianity in an understandable and convincing way to the people.

In his works, he tries to reconcile contemporary culture and historical Christianity in some way, hence his general tendency in dealing with theology can be considered completely pragmatic; that is, by observing the fundamental problems of humanity, he tries to read historical Christianity in a new way in order to provide an appropriate and reasonable answer to the emerging questions of humanity in the light of it. All of his remaining works are in fact an answer to two questions: first, why is human existence always threatened? second, what is the factor that has so far been able to resist such threats? The element of culture is considered the key word in understanding Tillich's theological thoughts. According to Tillich, there is a mutual and interdependent relationship between religion and culture. The relationship between religion and culture is like a question and answer relationship or form and substance. The form of religion is culture, and the content and substance of culture is religion. In Tillich's thought, the path of the relationship between the categories of culture and religion is such that one must always go to religion and get answers to problems and questions. Fundamental problems and questions that arise from the presence of mankind in the new conditions and requirements of the modern world. Such problems are initially identified by the elites of each society and crystallized and manifested in prominent artistic styles or social and political ideas. According to Tillich, the answer to all new human problems is manifested in religious symbols, and in fact, the mission of theologians and theologians of each religion is to provide society with appropriate and suitable answers by decoding these symbols.

Lifetime

Paul Tillich was born in 1886 into a religious family. His father was a conservative priest and a follower of Luther's ideas. After completing his preparatory education, he entered the University of Berlin and pursued his postgraduate studies at the University of

Tübingen, the University of Halle, and the University of Breslau. He received his doctorate from the University of Breslau in 1912. Paul Tillich's doctoral thesis was dedicated to introducing the philosophical and theological thoughts of the 19th-century philosopher Friedrich Schelling. At the same time as World War I, Tillich, with his religious and reformist tendencies, entered the German army as a missionary and served in this position for four years. Perhaps the first turning point in his life can be considered this period when he witnessed the presence of destructive and threatening forces of humanity with all his heart. In 1918, influenced by socialist ideas, he left the German army while having transformed from a conservative Lutheran into a passionate and rebellious young man who spoke with despair and pessimism about many of the religious teachings of Christianity and Western culture.

Tillich believed that the transformation of oneself required a profound transformation of Western civilization, and therefore began to explain his ideas in the form of sermons and scientific lectures in the fields of culture and theology. His first lecture, entitled *The Concept of the Theology of Culture*, in Berlin, was the concern of all his subsequent efforts. Berlin was the center of all kinds of political and social conflicts in those days, and of course art. Tillich taught at the University of Berlin, the University of Marburg, and the University of Frankfurt between 1925 and 1929, but during these years he was more involved in religious studies at the Institute of Modern Theology than teaching. In 1933, at the age of 47, Tillich published a book based on socialist and anti-fascist ideas, entitled *The Decision of Socialism*, in which the ideology of Nazism was criticized. This book became an excuse for his expulsion from the university and his escape to the United States. Tillich's protest history gradually brought his ideas to the fore, but his untimely arrival in a strange country with a foreign language caused a significant pause in Tillich's thoughts, but due to his fifteen-year teaching at the New York Theological Seminary, he became a respected figure among Americans, and since his accessible works until then were in a language other than English, he began to write in English despite all the difficulties of the new language. He published his first autobiography, entitled *On the Borderline*, which was not very well received. But his next book, entitled *The Unsettled Foundations*, which contained some of the sermons he delivered in the New York Theological Seminary chapel, achieved extraordinary fame. After the publication of the first volume of the three-volume series *Systematic Theology* in 1951, the topics of this book became a constant topic in American academic and church circles of the time. In 1955, after retiring from the Eliot Seminary, he succeeded in obtaining a teaching chair at Harvard University. The second volume of *Systematic Theology* was published in 1957, and while teaching at the University of Chicago in 1962, he decorated the third volume of this work with his writing.

Tillich died in 1965, known as one of the most influential theologians of his time, and his works occupied many passionate discussions in academic circles throughout the Christian world for a long time after his death.

Views and Topics

Tillich's theological views are mostly reflected in the three-volume collection *Systematic Theology*. In this collection, he attempts to establish a logical and convincing relationship between contemporary human culture of the twentieth century and historical Christianity. He believes in the mutual need of the category of faith and new culture. Tillich believes that apologetics is not a specialized branch of Christian theology, but a continuation of every theological section. In *Systematic Theology*, there is always a correlation between religion and culture. The form of religion is culture, and the essence and content of culture is religion. This means that one can always obtain answers to new problems from religion. So, first the fundamental issues. The essence of the world is known by the elites of each society, then these issues are manifested in the form of works of art and social thoughts, then religious experts find, decode and present appropriate symbolic answers from religious symbols. Therefore, in order to adapt and overcome the disorders of each era, it is necessary to always have a close relationship between the elites and religious experts.

Tillich's Ontology

Tillich's ontology must be sought entirely in his systemic thought. Perhaps influenced by existentialism, Tillich set his point of departure in existence; because in his opinion, there are moments in our lives that are threatened by meaninglessness, sin and death. He draws three ways of image and manifestation for existence and everything that has any amount of reality:

1. Subjective: The object consists of a unified whole in such a way that it functions as a completely independent system;
2. Creature: The object as part of a larger integrated whole that interacts with other members;
3. Finite: An object that is inherently vulnerable to the threat of collapse and separation from its own.

In Tillich's ontology, man is a creature and a finite being. He proves this with two separate arguments. In fact, the creaturehood of man and, consequently, divine power, is an answer to Tillich's second question, which is what is the cure for cultural finitude? How can man resist the destructive forces that threaten human life? He makes it clear with this argument that in order to be safe from fear and threat, we have no other way but to return to God as

the creator. It is God who, as the Almighty, always protects man from suffering and fear, sin and death, meaninglessness and emptiness and gives him peace. Tillich believes that we humans are finite beings who are inherently threatened by nothingness, while at the same time we ourselves experience resistance to these threats. Such a force is omnipotent, living, and sustaining, and ultimately the creator of man. This force is God.

Man is a created being

- Introduction 1) Our lives are always threatened by non-beings such as meaninglessness, sin, and death.
- Introduction 2) We all witness a kind of constant resistance to these threats.
- Introduction 3) The source of such resistance is not within ourselves.
- Conclusion) Such a source is our Creator and sustainer, who is manifested in the Christian symbol of God as the Creator.

Man is a finite being

Among Christian philosophers and theologians, Tillich's ontology enjoys worldwide fame. The reason for this is the presence of the philosophical existential approach on his theological foundations. Some philosophers believe that the reality of God can be proven by a careful analysis of existence, but Tillich does not think this way. In his ontological analysis, Tillich starts from the bottom up, that is, from his own existence, and in this respect he follows the same path that all existentialist philosophers before him, especially Heidegger, have taken. In this way, by analyzing the existence of man as a creature, he ends up with his poverty and need for the Creator and Preserver, and from there he proves attributes such as life and power for him. But how is man finite? In the previous argument, it became clear that man is a created being, that is, he is considered part of an integrated whole that needs to interact with other members of the set. On the one hand, the creatureliness of the universe requires that all actions and reactions within it, including our relationship with the world, have a single structure; that is, if there is balance among the elements of the universe, such elements in the existence of man must also have a balance. Therefore, man needs to create a balance in his existence in order to harmonize with the structure of the universe. In this argument, presence in polar categories and elements means finitude and limitation. Another form of argument is as follows:

- Premise 1) Man is a creature and part of a unified whole.
- Premise 2) The structure of creation is based on a balance in polar elements.

- Conclusion) Since man is a creature and a creature is enclosed in polar elements, therefore man is a finite being.

The structure of creation and polar elements

In Tillich's view, the universe has elements that allow the system to behave with its constituent parts in a completely unified way and according to a law. At the same time, these elements have a polar characteristic, meaning that everything in the universe is in a balanced position between the two ends of the pole. The polar elements present in the structure of creation are:

1. Individuality and participation,
2. Dynamics and form,
3. Freedom and destiny.

Everything in this finite and limited universe is in a balanced state between the two ends of the spectrum of each of these elements. It is natural that in order to treat human disorders, by considering man as a part of the coherent parts of the universe, an appropriate response to the unbalanced state of man in relation to these elements can be found by analyzing the equilibrium state of other parts of existence.

Individuality and participation

All parts of existence, while maintaining individual individuality and development, are in complete harmony with other parts, in such a way that the participation of these parts does not threaten their individuality. Man, in harmony with the universe, while being forced to move from individuality to participation, must at the same time achieve a balanced state in terms of individuality and participation, so that in the shadow of which he can both achieve development and establish balance with others, including humans and his environment.

Dynamics and Form

Also, in all parts of existence there is a kind of movement, innovation and creativity that sometimes man sees such seemingly fixed laws and forms as changed. We humans need to create a balance between the two poles of dynamics and law in order to harmonize with existence. If man breaks the legal boundaries to achieve freedom, society will suffer from disorder and abnormality, and in the same proportion, ignoring the creativity and dynamics of individuals will cause protests and revolutions in societies, and laws will seem inflexible and rigid.

Freedom and Destiny

Existence is always fraught with the two boundaries of freedom and destiny. Although freedom is focused on the will, the idea of chaos for existence is incompatible with the assumption of its creation. Existence has freedom of action to the extent that it does not create a disruption in its position in the system. Man is affected by history in his interaction with the world. Destiny at any moment shows the definitive path of our future, and the exercise of freedom by the parts of the world is always accompanied by a sense of responsibility and commitment to the entire coherent system.

The End of Attachment

After examining the human condition in existence and explaining the finitude and creatureliness of man due to his presence in the polar elements of the universe, Tillich explains that our experience of resistance to threats that originate outside the sphere of our will and desire is the ultimate attachment of man, namely God.

Five Systematic Questions

All of Tillich's systemic ideas can be traced to five fundamental questions. Questions that stem from a completely polar concept of threat and resistance. In Tillich's thought, humanity has always been threatened by factors such as meaninglessness, sin, and death, but what is puzzling is that despite all the threats, everyone has experienced constant resistance to these threats, which at the same time has been from something that he knows does not originate within himself. Using a model that he himself invented, Tillich has attempted to answer this ambiguity in his collection of works as to what the major issues are and what the appropriate response to each of them would be by rereading the religious symbols found in historical Christianity. The five basic questions are mentioned below.

1. How can one recognize the truth that is important from a human perspective?
2. How can one stand against the destructive forces that threaten human life?
3. How can one cure the problem of alienation?
4. How can our life be authentic when morality, practices, and cultural manifestations are completely ambiguous?
5. Does history have meaning?

The answers to these questions have been selected from among the symbols of the Christian religion in a completely coherent and coherent manner, in such a way that each

answer, in addition to being a convincing factor in the same question, is in a reciprocal relationship with other major issues.

1. The symbol of Logos for answering the problem of knowledge.
2. The symbol of God as creator to answer the problem of cultural finitude.
3. The symbol of Jesus as Christ to answer the problem of alienation.
4. The symbol of the Holy Spirit as an answer to ambiguity in the new culture.
5. The symbol of the kingdom of God as an answer to the meaning of history.

Paul Tillich's theological system begins with epistemology. He believes that knowledge both enables understanding of the world and enables domination of the world. Tillich's method of problem-finding and problem-solving was mentioned earlier. Tillich's questions usually convey a state of ambiguity to the audience and then seek to resolve this ambiguity; for example, when he paints a picture of humanity that has been threatened with death throughout history, he then raises the ambiguity of what force supports him despite such a threat? It is after this ambiguity that he presents the decoded answer from Christianity. Such a trend is also observed in the problem of knowledge. One of Tillich's first questions after World War I was the question of the origin of the threat of meaninglessness. By posing the question, what is the answer to meaninglessness? And how can one know the truth? He immediately raises the following ambiguity that despite such a threat, man has sufficient knowledge to continue his life. So where does this knowledge come from? In which Christian symbol can the answer be explained? By presenting these premises, he enters into the discussion of epistemology, the position of Logos, and the relationship of reason to revelation. By dividing reason into instrumental reason and ontological reason, Tillich expresses characteristics for ontological reason. In Tillich's opinion, in fact, the act of knowing is carried out by means of ontological reason, and in many ways such reason is richer than instrumental reason.

The Relationship of Reason and Revelation

Tillich introduces the symbolic concept of Logos as an answer to the problem of knowledge. Logos is a Greek word meaning reason, word, thought, and contemplation. Opposite the concept of Logos is Ontos, which is used to mean what exists. According to Tillich, Logos is the symbol that actually confronts the issue of skepticism. But reason alone is not capable of knowledge, and in this conflict between knowledge and skepticism, as long as reason alone is in the field, it is exposed to threat and defeat because reason is a creature and every creature is finite. Reason is always threatened by polar elements in the path of knowledge and shaping existence. The first group of polar elements of

knowledge includes the formal and emotional dimensions of reality. The rational understanding of reality always comes and goes between the two poles of form and emotion, and the formal and emotional functions are sometimes in conflict with each other, while man is forced to create a balance between these polar dimensions in order to harmonize with the world and somehow give them unity and coherence. The second group of polar elements of knowledge are the static and dynamic aspects of understanding reality. In a rational understanding of reality, both aspects must be in a state of balance and equilibrium. A tendency towards the static dimension of reality leads to conservatism and absolutism, and an excess of the dynamic aspects of reality leads to entanglement in the abyss of It is self-centeredness. The third group of polar elements of cognition is the conflict between reliance on oneself or reliance on the other as the ultimate authority in cognition. Man must also consider the balance between these two elements in cognition. In any case, self-centeredness and other-centeredness return to accepting the law. If the centering is with oneself, the criterion of reality and legitimacy of every law returns to oneself, and if the centering is solely with something outside oneself, the other is recognized as the law and the self is sacrificed. According to Tillich, the root of such a conflict between self-centeredness and other-centeredness lies in the structure and core of reason. The structure of reason is the mechanism of understanding and formatting reality, through which man is able to distinguish between good and bad, ugliness and beauty, and also to judge the truth of a claim. In contrast, this core is the reason that is the basis of rational interactions even when there is no awareness or consideration of it. With such a tool, man is able to understand pure truth, pure beauty, or pure goodness. Ultimately, it is with the kernel of reason that man will be able to understand the ultimate criteria expressing the existence and presence of the power of being (simply existing). In Tillich's thought, man always yearns for a kind of knowledge that is free from the constraints of alienation and dependence on himself. He calls such a state of cognitive equilibrium revelation. Revelation is in fact the manifestation of our ultimate attachment and the origin of resistance to the meaninglessness of our life, which has been manifested in the symbol of Jesus as the Messiah.

Analysis of the revelatory event and the answer to the problem of skepticism

So far, in answering the problem of skepticism, it has been revealed that reason, in order to know, always faces conflicts in the polar elements of the universe. The conflict between the element of emotion and form, the conflict between the objective element and the absolute element, and the conflict between egocentrism and other-centeredness are the tensions that have caused man to be subject to the problem of skepticism. In tracing the roots of these conflicts, Tillich sees the existence of such conflicts in the conflict between the structure of reason and the kernel of reason. He says that in the structure of reason,

man is concerned with the framing of reality in terms of evil and good, ugliness and beauty, or truth and falsehood, while at the core of reason, rational interactions belong to a higher realm that is dedicated to understanding and distinguishing between pure and mere matters, whether he pays attention to this interaction and knowledge or is oblivious to it due to its proximity to the head. The essential point is that the presence of such ultimate criteria as pure goodness, pure truth, and pure beauty indicates the presence of the power of existence in our minds. This is precisely why man has been in tension and questioning in historical periods between relying on himself or on others.

Tillich's next step after this analysis and rooting out of the problem of skepticism is to present a theological response from historical Christianity to this issue. According to Tillich, in order to respond to the problem of skepticism, one must first recognize the origin of resistance to skepticism. One must address the question of what constitutes the essence of resistance to skepticism, despite the existence of cognitive tensions and conflicts? What factor is present in the human mind that is the opposite of egocentrism, formalism, and staticity? Tillich believes that we have all experienced the existence of such a force within ourselves, that we all find such a common and intuitive perception within ourselves, and that we ultimately rely on it against the onslaught of dubious illusions. For this reason, we are attached to such a common reality and consider its persuasive power to be beyond the power of any doubt. Tillich calls this attachment and attachment the ultimate attachment. In his view, the ultimate attachment means our deepest connection with that which is the origin of our life, namely revelation.

Revelation, Ecstasy, and Miracle

In explaining the nature of revelation, Tillich examines every manifestation of a revelatory event from two areas and two aspects: 1) the aspect of the recipient or experiencer; 2) the aspect of the giver or giver. In the receptive aspect, in fact, a revelatory event occurs when the state of revelation encompasses the entire being of the recipient and has immersed him in attachment. Tillich calls such an experience, which all believers experience at every moment of their faith, an ecstatic experience. In fact, ecstasy is a state in which the intellect, in self-consciously understanding the core of the intellect, transcends itself and experiences the source and preserver of the intellect.

The second aspect of every revelatory experience is the giving aspect. According to Tillich, the experience that exists in the giving aspect always has such characteristics that, first, it is symbolic and symbolic, and second, it has originated directly from the source of meaning. On the other hand, such an experience of the source of meaning does not mean knowing this source, because the source of meaning is inherently secret and hidden even in revelation or revelation. The source of meaning is not among the other knowable

subjects and is beyond the structure of finite reason. Therefore, in principle, the possibility of the soul's awareness of the absolute presence or unconditional origin of meaning is not possible without a symbolic and intermediary thing that is a complete manifestation of that origin. Tillich refers to the symbolic phenomenon of revelatory experience as a miracle. A miracle is in fact a symbolic object, event, or personality through which the giver and origin of meaning makes his life and power present to individuals. In fact, in the Christian religion, Jesus Christ was the first miracle in the sense of such a revelatory event. Jesus was initially a miracle or symbol and intermediary of the origin of meaning for the apostles, because the axis of all the reports that were later presented by the apostles about the life of Jesus indicates his role in the objective development of the presence of the origin of meaning in life as the Logos. But throughout history, all those who responded to him in a state of ecstasy have encountered such an experience of encountering the origin of meaning.

In short, the skeptical problem led us to the root of the conflicts of polar elements such as egocentrism and other-centrism, as well as to the conflict between the structure and the kernel of reason. In fact, the pure categories that are revealed to us in the kernel of reason indicate the presence and experience of the origin of meaning in our being, which is known as revelation; therefore, the answer to the skeptical problem of revelation in the Skepticism is a symbolic act by the source of meaning that indicates the presence and experience of the source of meaning in the recipient and experiencer under the name of miracle. Such a miracle in Christianity is Jesus as the Messiah. In fact, the answer to the problem of skepticism is to accept Jesus as a symbolic manifestation of man's ultimate attachment to the source of meaning.

The Root of Skepticism

1. The Conflict of the Emotional and Formal Elements;
2. The Conflict of Absolutism and Relativism.

After examining the roots of skepticism and deciphering the symbol of Jesus as the Messiah, Tillich tries to show that such a symbol is the cause of humanity's liberation from the campaign of skepticism. In his belief, the unity of revelation or miracle in the human-like Jesus is the cause of resolving the conflict of the emotional and formal elements, and the unity of the objective and absolute event is the cause of overcoming the tension of relativism and absolutism. The important point in Tillich's explanation is that Jesus in this explanation is only the means of the presence of the head and should not be confused with the owner of the head.

The Symbol of God as the Creator

In explaining the question of what factor is outside of us that is constantly capable of resisting destructive forces and gives man security against the threat of death, ignorance, and sin, Tillich enters into theological discussions in its specific sense, i.e. discussions related to theology. But we must pay attention to the path that Tillich took. In a roundabout way, he found himself faced with fundamental questions, and through an ontological analysis he arrived at the essential nature of man with the description of creaturehood and finitude, and from there he concluded that there is a God for such a creation and that such a God is beyond any non-infinite boundary and limitation. Tillich's theology has two axes. He first begins with positive theology and ends with negative theology. Using the concept of ultimate attachment, Tillich actually seeks to explain love. Why should God always protect me from threats? The answer lies in a kind of mutual attachment. Such an attachment is unique and ultimate, that is, it appropriates all of human existence and is beyond any other kind of attachment.

Positive Theology

In Tillich's thought, God is the experience of the presence of the power of existence and its creator. The description of creation in this interpretation does not only refer to the origin of things, but also implies a kind of active presence in the life and survival of existence. God is alive and has life, and the life of existence depends on its will belonging to Him. On the other hand, the concept of "God is the Creator" also means being a protector; that is, He keeps man safe from any kind of threat. He is simply existing, unconditional, and present in everything and owns it. He is the origin of our existence and is in the midst of our being threatened by nothingness; that is, beyond nothingness, threat, and disorder, He creates again and has His creation under His care and protection.

Negative Theology

Tillich mentions some cases regarding the negative attributes of the final end of attachment that also indicate the general and negative characteristics of God. He believes, first, that the description of such presence and power is completely indescribable and secret because of its holiness. In addition, such a power does not exist within this structure, because in this case the name Creator would have no meaning for Him. On the other hand, God is not another general name for the structure of existence, meaning that it is not possible to say that God is the same existence with another name, such as, for example, the Almighty or the Creator of existence! At the same time, Tillich also denies "omni-godliness", as in some mystical schools, existence is referred to as the magazine and manifestation of God. God is not "existent" even if we assume that being is transcendent, because every being is necessarily finite; therefore, talking about the existence of God is unacceptable.

With the emergence of new sciences and the abolition of Ptolemaic cosmology, heavy blows have been dealt to the body of religious beliefs. First, Galileo declared heliocentrism and de-centeredness of the Earth in modern cosmology, then Descartes eliminated Aristotelian final cause and replaced it with active cause, as well as Kant's Copernican revolution, Darwin's theory of evolution, the emergence of new developments in physics from Newton's certainty to Einstein's relativity and Heisenberg's uncertainty principle, metaphysical and philosophical attitudes were quickly destroyed, and new structures and schools emerged that emphasized humanism and anthropocentrism, and ultimately, secularism. Although these changes were pleasant for man, they resulted in nothing but homelessness, wandering, and emptiness for him; because from then on, man lost his divine foundation and support and was forced to face fate and destiny alone; Therefore, the systematic rules of nature are no longer under the command of a supernatural agent and have given way to chance and chance, and blind and deaf elements devise them. The end product of this homelessness is the self-reliance of man and his loneliness, who must seek basic answers to the fundamental issues and questions of life, including the question of its value, meaning and purpose. Much research has recently been conducted on the important issue of the meaning of life. These studies show that this issue encompasses various aspects; in a way that it has been addressed both in the philosophy of religion, which deals mainly with the purposefulness of life, and in the discussions of ethics, which emphasizes the value of life, and in the field of psychology, which measures the degree of use, function and benefit of life. The aspect of the meaning of life that has been mentioned a lot is its purposefulness. In this research and in the process of comparing the fabrication or discovery of meaning, we are mostly faced with the concept of purpose in the discussion of meaning. Sometimes the purpose is attributed to a being that has knowledge and will and sometimes to a being that does not have knowledge and will... . A being that has knowledge and will, in each of its conscious actions, intends to achieve something that we call the purpose. If the purpose is hidden within the being and is located in the being that has the will, it is a self-founded purpose; but if it exists outside of it and is related to another being that is the creator of that primary being, that purpose is considered external and non-self-founded. By comparing the world and man, we can conclude that life does not have a self-founded purpose in its essence; because the purpose must be sought in a factor outside of the one that has knowledge and will; but this truth does not apply to man. Because man has both knowledge and will; therefore, he has a self-based purpose. The answer to the questions in this regard depends on the perspective of the person answering; in such a way that a secular person does not believe in an eternal creator and answers with a material perspective. Also, a theologian will answer in a different way and by considering the assumption that life has a constructive nature. The only difference between a divine person and a material person is that the ultimate whole for a material person is

nature; but a divine person considers nature to be a part of a larger whole called metaphysics or the world of abstracts, which he dominates. Considering these backgrounds, the question that arises is whether the meaning of life is discoverable or falsifiable. The answer to this question, if it involves discovering meaning, whether from the perspective of purpose or from the perspective of value, implies that life inherently contains meaning; That is, there is a meaning hidden in life that we just have to take the trouble to discover; but according to some, this is impossible; because man gives meaning to life with his actions; actions such as: creating a lasting work, experiencing a series of special conditions or fighting the difficulties of life and accepting its unpleasant suffering and pain. As we will see in Kierkegaard's philosophy, he has the motivation to defend pure Christianity and believes that in order to achieve a meaningful life, we must strive, with effort and asceticism, like Christ, to appear before God as a single person and carry out his commandments in the desired way. Therefore, meaning for this philosopher and his contemporaries is something worth searching for and discovering, and in other words, objective; but on the contrary, there are people who consider contemporary man abandoned and thrown into life, whose life is ruled by absolute determinism. The main meaningful indicator for these people is human freedom and will, which is achievable by relying on consciousness. This group of thinkers considers the origin and creator of meaning to be man, who relies only on the subjective world to achieve a meaningful life. Therefore, they consider meaning to be subjective and falsifiable. Sartre, the atheistic French existentialist philosopher, is one of these thinkers. Sartre is known as Kierkegaard's equal; however, he has fundamental differences with him in most philosophical and metaphysical fields, especially in the discussion of discovering or falsifying meaning, and it would be instructive and desirable to delve into their thoughts. Before entering into the discussion and comparison of these two thinkers, we first need to separate the boundaries of theistic and non-theistic approaches to the discussion of meaning.

2- Religious and Non-Religious Meaning of Life

2-1- Supernaturalism

Approaches to the issue of forging or discovering the meaning of life in the first division include two groups: on the one hand, naturalists, some of whom are individualists and others are objectivists, and on the other hand, supernaturalists, some of whom are theists and others are animists. Supernaturalism is a theory that says: a person's life is meaningful only if he or she has a special connection and relationship with a purely spiritual realm. If there is neither God nor spirit, or if there is, a person is not able to communicate with them, then the person's life is meaningless (Meaning of Life, 2010: 17). It follows that in these words, the meaning of life is clearly dependent and related to a spiritual factor; but

there are differences among supernaturalists. Some of them consider this spiritual factor to be God, and others consider it to be the soul. For theists, the presence of God is a necessary condition for meaning; but it is not a sufficient condition; because life does not find meaning only with the presence and existence of God; rather, other factors, such as human effort and effort, are necessary to discover the presence of this transcendental element and fulfill His goals. Therefore, human effort and effort is another criterion for discovering meaning in the presence of God. Although some have objected that if there is a God who is both omnipotent and omniscient, then man will no longer be free to choose and achieve life - in which case man is not free and the necessity of life will remove meaning from it - nevertheless, theists have stated many reasons for the compatibility of the presence of God and human freedom, which are beyond the scope of this study. Spiritualists also have some ideas about meaning, some of which are worth repeating: a soul-centered theory says that individuals are dependent on the soul being in a particular state. The soul, in the sense of a spiritual, immortal essence that can be embodied in time or exist without a body in a timeless world (The Meaning of Life, 2010: 26). However, the most influential spiritualist theory turns to ethical debates, in which the question is raised whether life is worth living or not. In other words, is life worth so much that we would do anything to preserve it and strive endlessly. Some have said in response to this question that life would be valuable if the human soul were immortal and would never end. In other words, our lives would only be valuable if we had hope for a world beyond this finite, material world. Despite the general responses and objections to this issue, ultimately, human survival in a world beyond this material world leads to finding meaning for life. Therefore, supernaturalists, whether soul-centered or theistic, agree on one issue; namely, the attempt to discover meaning with a true belief in an infinite and enduring world.

2-2- Naturalism

This group of people believe that life can be meaningful even without God or a soul and believe that special types of life in a purely material world can be enough to be meaningful. From a non-religious perspective, there is no superhuman state that seems interesting to us and there is no single true goal for human life; therefore, no recourse to God, Brahma, or Nirvana is conceivable in this perspective (Poya, 2007: 6). For this reason, those who believe in the natural element of meaning rely on the components of this world, and for this reason, emphasizing human power and abilities is more important than relying on the power of a divine being. There are different schools of thought among these people. A group of them are individualists and a group is objectivist. The theory of individualism says: what gives meaning to life depends on the individual (which does not have to be a spiritual essence). Individualists are more of a subordinate principle, according to which

the issue of the meaning of life belongs to human desire and desire. Another group considers the meaning-giving factor to be human will and the discovery of individual abilities, and some consider the right to choose and select as the meaning-giving factor; But what is important is the coordination of all these people in a single response that does not consider the existence of any transcendental factor to be necessary and necessary in the meaning of life. As we will see, Sartre adheres to this way of thinking, which is in contrast to the theistic thought of Kierkegaard. Another aspect of naturalism is objectivism. According to those who believe in it, a meaningful life is the association of certain mental faculties with values independent of the mind, which is best expressed by Ms. Susan Wolf: A meaningful life must meet two interrelated criteria: first, it must be actively involved in something and second, this involvement must be related to valuable projects. Life will be meaningless if it is not actively involved in something (The Meaning of Life, 2010, 40). As mentioned earlier, the individual effort of man, whether in nature or in thought and interiority, is a factor in the forgery of the meaning of life for objectivist and individualist naturalists. Therefore, anthropocentrism is one of the characteristics of naturalists, who are at the opposite end of the spectrum from supernaturalists. A detailed discussion of the aforementioned statements is found in the ontology of each of these philosophers, where they clearly define the place of human existence.

3- Kierkegaard's Theistic Ontology

As we know, in Kierkegaard's ontology, three types of existence are always analyzable, which he refers to as stages or spheres of existence. In Kierkegaard's philosophy, these spheres are not inseparable packages that are aimed at transcendence in the form of a staircase; rather, they are stages of human life and existence that can be unrelated to each other. Life is in the stage of self-gratification, in the stage of morality for others, and in the stage of faith for God.

3-1- For example, Don Juan in the stage of gratification spends his entire life seeking sexual and physical pleasures. He is always busy deceiving the opposite sex because he enjoys this and has made performing such an act the goal and end of life. Therefore, the goal in this sphere, although not compatible with reality, is something that satisfies Don Juan in the field of thought and leads him to his goals. "Listen to the beginning of his life. The only ray of light in his life is the blind spot of the dark cloud that has covered his life. He is outside the circle of truth. No light shines on his life. He is a prisoner of the blind desires of life and is caught like a bait in the trap of his boring life. Listen to how he is caught in fleeting pleasures. In the cover of dark deeds. (p.103) (1987). (Kierkegaard, In Kierkegaard's opinion, Don Juan's concept of life does not convey anything other than darkness and cloudiness to the audience; therefore, the purpose of his life, which is a very

small and insignificant thing, has trapped him in this darkness. Individuals' lives in this sphere are for themselves.

3-2- In the next step, Kierkegaard steps into the ethical stage and the realm of human values, in which individuals' lives are for others. As mentioned, Kierkegaard suspended the ethical matter because he pursued a very great goal in life. The tragic hero, or the moral man who lives in the realm of moral orders, aims to transcend the will of the individual in order to reach the universal. He endures the pain of destruction and death because his goal is to reach the universal. He also wants to be a general model of ethical life, like Socrates who drank the cup of hemlock to teach a historical lesson with his death. Humans learn; a lesson that shows the inferiority of human life in front of society. The hero of the moral arena seeks to establish justice. He sacrifices himself to be a lesson for history. He wants to be a monument in different periods of history; because he loves and cherishes the universal. The hero of tragedy sacrifices himself to become universal. His goal in life is to restore justice and law, and with his death, he revives the law (Lippitt, 2003, p.152). Therefore, the foundation of the goal of life in the moral sphere, like the sphere of praise, is not Kierkegaard's divine signs; because, unlike Socrates, who was the hero and model of the moral sphere, he does not want to be a sign on the crossroads of history that will remember him well. For Kierkegaard, such a goal is contemptible.

3-3- The third sphere of existence in Kierkegaard's theistic ontology is the stage and sphere of faith. All The goal and purpose of Kierkegaard's philosophy is to prove the correctness and fundamentality of this sphere. What has caused Kierkegaard to ignore the other two spheres and spheres and to consider them incapable of achieving truth is the passion, love, and sincerity of the individuals within those spheres. Therefore, in Kierkegaard's opinion, it is necessary for man to freely and willingly step towards the true beloved in the sphere of faith. Kierkegaard considered his era to be an era of lack of pleasure, because in it, humans either seek the fleeting pleasures of life (like all ordinary and common people who avoided them) or they try to sacrifice themselves to the general laws of morality (which annihilate and destroy passion in humans). Kierkegaard was looking for a truth that would awaken his inner "I" in his being and make it stable. If a person cannot reach the highest level of passion in the short period of life, he will not be able to find true individuality, and if he does, If one does not achieve individuality, one will never appear before God. Passion is a good criterion for human excellence.

Passion is not something that is equally within the power of all of us; rather, it is the main requirement of life that is worth living... In the end, not only is greatness not possible without passion, but without it, even individuality is at risk (Merino, 2001, p.86). For this reason, the sphere of faith is the place of special ones and not every individual can step into it. Kierkegaard's best example for this stage of existence is Prophet Abraham, the

Prophet of God. Kierkegaard tried to put the practical and theoretical aspects of Prophet Abraham at the forefront in practical life. His passion in the path of carrying out God's command is the most ideal action for a human being, according to Kierkegaard. Man is free and has the right to choose and must choose a path that will lead him to discover the meaning of life. A meaning that depends on faith in God. Freedom in Philosophy Kierkegaard is synonymous with the overall choice of a stage and the Leap from one stage to another. Therefore, with a leap of faith, man finds his inner "I" and reaches his authentic self. In order to achieve our "I" - which is the most important thing in life - we must choose one of the spheres of life and devote ourselves to it with all our heart, even though we know that there is no guarantee and that others may not appreciate or even understand our choice; but in the end, we must be responsible only to ourselves and if we make our decision and do not act on what is important to us, the despair that comes to us is much worse than this terrible acceptance of the decision and choice that we make. (Weston, 1994, p.31). Finally, in Kierkegaard's ontology Indeed, only three general choices are reserved for man: first, life for himself or the sphere of esteem and aesthetics; second, life for others, which occurs in the sphere of morality; and finally, life for God, which belongs to the sphere of religion and faith. But in any case, this choice must be made; because if we do not do this, according to Kierkegaard, we will be aimless humans, whose life will have no meaning for us and as a result we will not be able to reach our true self.

4- Sartre's Emmanic Ontology

Ontology in Sartre's philosophy is dependent on the knowledge of human existence. For this reason, in a book titled Existentialism is a Type of Emmanicism, Sartre recognizes existentialist philosophy as a type of anthropocentrism. Sartre emphasizes two types of existence: first, existence-for-itself, which is conscious, dynamic, creative, temporal, and spatial, and is always exploring in search of knowledge of the world around it. Second, existence-in-itself, which is simple, unconscious, atemporal, and object-like, occupying only space and not aware of any aspect of its existence. Sartre's ontology has three aspects:

4-1- The existence-for-itself is absolutely free and has the right to continuous choice. Therefore, it must use and benefit from this power to direct itself forward, and whatever hinders it in this path and deprives it of freedom, distances it from its human existence and robs its existence of meaning (Sartre, 1966, p.593).

According to Sartre, man is free and has the right to choose. If we look realistically, we will see that Sartre is concerned with freedom and that there is no issue more important to him than that. Since existence-for-itself is a conscious existence and knows that its life is short and limited and that it has many possibilities ahead; therefore, it must make a choice and choose whatever is important and beneficial to it. Therefore, in Sartre's opinion, man

is responsible for all his choices and is committed to them. In Sartre's thought, the central argument of existentialism is that man is the only being whose "existence precedes his essence"; that is, he exists first and then his essence and what is formed. This is why he says: Man is his own creation and determines his own destiny. The essence of man is the result of his various choices that arise from freedom, and the issue of freedom is the most fundamental concept that lies before existence-for-itself. We must understand that being-for-itself is free; but this does not mean that (being free) is the whole point, but if it is to be free in the fundamental sense, freedom will be the mastery of being and existence... In fact, we are free to choose, not to choose to be free. In fact, we are free when we have made a choice... and this happening is freedom (Sartre, 1966, P.593).

4-2- Being-in-itself belongs to the world of objects; that is, beings that do not have rational judgment. A tree, an animal, and a stone are beings that do not have the power of consciousness and are not aware of the time and space around them. Therefore, Sartre considers them to be beings that are simply confined within the framework of the occupied physical space. They are neither creative nor can they plan for their future. Projection, which is one of the fundamental categories of Sartre's philosophy, does not exist in these beings, and they are not like humans whose existence precedes their essence; rather, they first have a predetermined plan and essence and then come into existence. In Sartre's opinion, if a human being becomes alienated and helpless, he will fall from the human plane into the world of objects. Man is condemned to freedom; for this reason, he is anxious and worried about his immense freedom and tries to deny it in order to shirk the burden of responsibility. On the other hand, the second point is that for Sartre, contingency is the foundation of freedom. We have a series of situations and conditions that have been imposed on us in advance and without the right to choose. For example: skin color, height, nationality, and other characteristics that are intended for us innately. Therefore, by understanding these situations, as well as by understanding the right to choose and be free, and by correctly understanding the world around us, we can move forward in a desirable way or, in Sartre's words, make a project for ourselves; but sometimes this project and plan faces problems; because man, due to the difficulty of the circumstances and the difficulty of the path and the weight of the burden of responsibility and obligation, wants to escape from himself and get caught in the trap of bad faith. In this case, he forgets being-for-itself and becomes an object. The anxiety and terror of absolute freedom traps him within himself; because, according to Sartre, man is completely free. Human freedom manifests itself only through projection. Therefore, man, by continuous projections towards a certain goal and purpose, gives objectivity to his freedom and completes a part of his human world. Freedom is built with these goals. The path of man and his fundamental path are determined by having supreme goals and represent human freedom (Sartre, 1966, p.596). According to Sartre, man creates the real world and the world of his

values. Man is responsible for all his actions; therefore, he is committed to all of them and it is because of this absolute commitment that anxiety overcomes him.

4-3- Existence – for – the other. In Sartre's ontology, man has a universal and general aspect that is influenced by humans and consciousnesses outside of himself. The conflict and struggle between these consciousnesses is interesting and controversial. Others are trying to seize and hold my consciousness. For this reason, my will and consciousness are tools for dominating others, as well as for others to dominate me. Therefore, Sartre, following Hobbes, who he said: "Man is a wolf to man," and in *The Wall* he states: "Hell is others." According to Sartre, humans try to enslave their fellow humans and thwart their quest to project and construct the meaning of life. Therefore, we must overcome them through our consciousness and put an obstacle in the way of their sinister goals. God is the greatest "other" who stands in the way of my projecting and seizes my freedom, which is the only instrument of my consciousness; therefore, on the one hand, there is an endless conflict and struggle between me and my fellow humans, and on the other hand, between me and God. Thus, in Sartre's philosophy, man, because he is left to himself and has the right to absolute choice and is also an existence-for-himself, wants to become an absolute concept; that is, he himself constructs his own essence and stands on his own feet. In other words, in Sartre's philosophy, man desires to become God; because God is a contradictory concept whose possibility of existence seems unlikely, for this reason, man takes his place. God, as he came, is an absolute "other" who crucifies human consciousness and the absolute and prominent presence of God does not fit into the sphere of human authority and also causes the disappearance of human freedom and agency. From this point of view, it can be said that Sartre's ontology, unlike Kierkegaard's theistic ontology, is based on man and is amnestic.

5- Forgery or discovery of the meaning of life? In Kierkegaard's thought

As mentioned earlier, the discussion of the meaning of life is sometimes based on a goal and end and sometimes it is based on the benefit of life. The meaning of life, with the perspective of purpose, relies on two types of beings: one being with will and agency and the other being without will and agency. The purpose for beings with will is self-founded; that is, it is a goal whose foundation exists in the being with knowledge and agency itself. Sometimes this goal is attributed to a being that does not have knowledge and will, and we should ask about the creative motivation of this being for creating it, not about the way and manner of existence of that being. In the way that what is the creative purpose of this being for creating it? These types of goals are external goals. People who consider man as

a self-made being, attribute a self-founded goal to man, and people who consider man without choice and freedom, who was created by an external creator, seek an external goal. Religious people are more likely to seek this ultimate goal and try to find it, rather than create it. Søren Kierkegaard is also among these people. He is in search of truth. Kierkegaard has repeatedly mentioned in his works that he is looking for a truth that is true for him; A truth to live and die for: What I really need is to know what I should do, not what I should know, but because before we can do anything, we must know something. The point is to understand my destiny and see what God actually wants me to do. The most important thing is to find the truth; the truth that is the truth for me. I must search for a meaning and an idea for which I want to live and die (Kierkegaard, 1987, p.8). Kierkegaard's thought structure is based on an ultimate thing; something that is the origin and purpose of the universe. In this statement of Kierkegaard, we can clearly understand the essence of the meaning of life. He clearly says, I am looking for a truth for which I can live and sacrifice my life for it. This is certainly a sign of Kierkegaard's adaptation of the real life of Christ, who sacrificed himself before God the Father and for the sake of mankind. Therefore, Kierkegaard wants to simulate the same action in his private life. The prerequisite for achieving such a thing is to come out of oneself and seek that fundamental truth. Discovering this truth and sacrificing oneself in its heavenly court gives eternal meaning to human life. From this point of view, we can obtain several fundamental principles in Kierkegaard's thought regarding subjective truth.

5-1- First, subjectivity and the inner are truth; that is, truth is something that man finds from within. In other words, this truth is important only for man and the human mind, and it is a subjective matter that we must understand by delving deeply into our own being.

5-2- Second, subjective truth means something practical; as Kierkegaard says: having subjectivity (subjectivity) is truth. Subjectivity is reality. If being subjective is truth, then the definition of truth must also include an interpretation of its opposite, objectivity, a sign of a fork in the road (Kierkegaard, 1987, p. 191). In other words, as Kierkegaard clearly stated, subjective truth is equal to and synonymous with pragmatism. So the second thing that comes from Kierkegaard's statement is that man should be more pragmatic in life and not just a person of pure opinion and idea.

5-3- The third issue is the importance of this subjective matter, in such a way that the structure and foundation of human life until death is based on this truth.

5-4- The fourth issue is that that subjective matter is within the scope of God's will and, as he says, it is a divine command and order; Therefore, the subjectivity that organizes the truth of Kierkegaard's life is something that God has ordained for him.

5-5- The fifth issue in this discourse is that subjective truth is opposed to an objective and objective matter. In other words, this subjective truth is a doubt about an objective and objective matter that depicts man's anxiety about his presence in the world: The definition of truth is: truth is an objective and continuous doubt in the paths that lead to the acquisition of passionate existence, and this is the highest truth that a living person can achieve (Kierkegaard, 1987, P.192). Kierkegaard's Insistence on the Problem of Faith The pure is a paradoxical and complex issue, because it is both objective and subjective. In other words, it centers on subjectivity and objectivity is fundamental to him. In Kierkegaard's thought, being objective does not mean being objectified or concrete. For example, when he says that God is objective, he does not mean that God is an object among objects and beings that can be mentioned, but rather he considers this to mean the individual truth of God, because in Kierkegaard's view, God has an individual existence. Kierkegaard considered theorizing religion, especially the religion of Christ, to be very dangerous. Kierkegaard's ontology was based on his Christianity, because in his view, the true and unique existence belongs to God and the existence of humans must be such that they provide themselves with the conditions for presence in the divine realm, otherwise they will not be true beings. Objectivity is a belief that an unchanging human being understands another person, and that other person is Jesus Christ. We become Christians through Jesus Christ, we become members of Him, and we receive the Holy Spirit. Being existential and having a true existence is the event that makes me a human being, and all this is due to the elements of Jesus Christ (Cochrane, 1956, p. 31). Here we can clearly see what Kierkegaard means by the objectivity of God. God is a truth outside of us that lies objectively and objectively in the facts of the world. Therefore, we must strive to discover this truth in the desired way. He considers Christ to be the manifestation of this world of God and the sign of His personification; therefore, he points out that in order to provide a meaningful life for the attainment of happiness, it is necessary to surrender to the real life of Christ and His suffering. Here, we can clearly see the second principle about subjective truth or pragmatism. Discovering the meaning of life depends on our practical efforts to pursue and search for it. On the other hand, it has been repeatedly pointed out that philosophy, for Kierkegaard, is a tool for changing man, and he is trying to say that man is a self-made thing that determines his destiny by choice; that is, to the extent that man has free will and can influence the world around him to the extent possible, he is able to find a way to give meaning to his life: it is not about being everything we are, but it is about becoming everything we become (Jean Wall, 1978: 24). Therefore, on the one hand, standing before God as an individual is important for him, and on the other hand, choosing a right way in life is of particular importance. According to Kierkegaard, the masses of people, or herds (as Nietzsche calls them), are afraid of this reality and are trying to escape from it. All the cleverness of mankind is focused on one thing: to be able

to live without responsibility. The importance of the clergy for society should be that they do everything they can to make everyone know that they are forever responsible for their actions, even in the simplest things; because this is what true Christianity is (Westphal, 1990, p. 464). If we want to live an ideal life in practice, we must feel responsible for all our choices and not shirk the burden of responsibility and the problems of life. This reality of Kierkegaard can be compared to the people who are caught in self-deception, bad faith, and everyday life in Sartre's philosophy. In Sartre's thought, this group of people is also blamed; Because they fall into self-deception to escape freedom. The bourgeois love of God begins when the vegetative life reaches its peak. When everyone puts their hands on their stomachs, their heads rest on the sofa cushions, and their eyes are fixed in absolute sleep on the ceiling of the room (Kierkegaard, 1972, p.9). The truth is with God and that is all, and we must strive to reach the threshold of this supreme truth based on the practical life we have chosen for ourselves and spend it in discovering the truth; therefore, it can be said that one aspect of Kierkegaard's reference to the objectivity of the meaning of life lies in the fact that, in his opinion, individuality, identification, and uniqueness are attributes of God, and a human being must strive in life like Christ and choose a path in his choices that will make him appear as an individual before God as much as possible. We should not be caught up in self-centeredness; rather, we should discover our inner self and sacrifice it for the sake of knowing God; as Kierkegaard has repeatedly mentioned in his works: "God is hidden from the eyes of self-centered people." Self-centeredness appears when a person ignores God and denies His existence or makes unreasonable demands on God. If a person considers himself to be the creator and owner of himself, he will be caught up in self-centeredness. Therefore, self-centeredness causes a fundamental misunderstanding of knowing God (Podmore, 2011, p.122). According to the third principle, subjective truth constitutes the foundation of human life, and by discovering and seeking help from it, a person should advance his life as much as possible towards divine spirituality and prepare the ground for the transition from the stage of mortal life; because it is only through spiritual passage and journey that one can experience that supreme truth. According to Kierkegaard's existential philosophy, the nature of human beings is their own creation. Human beings are what they want and make themselves. This point has also become the axis of gravity of Sartre's atheistic philosophy. If the masses of people, according to Kierkegaard, are caught in the evasion of responsibility, it is because they have taken refuge in society out of fear and anxiety of responsibility in order to mitigate their presence. We are responsible for what we become and, as we have seen, Kierkegaard also emphasizes that there are no objective criteria for decision-making. Each individual must find his own way. He makes choices in his life, and it is along this path that he is shaped and becomes the person he is (Guignon, 2004, p. 29).

Considering the above-mentioned material, we can reach two important conclusions about the fabrication or discovery of meaning from Kierkegaard's perspective: a) To the extent that we are the builders of our own nature and identity and create our own values, the meaning of our life is a fake and fabricated thing, and others do not play a decisive role in it, and it is with loneliness and individuality that humans are born. b) On the other hand, by finding individuality and choosing the true path of life, which according to Kierkegaard occurs in the realm of faith, we can no longer have control over our actions, and orders and instructions come to us from another world. This is where the machine of the meaning of life enters a different path and its control is no longer in the hands of man. We must enter the arena of searching for meaning through intuition and revelation, and ultimately we find it on the safe shore of belief in God. This is the objective and external aspect of the meaning of life from Kierkegaard's perspective. Talking about discovering or forging meaning in Kierkegaard's thought seems somewhat paradoxical and ambiguous; but in general, it can be said that in his philosophy, we create the methods and values of life ourselves, and in other words, we are the forgers of values and the acquisition of the meaning of life. Although the fear of freedom sometimes keeps us away from choosing the right path, we must have enough strength to accept the dangerous and difficult choice of the meaning of life; but since for Kierkegaard, subjectivity is truth and man can see himself as an absolute individuality in front of Him by discovering the ultimate divine truth, it is understood that the general meaning of life, in his opinion, is something to be discovered that is very difficult to achieve. The prerequisite for such a journey is to go beyond human selfishness and join the oneness of God. Man finds himself unique and alone in front of God, and the path to divine truth lies in this individuality and solitude, and the original and ultimate meaning of human life depends on discovering the relationship with God, and the meaning of life is the discovery of God in life; consequently, it can be said that Kierkegaard's meaning of life has an objective aspect and must be discovered.

6- Forging or discovering the meaning of life? In Sartre's thought

Those thinkers who link meaning to a hidden purpose in the realm of human existence consider the entirety of human life to be absurd and meaningless, and they believe that no external agent or factor has formulated it. For this reason, they consider man responsible for giving meaning to his life and see it as containing a self-founded purpose whose creator and processor is man himself. For Sartre, life itself has no purpose, value, and in general, no meaning, and man gives it meaning according to his capacity and ability. From this perspective, meaning is a relative matter that cannot be definitively or absolutely defined, and the result of this approach is pluralism and indeterminacy. The answer to the question of whether the meaning of life, according to Sartre, is something to be discovered or

fabricated and made, is very simple to obtain by referring to the concept of eventfulness. With regard to this important concept, six points and matters regarding the falsity or discovery of the meaning of life from Sartre's perspective can be mentioned:

6-1- The first point is that for Sartre, first and foremost, life is absurd and nothing but fruitless wandering, and man can only make choices and defend his freedom. Man is a being who has the characteristics of an event and has no way of escaping from it, and he must elevate his eventfulness to the highest level. In other words, it creates its own essence, and this creation of what and essence is the secret of the meaning of human life. Humans themselves create their own essential structure and give themselves an identity by projecting. Sartre's rational structure, which is a follower of Descartes and is considered a Cartesian, measures everything based on rational calculations and through rational measurement, in contrast to Kierkegaard's anti-rational nature. This is why the meaning of life can only be achieved through rational calculations and not through heartfelt and faith-based acceptance: Human reality is a deficiency and deficiency, and reason eliminates this deficiency during life in the world. Just as Descartes and I think, we ourselves try to respond to it. Man must inevitably take steps towards eliminating this deficiency; but in any case, only the face and appearance of human existence in the world is justified by this deficiency. Human deficiency cannot be eliminated by relying on the concept of God. (Sartre, 1996, p.109)

6-2- In the next stage, it is clear that Sartre means by the deficiency and deficiency in life that he has repeatedly mentioned in the book *Being and Nothingness*, the absence and nothingness of man. Nothingness is one of the consequences of consciousness. For example, a cat is not aware of its own nothingness and nothingness; because it does not have a faculty called consciousness and due to lack of consciousness, it is also deprived of temporality; for this reason, it is not aware of the place it occupies in the world; but man is aware of this fact and, in addition, he knows that a day will come when he is gone and does not have this current place. Therefore, he sees his life as limited to time limits and tries to make the most of this opportunity. According to Sartre, man is the only being who introduces nothingness and absence into existence. Man is only an entity that has entered the realm of life and has the duty to build himself, and this building of himself is the greatest project that he always projects to realize. Sartre has considered human existence to be prior to essence in accordance with the fundamental principle of existentialism, and on this basis, he has always been considered his own creator.

6-3- Thirdly, although in Sartre's philosophy, projecting is doomed to failure due to existential anxiety and fear, and man is a project that will never be realized in an ideal form; nevertheless, this extreme despair in Sartre does not make him stop searching for meaning in life. In the play *The Flies*, in which he used Greek and Roman mythology,

Sartre has repeatedly depicted the glimmer of hope for the meaning of life. Especially where Electra asks Orestes: “Where are you going?” and Orestes replies: “Towards ourselves, beyond the rivers and mountains where Orestes and Electra await us and we must patiently walk towards them” (Sartre, 2011: 84). 6-4- Fourth, Sartre has repeatedly acknowledged the bitter reality that our birth is meaningless and our death is also meaningless; but he has never considered suicide to be the only philosophical issue, like Albecamo, and this issue can be easily observed in his real life. Sartre was a man of great potential who always wrote and participated in revolutions and social reforms, and never stopped trying. In this same pragmatism of Sartre, we can understand another fundamental point, which is that the fundamental aspect of the meaning of human life and its clue is presence among others and living alongside the values of society. Sartre always fought. He had breathed his last in various revolutions such as the Cuban Revolution, African social movements, the French Revolution, and the Japanese Revolution, and he knew that the power of society is much more effective than the power of the individual. Although he relied specifically on the psychological structure and individual consciousness, he considered it to be in the service of society. Unlike Kierkegaard, who thought individually and did not pay attention to collective values. For Sartre, commitment and responsibility are words that make the human world meaningful. Freedom is the result of individual relationships between humans, which find meaning with collective values. Therefore, the individual considered by Sartre flourishes in society. The aspect of human existence – for – otherness draws him to society. Values gain meaning in relation to goals, and goals come into being through choice. My individual existence is the result of free choice, and I am the creator of my own world; but in this individual world, other consciousnesses and individualities should not be ignored; because my world is located in the neighborhood of the world of others, and I am always in action and reaction with them.

6-5- The fifth point is that in Sartre's philosophy, since there is no place for God, Sartre is not a theist and does not see a need for the concept of God. For this reason, like Kierkegaard, he does not seek to discover meaning in the realm of faith in God and, with blasphemous concepts, has assumed that man is responsible for all his actions, that he creates his own life and meaning. In this way, Sartre - the same Sartre who says that man is a useless passion - values the search for meaning and even suggests ways for this search. These ways include: finding a home and companion in the world, action, freedom, rebellion against oppression, service to others, enlightenment, self-realization and commitment, always and most importantly, commitment (Yalom, 2011: 597).

6-6- Living in a community and accepting the values of society creates obligations and commitments. Therefore, the sixth point in proving the false and subjective nature of meaning according to Sartre is the issue of commitment. Having a commitment and

altruism can open a door for man and pull him out of his inner prison. Life is inherently meaningless and searching for meaning in life is useless and absurd. Man is fruitless as an individual, and the fear of freedom further reveals this emptiness and causes existential anxiety and apprehension; but we should not sit idly by and do nothing, but rather we should promote meaning in the layers of life and give it color and color through continuous efforts within society and altruism, promoting morality and freedom, and making people aware of their rights. The challenge of committed literature, which Sartre sought to defend for years, is a convincing proof of this; But Viktor Frankl, one of the founders of semantic therapy, whose constructive theories have greatly influenced the discussions of the meaning of life in the contemporary world and who sometimes criticizes Sartre, believes that meaning should be something to be discovered, because it brings peace:

It is much more comforting to believe that meaning has existed "somewhere" and that we have discovered it. He questions Sartre's position that one of the responsibilities of being free is that one must create meaning for oneself. Frankl emphasizes throughout his writings that "meaning must be found, not given." Frankl's position has a religious foundation and is based on the assumption that there is a God who has destined meaning for each of us... (Yalom, 2011: 640).

However, it should be noted that this is merely Frankl's opinion and belief, and Sartre does not believe in such a thing. In addition, Sartre rejects the theory of psychological determinism. This theory is rooted in the past of man. Unlike Freud, who searched for the truth of man in the past and within the unconscious of man, he searches for the truth in the future and the possibilities ahead and within the consciousness of man, and closes the door to the past. As mentioned earlier, the subjectivity of the meaning of life implies the fact that meaning is something intra-subjective and is created and processed in the human mind. In other words, it is a creation of the human mind, unlike objectivity, which centers on the objective world and according to which the meaning of life arises from the outside world, not the human mind. For this reason, Sartre considers man to be his own creation and denies God, and considers meaning to be something created and processed by human effort, and in his opinion, it is subjective and fake. It is both difficult and simple to talk about the similarities and differences between Kierkegaard and Sartre. Since these two thinkers belong to the same philosophical school called existentialism, they have much in common. However, Kierkegaard's paradoxical philosophy makes it difficult to judge and adjudicate in this field. On the one hand, he is subjective. Witte considers truth to be truth, and on the other hand, he considers true truth to be objective and external, which reaches man from an eternal source; while for Sartre, all truth must be obtained within man and his subjectivity. However, a few important points can be mentioned about them:

6-1- First, both philosophers are pragmatists and implement their subjective and theoretical truth in life and make it practical. Kierkegaard by following the true life of Abraham and Jesus Christ and implementing their goals in his private life, and Sartre by accepting society and committing to it, as well as striving for the liberation of mankind.

6-2- Secondly, both philosophers consider existence to be prior to essence. In Kierkegaard's philosophy, man first exists and then, by seeking true faith in God, he forms his essence, and by finding individuality before God, his human essence is completed and he reaches the ultimate meaning of life. In Sartre, man also exists first and then, by understanding his position and recognizing the power of consciousness, he projects.

6-3- In the discussion of forging or discovering the meaning of life, both philosophers also have an understanding on one issue. Kierkegaard considers truth to be a subjective matter and, relying on it, discovers the objective meaning. Sartre also considers the truth of man to be a subjective and internal matter that remains internal and accompanies man until the end and until death.

6-4- The most fundamental difference between Sartre and Kierkegaard is Kierkegaard's theism and Sartre's atheism. In Kierkegaard's ontology, which consists of three stages: ideal, moral, and faith, the only determining and distinguishing factor is the issue of faith. The last and most important sphere, which is the stage of faith, is the stage where an individual achieves a life full of meaning by having pure faith in God; but in Sartre's ontology, which is divided into two categories: being-for-itself and being-in-itself, the only criterion of difference is the issue of consciousness.

6-5- Another point of difference between these two philosophers is that for Kierkegaard, the discovery of meaning is dependent on finding individuality; because since God is unique and incomparable, man appears before Him as an individual. Therefore, the only true commitment is commitment to God and faith in Him; But in Sartre's philosophy, although man is unique and individual, he still flourishes in society, and if he is committed and committed to society, his life takes on a desirable meaning. Therefore, it can be said that an ideal Sartre always remains in Kierkegaard's moral sphere and does not cross it; but Kierkegaard crosses the boundaries of morality to reach a lofty goal.

6-6- Finally, the meaning of life for Kierkegaard is an objective, external, and discoverable matter; while for Sartre, it is a subjective, internal, and falsifiable issue that man consciously creates.

Systematic Christian Theology According to Paul Tillich (Being and God)

Paul Tillich is often introduced as a moderate theologian who tries to establish a relationship between liberalism and neo-orthodoxy, idealism and realism, and

Protestant and Roman Catholic theology. His religion, inspired by the Romantic movement of the 19th century, gave his theology a completely philosophical theological flavor. In his opinion, the main task of Christian theology is to justify and express the truth of the Christian message and to interpret this truth for new generations. Therefore, he used the message of Christ to answer philosophical questions arising from the realm of culture. (As Tillich's goal has sometimes been stated as mediation between faith and culture.) Solidarity as one of the components of systematic Christian theology is Tillich's method. This methodology is considered one of his most important achievements for modern theology.

Systematic Theology According to Tillich

For Tillich, the systematic form in theology contains significant features, among which the following can be mentioned:

In Tillich's opinion, this form has caused his intellectual coherence, which is one of the most difficult tasks in theology and few people are successful in this regard.

It is a tool for discovering and revealing the relationships between symbols and concepts.

This method is a factor in understanding theology as a coherent whole whose parts and elements are connected to each other under principles and relationships.

Tillich believes that the human condition raises fundamental issues that human culture manifests in different ways in the prominent styles of its artistic works and that religious traditions provide answers to them that are manifested in religious symbols. Hence, Tillich organizes his systematic theology into five parts, in each part, a major religious symbol of the Bible is related as an answer to a major human problem crystallized in the new culture.

*The first part relates the symbol of the Logos to the skeptical problem of the new culture. How can we know with certainty the truth that is important for humanity?

The second part connects the symbol of “God as Creator” to the manifestations of the problem of the finitude of the new culture, how can we resist the destructive forces that threaten our lives with collapse?

The third part connects the symbol of “Jesus as Christ” to the worldly manifestations of the problem of the alienation of the new culture, how can we heal the alienation that we renew in ourselves and around us?

The fourth part connects the symbol of “the divine spirit” to the manifestations of the problem of the ambiguity of the new culture, how can our life be authentic when our morals, actions, and cultural manifestations are completely ambiguous?

The fifth part connects the symbol of “the kingdom of God” to the question of whether history has meaning?

The task of systematic Christian theology

According to Tillich, the task of Christian theology is to fulfill the demands of the church. Proclaiming the truth of Christ's message and interpreting this truth for the new generation are two ways for the church to answer questions that arise from the church's situation and condition, and in other words, "theology is a method of interpreting and explaining the content of the Christian faith." Situation and condition raise different questions about human existence, and Christian theology's answer to those questions is based on the message of Christ. The distinctive feature of Tillich's theology is his existential approach to theology. Examining the human condition is the first step of a theologian who intends to answer human existential questions. According to Tillich, every theology must have two components: a) the object of every theology must be something that is our ultimate attachment and b) such a question of our being and not being. In other words, the object of theology is the explanation of our ultimate attachment that determines our being and not being. The explanation of our ultimate attachment must be derived from the message of Christ, a message that includes the Bible, the history of the church, the history of religion and culture, and all of these are considered sources and references of systematic theology. In the meantime, religious experience is a medium for us to access the resources. With the resources and experiences, the search for the norm of Christian systematic theology is necessary to guide theologians. According to Tillich, this middle ground is the new being in Jesus as Christ. Hence, the “new being in Jesus as Christ” is not only the subject of theology, but also our ultimate concern that determines our being and not-being. Therefore, the method considered by Tillich, which is the “method of correlation,” is a way to connect questions with answers, situations with messages, human existence and divine revelation. This method summarizes Tillich’s theological system. In this system, philosophical questions arise from the analysis and examination of human existence, and theological answers are based on sources and references. The middle and middle ground of systematic theology must be divided and mentioned. For Tillich, such a division contains the structure of systematic theology.

The Role of Reason in Christian Theology

Although reason is not one of the sources of theology, it has an important role in theology. Tillich distinguishes two categories of reason: a) Existential reason and b) Technical reason. Existential reason is the structure of the mind that enables the mind to understand and imagine reality. Technical reason is the powers of reasoning. For Tillich, the fundamental category of reason is existential reason. Technical reason is only a tool for

existential reason to obtain and receive revelation. Existential reason, from which the subjective and objective reasons originate, has the ability to be connected to the logos. The subjective reason can be defined as the rational structure of the mind, and this reason is capable of forming reality. Objective reason is the rational structure of reality, and since logos means understanding and forming reality, it is therefore existential reason. Tillich uses the word depth of reason to relate its transcendental power in the sense of being-itself. In any case, reason is a subject to our actual existence, so reason experiences the limitations, contradictions, and ambiguities of our existence. Hence, the search for revelation seems inevitable because it removes the finitude and limitation of our reason.

The Role of Revelation in Christian Theology

Revelation reveals our ultimate attachment. According to Tillich, there are two categories in revelation: a) primary revelation, b) dependent revelation. Primary revelation is the given and given aspect, the revelation that has not been given to us before, and dependent revelation is its received aspect, by which the individual and the group are changed. "Jesus is the Christ" for two reasons, first, that he can become the Christ, and second, that he is the one who has been received as the Christ. Therefore, the revelation of Jesus as the Christ, from whom the message of Christianity originates, is the final and actual revelation, and that in turn removes the finitude of our existential reason. Revelation reveals our ultimate attachment. For Tillich, the origin of revelation is the origin which is revealed in being and, in Christian terms, is the origin of God's being. Revelation is the medium of knowledge. His knowledge is the knowledge of God, something that must be expressed and described symbolically.

The role of the symbol in Christian theology

The "word of God" is a symbol for revealing God and himself. In Jesus as the Messiah, the symbol refers to something beyond itself. The symbol has a power that it represents. The symbol is the truth and the expression of revelation. Religious symbols can be true symbols. Therefore, if symbols have divine power, they represent that power. Religious symbols are twofold. They open themselves to the infinite, as well as to the finite. They set the infinite in motion against the finite and the finite in motion against the infinite. They are the revealers of divine life to man and human life to God. Religious symbols communicate ultimate truth through objects, persons, and events.

Being and God in Christian Theology

The question of God is the fundamental question of theology. Undoubtedly, God is the answer to the question of theology. But according to Tillich, the answer to this question

lies in the analysis of being. The study and analysis of being does not mean the analysis and study of the being of a certain thing or a category of beings. This study seeks the meaning of being. The question of being arises with the revelation of "non-being", something that threatens being and creates the meaning of finitude and limitation. In other words, finitude connects being with non-being. Therefore, the fundamental question is the question of these two categories. Since at a certain level finitude and limitation are experienced by humans, human finitude is incomprehensible without the concept of non-being, and our imagination can deal with infinity despite our finitude, so we have the ability to be aware of it, and this awareness presupposes the question of God. Also, this awareness of non-infinity has its source in our awareness of finitude. Since the concept of finitude is central to Tillich's transition to the discussion of God, this concept plays an important role in his theology. In his view, because we are aware of the concept of infinity, we are able to ask about God. "The question of God is possible because the awareness of God is involved in the question of God, and this awareness precedes that question." God must be asked because the threat of non-being, which man experiences as apprehension and anxiety, moves him to the question of being that overcomes non-being and the courage and bravery that overcomes anxiety. Therefore, the search for God is inevitable for man. God is the answer to the question that man's awareness of finitude contains. God is our ultimate attachment, whatever we recognize as our ultimate attachment, we call God. God is being-itself, not a being among other beings. To describe the relationship between being-itself and finite beings, Tillich uses the word ground. God, as the essence of being and existence, is the origin of the structure of existence, and every being must benefit from this origin in order to exist. According to Tillich, we are able to know God because of the theory of the similarity of being, which means that what is infinite is the essence of being and everything has benefited from this essence of being. In any case, this theory is a reason for everything we can say about God under the fact that "God must be understood as the essence of being." Existence and Christ in Systematic Theology

In this section, Tillich presents the discussion of Christology and cognitive salvation from the perspective of existentialism. Contrary to the existing tradition, he examines the person and act of Christ as a single and unique whole. Christology is considered a part of the discussion of cognitive salvation. According to Tillich, since existentialist thought presents an analysis of the meaning of existence (to exist), and since Tillich, as a philosopher of life, his approach to the relationship between religion and belief is based on existence, he therefore connects Christian theology to existentialist thought. Tillich's philosophical theology consists of interpreting the symbols of Christianity through his own understanding of Christian existentialism. Tillich considers existentialism to be the result of a conflict and confrontation with Hegel's idea of absolute essential authenticity. A prominent point in existentialist thought is the state of man's separation from his

inherent nature. Tillich considers Hegel's philosophy invalid because it is based on the idea that not only has the rupture prevailed, but only in this way does human existence conform to its true being. Existentialism is an analysis of the human predicament and the answer to this human predicament lies in religion, and Tillich, as a theologian, prefers to seek this answer in the symbol of the "message of Christ." Existentialist thought revived the classical Christian interpretation of human existence, as shown in the myth of the fall. Both existentialism and Christianity analyze and examine the nature of human existence, so there is a natural union between them. This is a reason for Tillich's adherence to the method of correlation, by which, through existential analysis, he elucidates the ultimate attachment of man and the process of revealing a new being in Jesus Christ, which is the answer to human predicament.

Transition from essence to being in existentialist theology

Transition from essence to being in existentialist theology is considered very important, and the symbol of the fall, according to Tillich, is very suitable for depicting this concept. However, in interpreting this symbol, Tillich does not accept the literal interpretation and believes that textualism (the originality of the text) destroys their religious and religious meanings in dealing with symbols and myths. The story of Genesis expresses human awareness of the discontinuity of existence, which implicitly contains a plan for how to transition from essence to being. From the perspective of limited freedom, human existence is contrary to its inherent nature, and it is this limited freedom that makes the transition from essence to being possible. Tillich describes the state before the fall using psychological terms such as "dreaming innocence." The word dream is a metaphor for describing the state of inherent existence, and innocence also refers to the unactualized power. According to Tillich, the symbol of Adam before the fall should be seen as a dreamlike innocence, unlimited possibilities. With the actualization of limited freedom, which is achieved through the awareness of finitude and anxiety, dreamlike innocence is lost. When humanity decided to actualize itself, it ended dreamlike innocence.

Conclusion:

In the era of late modernity, humanity has found itself facing a fundamental crisis; a crisis that includes not only the loss of meaning and value, but also the loss of trust in traditional explanatory systems, whether religion, classical metaphysics, or even modern science. This research was an attempt to examine different philosophical paths to overcome the existential crisis of modern man in the light of the thoughts of four prominent thinkers – Jean-Paul Sartre, Karl Marx, Søren Kierkegaard, and Paul Tillich. A comparative analysis of these approaches showed that there are different ways of dealing with anxiety, emptiness, freedom and the possibility of meaning, each of which relies on its own

ontology, anthropology and metaphysics. On the one hand, Sartre and Marx, as representatives of the atheistic-materialist approach, seek meaning not in the discovery of a transcendent reality, but in the uprising of individual consciousness or the change of socio-economic structures. Sartre, by declaring that “man is condemned to freedom”, considers the meaning of existence to be a self-created matter and sees God as an obstacle to man’s self-foundation. From his point of view, existential anxiety arises from the perception of this absolute freedom that falls on the shoulders of the individual without a metaphysical refuge. Marx, too, in the paradigm of historical materialism, sees meaning in social action and the removal of man’s alienation through social revolution; In other words, the existential crisis is tied to man's place in the relations of production, not to his relationship with the transcendent.

On the other hand, Kierkegaard and Tillich, emphasizing faith, lived experience, and the depth of man's being, seek to recover meaning through man's relationship with absolute being. Kierkegaard, with his "leap of faith," emphasizes that the way out of existential despair is not through rebellion, but through accepting the void and then leaping into the realm of faith; a faith that is irrational, personal, and risky. Tillich, too, by combining Christian theology and philosophical ontology, shows that existential anxiety is not a sign of failure, but a sign of a meaningful depth. In his view, faith, as the "ultimate surrender" to the foundation of existence, guides man from the level of the threat of nothingness to the depth of meaning.

The conceptual analysis of these four perspectives showed that existentialism is not a coherent school, but a tension-generating and dialogue-oriented field in which seemingly opposing tendencies can be involved in a common question: How can man give meaning to his life in a world that is de-centered and devoid of a priori poles? This question carries within itself the possibility of a dialogue between two main approaches: active atheism and existential faith. The key point of this research is that perhaps the final answer to the existential crisis lies not in the complete negation of God nor in the reduction of freedom, but in rethinking man's relationship with existence, consciousness, society, and The transcendent. Each of these thinkers has opened a window onto an aspect of the human condition, and the richness of their thought can be a platform for philosophy to open up to the various dimensions of human experience. This article has shown that the possibility of overcoming the existential crisis depends on a deeper understanding of man: a being who, while free, seeks roots, and in the heart of despair, thirsts for meaning.

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